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How Law Supports Worker-Driven Social Responsibility as Private Labor Governance:

An Examination of the Role of Contract and Courts in the Fair Food Program and Bangladesh Accord

This Paper is equivalent to a Thesis (for LL.M. graduates without a thesis)

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Abstract

The lack of legal protections for workers—whether due to the absence of law or poor enforcement of it—has allowed labor exploitation to flourish in a variety of contexts. The private monitoring and enforcement model, worker-driven social responsibility (WSR), has provided a novel contract-based solution. WSR enables workers to bargain with firms that control supply chains, then create legally enforceable contracts that require the firms to source from suppliers that protect workers' rights. Although one WSR initiative has been a shining success, the model has not proved to be easily replicable. Neither has it shown to be sustainable in global supply chains. In the pursuit of solutions to WSR's expansion problem, the literature has focused primarily on non-legal background conditions, as most scholars examining WSR understand the model to operate almost entirely outside the ambit of law. This work aims to explore whether WSR and law are in fact discrete operations through a case study analysis of two WSR initiatives—the Fair Food Program and the Bangladesh Accord, which govern a domestic and a global supply chain, respectively. This thesis argues that contract law and courts play a role in the ability of WSR to form and function. WSR depends on relational contract and associated informal sanctions (trade group exclusion and reputational harm). The relational contract, in turn, depends on the legal contract, which serves to reduce costs and signal trustworthiness. Furthermore, a friendly relationship between private and public institutions also contributes to the sustainability of WSR. The jurisdictional complexities of transnational supply chains introduce additional tensions that make the public-private relationship more likely to become hostile, as does the exclusion of non-signatory suppliers from the relational contract. Finally, I offer recommendations for WSR proponents that consider the contract and legal environment in which WSR is embedded.

INTRODUCTION

The lack of legal protections for workers—whether due to the absence of law or poor enforcement of it—has allowed labor exploitation to flourish in a variety of labor-repressive¹ contexts. The problem is accentuated in supply chains where employers are under intense pressure from financially powerful lead firms to produce at ever-cheaper prices, despite damages to workers’ safety and wellbeing.² The private monitoring and enforcement model, worker-driven social responsibility (WSR), has provided a novel contract-based solution. WSR enables workers to bargain with firms that control supply chains, then create legally enforceable contracts that require the firms to source from suppliers that protect workers’ rights. Although one WSR initiative has been a shining success, the model has not proved to be easily replicable. Neither has it shown to be sustainable in global supply chains. In the pursuit of solutions to WSR’s expansion problem, the literature has focused primarily on non-legal background conditions, as most scholars examining WSR understand the model to operate almost entirely outside the ambit of law. This work aims to explore whether WSR and law are in fact discrete operations through a case study analysis of two WSR initiatives—the Fair Food Program and the Bangladesh Accord, which govern a domestic and a global supply chain, respectively. The thesis focuses on contract law and the role of courts in particular because WSR is a contract-based private governance scheme.

WSR is a novel form of private labor governance that has proved dramatically successful at reducing workplace abuses,³ and is regarded by many scholars and labor activists

¹ Janice Fine & Tim Bartley, *Raising the floor: New directions in public and private enforcement of labor standards in the United States*, 61 J. OF INDUS. REL. 252, 262 (2018) (describing Florida’s tomato industry as a labor-repressive environment because agricultural workers are exempted from key labor law protections).

² OXFAM AMERICA, *Like Machines in the Fields: Workers without Rights in American Agriculture*, 1, 26 (2004), <https://s3.amazonaws.com/oxfam-us/www/static/media/files/like-machines-in-the-fields.pdf>; INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION, *Purchasing practices and working conditions in global supply chains: Global Survey results (INWORK Issue Brief No.10)*, 1, 8 (2017), https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---travail/documents/publication/wcms_556336.pdf (showing that 52% of Bangladeshi garment suppliers reported selling below cost because of price pressure from lead firms).

³ The Fair Food Program, the flagship WSR program, has eradicated modern slavery conditions, such as pistol whippings, forced labor, coercive debt practices, and sexual violence. See Greg Asbed & Steve Hitov, *Preventing Forced Labor in Corporate Supply Chains: The Fair Food Program and Worker-driven Social Responsibility*, 52 WAKE FOREST L. REV. 497, 509 (2017), https://ciw-online.org/wp-content/uploads/HitovAsbedArticle_AuthorCopy.pdf. The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh, the second most prominent WSR program, has also dramatically improve garment workers’ safety conditions in factories in Bangladesh. See PAUL BARRETT ET AL., *Five Years After Rana Plaza: The Way Forward*, (2018), <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/547df270e4b0>

as the most promising and viable model of labor governance in value chains to date.⁴ The first and most prominent instance of it, the Fair Food Program (FFP), has operated in the tomato fields in the U.S. state of Florida since 2011. The FFP transformed the tomato fields from what the Department of Justice called “ground zero for modern slavery”⁵ to some of the best agricultural working conditions in the nation.⁶

WSR is premised on the idea that contracting with lead firms has the power to improve workers’ conditions because lead firms control the flow of money and resources throughout supply chains.⁷ The WSR model, which the FFP pioneered, operates by empowering workers to bargain with⁸ lead firms to create enforceable contracts that hold lead firms responsible for the treatment of their suppliers’ employees.⁹ The contracts require lead firms to limit their

ba184dfc490e/t/5ac9514eaa4a998f3f30ae13/1523143088805/NYU+Bangladesh+Rana+Plaza+Report.pdf (showing the Accord dramatically reduced building safety accidents).

⁴ Aaron Gladstone, *Worker Driven Social Responsibility Agreements: A New Future in Labor Rights Protections*, 44 *FORDHAM INT’L L.J.* 549 (2020); Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3; Jeremy Blasi & Jennifer Bair, *An Analysis of Multiparty Bargaining Models for Global Supply Chains*, Conditions of Work and Employment Series No. 105, INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION 1, 15–20, 36 (2019), https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---travail/documents/publication/wcms_655541.pdf; DANIEL M. BRINKS ET AL., POWER, PARTICIPATION, AND PRIVATE REGULATORY INITIATIVES: HUMAN RIGHTS UNDER SUPPLY CHAIN CAPITALISM 1 (2021); Kathryn Babineau & Jennifer Bair, *The art of using supply chains to defend worker rights*, OPENDEMOCRACY (2020), <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/beyond-trafficking-and-slavery/art-using-supply-chains-defend-worker-rights/>; Karin Astrid Siegmann et al., *Civic Innovation in Value Chains: Towards Workers as Agents in Non-governmental Labour Regulation*, in *EXPLORING CIVIC INNOVATION FOR SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION* 109 (Kees Biekart, Wendy Harcourt, & Peter Knorringa eds., 2016).

⁵ John Bowe, *Nobodies: Does slavery exist in America?*, *THE NEW YORKER*, April 13, 2003, <http://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2003/04/21/nobodies> (referring to a Justice Department official’s reference to South Florida farms as “ground zero for modern slavery”).

⁶ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 509; FAIR FOOD STANDARDS COUNCIL, *Fair Food 2017 Annual Report* (hereinafter FFSC 2017 Report), FAIRFOODPROGRAM.ORG (2017), <https://fairfoodprogram.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/>

<Fair-Food-Program-2017-Annual-Report-Final.pdf>; FAIR FOOD STANDARDS COUNCIL (hereinafter FFSC 2021 Report), *Fair Food 2021 Annual Report*, 1, 31 (2021), https://adobeindd.com/view/publications/2e8c5302-3772-4122-a6a7-f345d4801a16/4tfw/publication-web-resources/pdf/FFP_2021_SOTP_REPORT_Final_TO_PRINT_8.26.21.pdf.

26.21.pdf; Sean Sellers & Greg Asbed, *The Fair Food Program: Comprehensive, Verifiable and Sustainable Change for Farmworkers*, 16 *U. PA. J.L. & SOC. CHANGE* 29 (2013), <https://scholarship.law.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1159&context=jlasc>; SUSAN L. MARQUIS, *I AM NOT A TRACTOR! HOW FLORIDA FARMWORKERS TOOK ON THE FAST FOOD GIANTS AND WON* 1, 169–70 (2017).

⁷ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 509.

⁸ Manoj Dias-Abey, *Using law to support social-movement-led collective bargaining structures in supply chains*, 32 *AUSTL. J. OF LAB. L.* 123 *1 (2019), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3400564> (saying WSR represents a nascent form of supply chain collective bargaining).

⁹ OXFAM AMERICA, *supra* note 2 at 10 (describing how the Coalition of Immokalee Workers built the FFP only after realizing that the slavery conditions in Florida were not going to be solved through one-off criminal cases, but through targeting lead firms that held the power to change workers’ treatment).

purchases to suppliers that WSR continuously adhere to a strict Code of Conduct that establishes workers' rights. The program ensures Code compliance through multiple, robust monitoring mechanisms. WSR is then enforced via a combination of contract and market sanctions, as well as reputational pressures. Workers' organizations can sue noncompliant lead firms for contract breach, and the workers' organization can require the lead firms to stop buying from noncompliant suppliers.¹⁰ Reputational pressures from consumers and civil society make it desirable for lead firms to join a WSR program and remain in it.¹¹

The WSR model was designed to operate as a private replacement for lack of public labor governance.¹² According to WSR's designers, the model should be adaptable to various supply chains and locales because of its private nature.¹³ However, the model has so far failed to be widely diffused into more chains and to remain viable in longer, global value chains. Researchers have emphasized the importance of suitable market conditions for WSR's viability, pointing specifically to the importance of a consolidated market with a small number of lead firms where consumers are willing to pressure lead firms into signing WSR contracts.¹⁴

The conventional understanding of WSR holds that it operates as separate and distinct from public governance, thus freeing it from the constraints and prejudices of any single legal system and the strictures of transnational considerations or differing legal norms.¹⁵ A small but budding trend in the literature questions the assertion that WSR is divorced from law, arguing instead that law has played a substantial role in the creation and operation of WSR.¹⁶

¹⁰ Asbed and Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 510 & 526.

¹¹ Siegmann et al., *supra* note 4 at 122–23.

¹² Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 526.

¹³ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 526–27.

¹⁴ Siegmann et al., *supra* note 4 at 122–23; Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 507 n.66, 526–27, 529–31; Manoj Dias-Abey, *Justice on Our Fields: Can “Alt-Labor” Organizations Improve Migrant Farm Workers’ Conditions?*, 53 HARV. CIV. RIGHTS-CIVIL LIB. LAW REV. 167, 209 (2018), http://www.labourlawresearch.net/sites/default/files/papers/FINAL_Justice%20on%20our%20Fields-2%20copy.pdf.

¹⁵ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 526–27 (stating the intent of WSR's architects was to design a program with near-complete divorce from a country's legal system because of the prejudice of the American legal system against marginalized farmworkers and the potential for WSR to harness market power transnationally); Siegmann et al., *supra* note 4 at 122–23 (noting that although the FFP is based on enforceable contracts, it relies on reputational pressure from consumers to get lead firms at the top of the supply chain to join the FFP and spark wider acceptance of it); Marquis, *supra* note 6 at 222 (“[The CIW’s success] ... shows the need for, and the power of, novel solutions in those policy areas where the nature of government may mean the solution cannot come through government mechanism. Government do many things well, but they cannot solve every societal problem.”).

¹⁶ Manoj Dias-Abey, *A Socio-Legal History of the Coalition of Immokalee Workers*, in *THEORISING LABOUR LAW IN A CHANGING WORLD: TOWARDS INCLUSIVE LABOUR LAW* (Alysia Blackham et al. ed., 2019); Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8; Jaakko Salminen, *The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh: A New Paradigm for Limiting*

While acknowledging the importance of market dynamics and consumers' influence on the success and replicability of WSR, this work attempts to probe the yet uncharted territory of how public legal governance plays a part in WSR's story. Specifically, how and to what extent do legal contractual mechanisms, such as arbitration and choice of forum and law, and public legal institutions, like the relationship WSR has with courts, support or hinder WSR? I answer this question by detailing the interactions of public governance and private WSR governance in two case studies: the Fair Food Program (FFP) and the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh ("Bangladesh Accord" or simply "Accord"). I propose that public-private interactions are key to this project because they reveal when a public legal system is supporting (through complementarity, cooperation, or coordination) or hindering (through displacement or competition) a WSR case, while unveiling the public institutions' disposition toward the WSR program and its impact. Through granular articulation and analysis of the two WSR programs in their sociopolitical and legal contexts, this work explores how underlying legal structures (public governance institutions) have interacted with the WSR programs.

Specifically, the thesis argues that WSR relies on contract law and structures—including arbitration clauses, choices of law and forum, and the mechanical and relational facets of contract—as background rules that facilitate it. Contract law is the focus here, as opposed to other legal fields, because WSR is distinguished from other labor governance methods by its creation of legally enforceable contracts. I also examine how the public-private governance interactions regarding contract differ in WSR's governance of domestic value chains (as in the FFP) versus global ones (as in the Accord), such as in the context of private international law considerations for arbitration-based adjudication. Toward the end of this thesis, I present a synthesized set of recommendations for how WSR proponents ought to approach a legal system so as to cultivate a public-private interaction that enables WSR's work.

This project implements a case study analysis of two relevant WSR programs to identify the legal factors that have supported or hindered their success. This is a particularly apt method for rich and contextualized analysis of phenomena, and, as researchers have noted, it is a useful

Buyers' Liability in Global Supply Chains?, 66 AM. J. OF COMP. L. 411 (2018) (arguing in small part that the power of courts will become increasingly important as labor governance is shifted to private hands through contracts, thereby re-centering the power of courts to interpret labor rights through contract); Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 (suggesting briefly that governments may help WSR take hold in markets where reputationally-based social campaigns are difficult to achieve due to industrial complexity).

method for drawing descriptive inferences.¹⁷ The limitations of this method—namely that it is a very small sample and there are relevant differences beyond law that cannot be isolated—admittedly make it difficult to draw conclusive inferences. However, the availability of the information makes case study a realistic method to conduct an analysis of WSR. Specifically, there have only been four WSR programs to date, including the FFP and the Accord. The other two WSR cases are less helpful for this analysis, as they are either too new for sufficient information to be available¹⁸ or too limited to indicate broader significance.¹⁹ Further, I have chosen the two case studies because each is the longest-lasting or most successful²⁰ of the WSR programs instituted. The FFP (which governs a domestic value chain) has led a successful operation for over a decade, while the Accord (which governs a global value chain) was prematurely transferred to local authorities but had previously made significant improvements to workers’ occupational safety conditions. Thus, the choice of method and WSR programs make it possible to examine the contrasting legal circumstances of the longevity of the WSR program and transnationality of its governed value chain.

Countering the common perception that the FFP emerged as a private enforcement system divorced from state involvement, Manoj Dias-Abey, a jurist and labor rights researcher, has analyzed the role of law within WSR governance. He argues that the “discursive” power of U.S. anti-trafficking law and the “symbolic” power of law—derived from interactions between the FFP’s founding group and the public governance institutions—were crucial resources in the creation of the FFP.²¹ I contribute to this burgeoning strain in the literature by examining how contract law, as well as the public-private interactions between the FFP and

¹⁷ For more information on the case study method see, e.g., Bent Flyvbjerg, *Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research*, 12 QUALITATIVE INQUIRY 219 (2006); John Gerring, *What is the Case Study and What is it Good For?*, 98 AM. POL. SCI. REV. 341 (2004); KHUSHAL VIBHUTE & FILIPOS AYNALAM, LEGAL RESEARCH METHODS: TEACHING MATERIAL 141 (2009), <https://chilot.files.wordpress.com/2011/06/legal-research-methods.pdf>.

¹⁸ The Gender Justice Program (GJP) in Lesotho began in 2019 but no academic studies of it have been published. For more information about the GJP, see Tula Connell, *Lesotho Plan Has All Elements to End GBV at Work*, SOLIDARITY CENTER (2019), <https://www.solidaritycenter.org/lesotho-plan-has-all-elements-to-end-gbv-at-work/>.

¹⁹ Milk with Dignity (MD) in Vermont, U.S. began in 2017 and involves only one domestic value chain (Ben & Jerry’s northeastern U.S. dairy production). For more information about MD, see MILK WITH DIGNITY & MIGRANT JUSTICE, *First Biennial Report: 2018-2019*, 1 (2020), <https://milkwithdignity.org/sites/default/files/2020-MDReport.pdf>.

²⁰ Throughout this work, the “success” of a WSR project refers to how well it has reduced labor exploitation for the workers the WSR project intends to protect, as determined in the WSR’s project annual reports for compliance and defect remediation.

²¹ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14.

the Accord, have provided structural support to the two cases of WSR. While law cannot be hailed as the singular reason for WSR's success²² or blamed entirely for its failure, it would be a disservice to the WSR replication effort to leave the role of law unexamined. To analyze how law may facilitate a program designed to be—and conventionally understood to be—separate from law is a pursuit made worthwhile by its potential to better explain how WSR may be supported in new and varied legal contexts.

The implications of this research may inform WSR advocates and leadership to adapt their efforts and contractual frameworks to better support WSR governance. This is a particularly relevant concern for workers, workers' rights activists, and other business and human rights stakeholders that seek to improve work in value chains extending through labor-repressive jurisdictions. In other words, where labor law fails to address these concerns, contract law provides an alternative legal, albeit private, route to protect workers' rights.

The structure of the work will be as follows: The first part provides a review of the relevant literature on the labor governance deficit in value chains, the corporate social responsibility method as the primary attempt at a governance solution, and the WSR model as a response to the problems of corporate social responsibility. This first part also lays the theoretical foundation for the analysis, outlining the literature on the conceptualizations of the interactions between public and private labor governance regimes. The second part engages the question of how contract and public institutions interact with WSR. It first examines each case study individually, in terms of relevant legal contract structures and the courts that interpret and enforce contract. Then, it proceeds to conduct a comparative analysis of the two case studies, identifying the legal factors that may have contributed to the differing outcomes in each. The third part discusses the recommendations for how WSR proponents may foster more beneficial interactions between WSR and public governance, even where labor law may be antagonistic toward workers' rights. The fourth and final part finishes the thesis with some concluding thoughts on the way forward with WSR and WSR research.

PART 1. LITERATURE REVIEW

This Part presents a two-pronged literature review that lays the theoretical foundation for this work. In the first subpart, I address the fields fundamental to understanding WSR. This includes the labor governance deficit in supply chains and the prominent corporate social

²² Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14 at 16.

responsibility (CSR) model as a governance attempt. I then present the WSR approach and how it distinguishes itself from CSR, while laying out the challenges that WSR has faced, particularly as to replication and sustainability. Finally, I summarize some prominent analyses by scholars on WSR's replication problem and the nascent literature on the relationship between WSR and law.

The second subpart continues the literature review with a more theoretical lens. I address how scholars have conceptualized the interaction of public and private governance. In particular, I explain two relevant articles that provide helpful classifications of public-private interactions. Together, the two prongs of this Part provide the necessary elements to understand the analysis that follows.

1.1. Worker-Driven Social Responsibility: Origins and Operations

First, it is crucial to understand why many scholars consider WSR to be an innovative and important development in addressing labor exploitation in value chains. Before that, though, a couple of clarifications are in order: what are value chains and why labor exploitation has proliferated in them. Then, I present the CSR governance model because it is the conventional private governance mechanism currently utilized to govern labor abuses in value chains. I also draw attention to the criticism directed against the CSR governance model. Finally, I introduce the WSR model as a novel alternative to CSR, highlighting how the model distinguishes itself.

Supply chains and value chains are dynamic supply and demand networks created by various players to design, produce, and distribute products to end consumers.²³ The concept of value chains in particular attempts to capture the added value that is created from, *inter alia*, the sourcing and manufacturing conditions of the end products.²⁴ These chains may be either domestic or global, extending exclusively within the bounds of a nation²⁵—being domestic value chains (DVCs)—or across national borders²⁶—constituting global value chains (GVCs).

²³ ANDREW FELLER, DAN SHUNK & TOM CALLARMAN, *Value Chains Versus Supply Chains*, BPTRENDS 1 (2006), <https://www.bptrends.com/bpt/wp-content/publicationfiles/03-06-ART-ValueChains-SupplyChains-Feller.pdf>.

²⁴ Gary Gereffi et al., *The governance of global value chains*, 12 REV. OF INT'L POL. ECON. 78, 79–80 (2005).

²⁵ Cosimo Beverelli et al., *Domestic Foundations of Global Value Chains*, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION (2015), <http://rigvc.uibe.edu.cn/docs/20160329200657581121.pdf>.

²⁶ Gary Gereffi et al., *supra* note 24.

The chains may be relatively simple or complex, referring to how many suppliers or nodes are present in the chain.

The current structure of labor law, which governs the relationships between employers and groups of employees (usually in unions), generally does not protect employees' rights as against lead firms or hold them accountable for their suppliers' treatment of employees.²⁷ Since unions source their power in part from public governance (through legally-enforceable collective bargaining agreements),²⁸ unions have little leverage to reduce the labor governance deficit in value chains, which disconnect workers from lead firms. Additionally, the current structure of employment law, which governs the relationship between employers and individual employees, does not account for work relationships that are not direct employment. Thus, workers have no labor or employment law rights (collectively referred to as "work law" rights) toward the firms up the value chain with whom they have no direct employment relationship.

The lack of work law protections outside of direct employment is a particularly acute vulnerability for workers who are already marginalized, such as migrant or informal workers. Marginalized workers are often excluded from work law (that would otherwise protect them in their direct employment relationships) because of their type of work or their immigration status.²⁹ Lack of enforcement of applicable work laws also challenges the feasibility of ensuring workers' rights in labor-repressive jurisdictions,³⁰ whether due to lack of resources for public institutions or lack of political will. In GVCs, workers face additional challenges in asserting their work rights. GVC production centers are mostly concentrated in Global South countries,³¹ which have additional national pressures to maintain cheap and loosely regulated

²⁷ This caveat is added because there are some extremely limited protections for when a "secondary" employer (any employer that is not a direct or "primary" employer) is an "ally" of a primary employer. For more information, see National Labor Relations Act of 1935 (hereinafter NLRA), 29 U.S.C. §§ 158 at 8(b)(4).

²⁸ Virginia Doellgast & Chiara Benassi, *Collective bargaining*, in HANDBOOK OF RESEARCH ON EMPLOYEE VOICE (Adrian Wilkinson ed., 2023).

²⁹ An example is farmworkers' exclusion from U.S. federal NLRA protections. See NLRA, *supra* note 27 at § 152(3) (excluding agricultural laborers). Another example is undocumented workers' exclusion from the protection of labor law. See *Hoffman Plastic Compounds, Inc. v. National Labor Relations Board*, 535 U.S. 137 (2002).

³⁰ Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 (describing Florida's tomato industry as a labor-repressive environment because agricultural workers are exempted from key labor law protections).

³¹ The Global South refers to typically low- and middle-income nations in Latin America, Asia, Africa, and Oceania. Although the term is not perfectly accurate, it attempts to be a value-free alternative to those terms and better reflects patterns of colonial relations that influence business and geopolitics today. For in-depth analyses, see DIANA MITLIN & DAVID SATTERTHWAITE, *URBAN POVERTY IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH: SCALE AND NATURE* 1,

labor forces to attract foreign business, typically from multinational firms based in Global North countries.³² A combination of the above factors has resulted in a lack of legal oversight or public regulation protecting workers in value chains. Scholars specializing in value chain governance, such as Gary Gereffi and Frederick Mayer, refer to this as the labor “governance deficit” in value chains.³³ I adopt this term in my work.

The labor governance deficit in value chains has inspired a range of governance attempts. The most prominent of these, and the most relevant to this thesis, is the corporate social responsibility (CSR) model. Note, however, that the “corporate” in CSR is used broadly to refer to not only legally incorporated business entities, but any for-profit firm. It is a private governance method, meaning it decenters the state’s governance role, by having non-state actors take on some or all of the governance duties in a regulatory field.³⁴ In the CSR model, corporations themselves are the primary non-state governance actors. CSR is best described in the words of the European Commission, as “a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis”.³⁵ CSR emphasizes corporations’ social responsibilities toward their workers and the communities in which they operate.

13 (2013); NAHZEEM OLUWAFEMI MIMIKO, *GLOBALIZATION: THE POLITICS OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS AND INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS* 1, 47 (2012); M.D. Litonjua, *Third World/Global South: From Modernization, to Dependency/Liberation, to Postdevelopment*, 29 *J. OF THIRD WORLD STUD.* 25 (2012).

³² Mark Anner, *Squeezing workers’ rights in global supply chains: purchasing practices in the Bangladesh garment export sector in comparative perspective*, 27 *REV. OF INT’L POL. ECON.* 320, 326 (2019) (describing how GVCs create pressures on suppliers and supplier-host states to keep wages down and unions out in order to attract and keep investors); David Graham & Ngaire Woods, *Making corporate self-regulation effective in developing countries*, 34 *WORLD DEV.* 868 (2006), <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/196277/1/GEG-WP-014.pdf>; Tim Bartley & Doug Kincaid, *The Mobility of Industries and the Limits of Corporate Social Responsibility: Labor Codes of Conduct in Indonesian Factories*, in *CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN A GLOBALIZING WORLD: GLOBAL DYNAMICS AND LOCAL PRACTICES* 393–429 (Kiyoteru Tsutsui & Alwyn Lim eds., 2015).

³³ Gary Gereffi & Frederick Mayer, *Globalization and the Demand for Governance*, in *THE NEW OFFSHORING OF JOBS AND GLOBAL DEVELOPMENT* 39, 48–49 (Gary Gereffi ed., 2005).

³⁴ Julia Black, *Decentering Regulation: Understanding the Role of Regulation and Self-Regulation in a “Post-Regulatory” World*, 54 *CURRENT LEGAL PROBS.* 103, 118 (2001), <https://academic.oup.com/clp/article-abstract/54/1/103/400274?redirectedFrom=fulltext>; Fabrizio Cafaggi, *New Foundations of Transnational Private Regulation*, 38 *J. OF L. AND SOC’Y.* 20, 39–40 (2011), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23030395>.

³⁵ COMMISSION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES, *Promoting a European framework for Corporate Social Responsibility (Green Paper)*, *EUROPARL.EUROPA.EU* 1, para. 20 (2001), [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meet/docs/committees/deve/20020122/com\(2001\)366_en.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meet/docs/committees/deve/20020122/com(2001)366_en.pdf).

Although CSR has been implemented in a variety of ways in multiple regulatory fields since its first applications in the 1980s,³⁶ CSR for governance of labor exploitation typically works via two primary mechanisms. First, firms may create codes of conduct to establish “good practices” or “beliefs” of the firm. Second, firms may choose to audit their suppliers and disclose their findings to civil society.³⁷ It is important to note that since the CSR model has not been a concerted, unified effort, the real-world application of these two has been inconsistent. Not every firm’s CSR program has these characteristics—and when they do—they are not identical.

A CSR code of conduct communicates the firm’s stance on their responsibilities to the workers under their direct employment and sometimes extends this to apply to the workers along their value chain. The codes encapsulate “good practices” that the firms purportedly value. Firms that wish to extend the code’s provisions to the suppliers in their value chains may choose to hire auditors to confirm compliance. However, the social audit industry is infamously plagued by conflicts of interest,³⁸ since the auditors are inherently interested in securing the recurring business from the lead firms that hire them and the lead firms’ interest is to protect their reputation. The “checking” mechanism—should a firm engage in questionable labor practices or source from a supplier engaging in labor exploitation—is supposed to be reputational damage inflicted by civil society, resulting in monetary losses. In practice, however, the reputational damages do not always work, such as when information on the labor practices is inconclusive, fragmentary, or even deliberately concealed.³⁹ The critiques of CSR form an extensive body of literature beyond the scope of this review, but the most common and

³⁶ Mauricio Andrés Latapí Agudelo et al., *A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility*, 4 INT’L J. OF CORP. SOC. RESP. 1, 6–7 (2019), <https://jcsr.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40991-018-0039-y>; Debora L. Spar & Jennifer Burns, *Hitting the Wall: Nike and International Labor Practices*, HARVARD BUSINESS SCHOOL CASE 700-047 (2000), <https://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Pages/item.aspx?num=26875>; Sandra Waddock, *Corporate Citizenship*, in CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND RELATED TERMS 1, 29 (2007), https://www.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-binaries/41167_1.pdf.

³⁷ Waddock, *supra* note 36.

³⁸ BRIAN FINNEGAN, *Responsibility Outsourced: Social Audits, Workplace Certification and Twenty Years of Failure to Protect Worker Rights*, 1 (2014), <https://aflcio.org/sites/default/files/2017-03/CSRReport.pdf>.

³⁹ Corporations often over-emphasize positive findings in their reports and attempt to give consumers a positive impression of the firm’s ethical stance in lieu of real change. See Steve J. New, *Modern Slavery and Supply Chain Transparency*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT 1 (Thomas Y. Choi et al. eds., 2020); Joanne Meehan & Bruce D. Pinnington, *Modern Slavery in Supply Chains: Insights through Strategic Ambiguity*, 41 INT’L J. OF OPERATIONS & PROD. MGMT. 1 (2021); Kimberly D. Elsbach, *Organizational Perception Management*, 25 RESEARCH IN ORG. BEHAV. 297 (2003); Shobod Deba Nath, Gabriel Eweje & Aymen Sajjad, *The Hidden Side of Sub-Supplier Firms’ Sustainability – an Empirical Analysis*, 40 INT’L J. OF OPERATIONS & PROD. MGMT. 1771 (2020).

pointed are that CSR is little more than performative, well-publicized window-dressing that prioritizes firms' reputation over workers' wellbeing.⁴⁰

Multi-stakeholder initiatives (MSIs) arose from a critique of CSR during the 2000s, which argued that CSR is unilaterally controlled by corporations without external oversight.⁴¹ MSIs introduced a multiparty model, involving not only businesses (especially lead firms), but also trade unions, non-governmental organizations, and sometimes states, in the standards-setting process (i.e., creating the codes of conduct). They often include a certification program for vetted products, like a fair-trade label.⁴² Some scholars consider WSR to be a form of MSI because it involves workers in the process of creating and monitoring compliance with codes of conduct.⁴³ However, not all MSIs involve workers to the extent that WSR does or have the binding contractual power that characterizes WSR and distinguishes it from other labor governance attempts.

To be clear, many other attempts to solve the labor governance deficit in value chains have been developed and are in operation,⁴⁴ but they are not directly pertinent to WSR. Instead, I have focused on the CSR model because the creators of WSR designed it in pointed response to CSR's failures.⁴⁵

⁴⁰ Jennifer Gordon, *The Problem with Corporate Social Responsibility* 1 (2017), <https://wsr-network.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Gordon-CSR-vs-WSR-FINAL-July-2017.pdf> (an updated and expanded version of "The Problem with MSIs," a public talk given by the author on June 11, 2014, at the Open Society Foundations, New York City); DAVID HENDERSON, MISGUIDED VIRTUE: FALSE NOTIONS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY 1, 25 (2001); Peter Benson & Stuart Kirsch, *Capitalism and the Politics of Resignation*, 51 CURRENT ANTHROPOLOGY 459, 466 (2010); Benedict Sheehy, *Defining CSR: Problems and Solutions*, 131 J. OF BUS. ETHICS 625 (2014), <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10551-014-2281-x>; JED GREER & KENNY BRUNO, GREENWASH: REALITY BEHIND CORPORATE ENVIRONMENTALISM (2000); Stephen John New, *Modern slavery and the supply chain: the limits of corporate social responsibility?*, 20(6) SUPPLY CHAIN MGMT. 697 (2015); JEAN ALLAIN et al., *Forced Labour's Business Models and Supply Chains*, Joseph ROWNTREE FOUNDATION AND QUEENS UNIVERSITY (2013); TIM BARTLEY, RULES WITHOUT RIGHTS: LAND, LABOR, AND PRIVATE AUTHORITY IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY (2018).

⁴¹ Gordon, *supra* note 40 at 2.

⁴² *Id.*

⁴³ Blasi & Bair, *supra* note 4 at 18–20.

⁴⁴ One may note the development of human rights due diligence legislation (HRDD). For a concise but comprehensive discussion of HRDD, see GENEVIEVE LEBARON et al., *Forced Labour Evidence Brief: Due Diligence and Transparency Legislation Drafting team*, 3 (2021), https://static1.squarespace.com/static/6055c0601c885456ba8c962a/t/61d71e46967f033bb694f6e5/1641487943126/ReStructureLab_DueDiligence_April2021_AW.pdf.

⁴⁵ Coalition of Immokalee Workers, *Worker-driven Social Responsibility (WSR): A new idea for a new century*, COALITION OF IMMOKALEE WORKERS (2014), <https://ciw-online.org/blog/2014/06/wsr/>; Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3.

I.I.A. WSR's Innovation

WSR offers a novel solution to the labor governance problem based on enabling workers to access lead firms and negotiate with them to create legally enforceable contracts. Dias-Abey refers to this as a nascent form of “supply chain collective bargaining” that allows workers to do what law does not enable them to do—bargain with the lead firms.⁴⁶ In terms of mechanics, WSR ensures workers’ labor rights are respected by: (i) allowing workers to negotiate employment conditions with the lead firms that source their products from the suppliers (workers’ direct employers), (ii) thereby creating legally binding contracts (iii) that establish mechanisms to ensure accurate monitoring of compliance and enforcement of labor standards. Consumers’ and workers’ influence are utilized to pressure lead firms to sign the WSR contracts. The WSR structure gives lead firms reputational assurance, while giving suppliers assurance that they may continue to sell to major lead firms. WSR thereby creates what I call a “trade group” of signatory lead firms and non-signatory suppliers that are committed to following the code of the WSR program.

Like CSR, WSR is a method of private governance because it decenters the state’s role in labor governance. In contrast to CSR, however, WSR does not rely on corporate-made codes of conduct or corporate self-regulation. Workers’ voice is instead centered within the process of standard-setting, monitoring, and enforcement, thereby drawing on their lived experiences.⁴⁷ For instance, the model implements worker-to-worker education, equipping workers to become ground-level monitors of their rights.⁴⁸ As Janice Fine has argued, worker involvement is important in part because the workers are in the best position to know what is happening on the ground (and state investigation and audit mechanisms will never have the resources to reach the same information), and worker-based organizations generate more trust than the state can.⁴⁹ An oversight body run by the workers’ organization operates thorough workplace audits and a 24-hour hotline free from the lead firms’ control, and makes decisions on whether suppliers may continue to participate in the WSR program. A scaling fee, charged to the lead firms, may

⁴⁶ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 14.

⁴⁷ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 514.

⁴⁸ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 518.

⁴⁹ See Janice Fine (hereinafter Fine 2018), *New Approaches to Enforcing Labor Standards: How Co-enforcement Partnerships between Government and Civil Society Are Showing the Way Forward*, 2017 U. CHI. LEGAL F. 143, 149–54 (2018), <https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1594&context=uclf>; Janice Fine (hereinafter Fine 2017), *Enforcing Labor Standards in Partnership with Civil Society: Can Co-enforcement Succeed Where the State Alone Has Failed?*, 45 POL. & SOC’Y 359, 364–66 (2017).

be used to fund the private governance program and/or to boost the workers' wages.⁵⁰ Regular reports from the WSR program's worker-run oversight body disclose to consumers and civil society the progress made on the ground.⁵¹

Thus, the WSR model offers a clear answer to the governance deficit by allowing workers to directly bargain with the lead firms that control the value chains in which they work. WSR distinguishes itself by its heavy involvement of workers throughout the governance process. Finally, the governance model improves the voluntary models of private governance like CSR and MSIs by imposing enforceable contractual obligations.

1.1.B. WSR's Replication Problem

The considerable number of articles written on the WSR model engage its innovative structure, praising the model particularly for its efficacy in addressing labor exploitation of marginalized workers, as well as securing enforcement and incorporating workers' voice and industrial democracy.⁵² Greg Asbed, cofounder of the FFP, and Steve Hitov, legal counsel for the FFP's parent group, the Coalition of Immokalee Workers (CIW),⁵³ wrote that the FFP "models an approach that can succeed in a multitude of low-wage environments around the globe".⁵⁴ To the architects of WSR, its expansion seems to be all but a matter of time. However, in the decade since the first WSR contract was signed, there have only been four WSR

⁵⁰ In the FFP, the price premium is used to increase the workers' wages, while the price premium in the Accord is used to fund the program and allow for suppliers to remediate.

⁵¹ See, e.g., regular reports from FFP at Fair Food Standards Council, *Reports*, FAIR FOOD STANDARDS (2021), <https://www.fairfoodstandards.org/reports/>. See also regular reports from the Milk with Dignity program at Migrant Justice, *Milk with Dignity turns 4 - and releases new report!*, MIGRANT JUSTICE/JUSTICIA MIGRANTE (2021), <https://migrantjustice.net/news/milk-with-dignity-turns-4-and-releases-new-report>.

⁵² See, e.g., Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14; Fabiola Mieres & Siobhán McGrath, *Ripe to be heard: Worker voice in the Fair Food Program*, 160 INT'L LAB. REV. (2021); Aaron Gladstone, *Worker Driven Social Responsibility Agreements: A New Future in Labor Rights Protections*, 44 FORDHAM INT'L L.J. 549 (2020); Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3; Babineau & Bair, *supra* note 4; Jennifer Bair et al., *The Political Economy of Private and Public Regulation in Post-Rana Plaza Bangladesh*, 73 ILR REV. 969, 980–81 (2020); Beryl Ter Haar & Maarten Keune, *One Step Forward or More Window-Dressing: A Legal Analysis of Recent CSR Initiatives in the Garment Industry in Bangladesh*, 30 INT'L J. OF COMP. LAB. L. AND INDUS. REL. 5 (2014), <https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.kluwer/clir0030&div=6&id=&page=>; James J. Brudney, *Decent Labour Standards in Corporate Supply Chains: The Immokalee Workers Model*, in TEMPORARY LABOUR MIGRATION IN THE GLOBAL ERA: THE REGULATORY CHALLENGES 351 (Joanna Howe & Rosemary Owens eds., 2016); see, e.g., Brishen Rogers, *Law and the Global Sweatshop Problem*, in ACHIEVING WORKERS' RIGHTS IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY (Richard P. Appelbaum & Nelson Lichtenstein eds., 2016); Blasi & Bair, *supra* note 4.

⁵³ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 497.

⁵⁴ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 531.

programs, and one was prematurely dismantled. It appears that WSR is not as easily replicable and sustainable as Asbed and Hitov had hoped.

Scholars have turned with particular interest to the question of how to expand WSR, especially into longer and more complex value chains. Jennifer Bair and Kathryn Babineau wrote an incisive post⁵⁵ related directly to WSR’s replicability problem, identifying four conditions under which the WSR can be replicated: First, where there is a willingness of consumers to put pressure on lead firms. Second, where the brands are consumer-facing (i.e., the lead firms are susceptible to civil society-backed campaign mobilization). Third, where there is unequal bargaining power of the lead firms vis-à-vis the suppliers, so the former can use their leverage against the latter to require them to meet Code standards. And fourth, Bair and Babineau refer to the existence of a “legal system with labor regulations (even if poorly enforced)” and a “functioning judicial regime capable of upholding the [WSR] agreements in the event of a dispute”.⁵⁶

Other authors homed in on the importance of some of these conditions even prior to Bair and Babineau’s post, although the lion’s share of these have been written on the interaction of the first three of the four conditions that Bair and Babineau identified—all relating to the value chain’s market dynamics. Janice Fine and Tim Bartley⁵⁷ think that industrial complexity and mobility impacts WSR’s ability to replicate. That is, WSR will be more difficult to establish when the governed chain involves a sector such as apparel or electronics, since there are complex and “opaque layers of subcontracting” that complicate oversight.⁵⁸ As for mobility, Fine and Bartley note that the FFP owes much of its success to the locally grounded character of monitoring and enforcement because of the nature of tomato growing in Florida. Fine and Bartley argue that WSR would not be as easy to secure in geographically dispersed and mobile industries.⁵⁹ The authors suggest that co-enforcement by governments and non-standard workers’ organizations like the CIW could assist WSR in taking hold in more industries and chains.⁶⁰

⁵⁵ Babineau & Bair, *supra* note 4.

⁵⁶ *Id.*

⁵⁷ Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1.

⁵⁸ Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 at 269.

⁵⁹ *Id.*

⁶⁰ The authors use an example of how the city of Austin, Texas has established an expedited permitting process for construction developers and contractors that submit to a set of standards monitored by Better Builders, a Workers Defense Project staffed by former immigrant construction workers.

Jeremy Blasi and Jennifer Bair focus on the impact of how well civil society, through campaigning, can influence lead firms to bring them to the bargaining table and pressure them to sign.⁶¹ Sean Sellers, in his analysis of the FFP, also identifies limits to workers' and allies' organizational power and campaign capacity as key challenges for creating new WSR programs.⁶² Likewise, James Brudney, in exploring early prospects for replication of the FFP, indicates that the market consequences stemming from the lead firms' control are fundamental to its success.⁶³ Fabiola Mieres and Siobhan McGrath also recognize WSR's replicability is related to market consequences and the structure and dynamics of value chains.⁶⁴

One scholar in particular has taken up the fourth condition that Bair and Babineau identified—the role of law and legal regime in WSR. In a 2019 paper, Manoj Dias-Abey reviews the sociolegal history of the CIW and explains how the group drew on the symbolic and discursive role of anti-trafficking law to create the FFP.⁶⁵ Dias-Abey examines the role of law because he considers it to be an important consideration for WSR's replicability, although he admits that it cannot explain all of WSR's success.⁶⁶ He identifies key points in time when the CIW actively created legal opportunities for itself by encouraging U.S. state governance institutions to prosecute labor trafficking in Florida's farms. Moreover, he argues that the CIW draws on alternative legal resources—namely, anti-trafficking law and its enforcers—where labor law has often collapsed. Furthermore, the CIW seized the moment in the 1990s and early 2000s, utilizing an increased interest in combatting human trafficking at the time.⁶⁷ In another paper published the same year,⁶⁸ Dias-Abey argues that WSR is a form of supply chain collective bargaining that relies on the legally binding nature of the FFP and Accord. Furthermore, he contends that the power of state law can and should be harnessed to encourage

⁶¹ Blasi & Bair, *supra* note 4.

⁶² Sean Sellers, *Assessing Feasibility for Worker-Driven Social Responsibility Programs*, in *POWER, PARTICIPATION, AND PRIVATE REGULATORY INITIATIVES: HUMAN RIGHTS UNDER SUPPLY CHAIN CAPITALISM* (Daniel M. Brinks et al. ed., 2021).

⁶³ Brudney, *supra* note 52 at 374–76.

⁶⁴ Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52.

⁶⁵ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14.

⁶⁶ *Id.* at 3 (“My approach in this chapter is to analyze key moments in the CIW’s history and ask: how were law and legal processes involved in the CIW’s strategy for achieving labor rights for farm workers? This question is a pertinent one because the risk of eliding the role of law in the CIW’s story is that it limits the full range of resources that other labour organizations, hoping to replicate the CIW’s success, may consider available.”).

⁶⁷ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14.

⁶⁸ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8.

expansion of collective bargaining structures like WSR.⁶⁹ He states clearly, “we need not see state law and private regulation as mutually exclusive.”⁷⁰

1.1.C. Summary

In review, WSR has been widely praised in the literature for its efficacy as a solution for the labor governance deficit in value chains, especially as opposed to the unfulfilled promises and window-dressing of CSR. However, the question of WSR’s replicability has been the topic of much concern in the literature. Scholars focused on the background conditions for a successful WSR program have generally centered on the market dynamics, such as a consolidated market with a handful of consumer-facing lead firms, consumers that have labor activist tendencies, and suppliers that have substantially less bargaining power than lead firms. However, scholars have not engaged nearly as much with the relationship between WSR and its legal environments.

Dias-Abey stands out in the literature because he addressed the relationship between WSR and law. His articles focus on the discursive and symbolic roles of law particularly in the context of American anti-trafficking law in the FFP. He also calls for states to use law to support WSR efforts. However, his articles do not address in detail the legal mechanisms for how to accomplish this—like WSR’s contractual nature. While Dias-Abey’s articles make significant contributions to the gap in the literature, the question of contract law’s impact on WSR, in particular, remains unexplored. Moreover, the WSR literature as a whole does not examine the broader interactions of law and WSR as public and private governance, although scholars have examined other labor programs in this way. This literature is examined in the following subpart.

1.2. Public-Private Labor Governance: Classification and Theorization

Whereas the previous section examined the background of WSR and the models that preceded it, this subpart turns to the broader theory of the relationship between private and public governance models that I will use in my analysis of the two WSR case studies. First, I address two theoretical frameworks present in the literature that are used to classify public-private governance interactions. Then, I explain how a blend of the two classification systems

⁶⁹ *Id.* at 16.

⁷⁰ *Id.* at 20.

is useful. Lastly, I briefly review some literature examining the private and public labor governance relationship before concluding the literature review.

1.2.A. Classes of Public-Private Governance Interactions

A sizeable field of literature has emerged that examines the interactions of public and private governance in domestic and global value chains, generally,⁷¹ as well as specifically in global food safety and horticulture governance,⁷² environmental protections,⁷³ and labor exploitation.⁷⁴ The ongoing trend tells of the movement away from the assumption that public and private governance remain separate and toward the examination of how the two governance systems interact.⁷⁵ Here, I present two ways of classifying types of public-private governance interactions, and I explain how a combination of each is useful to characterize this project's two WSR case studies.

According to Fabrizio Cafaggi, at least three classes of public-private governance interactions exist: collaboration, coordination, and competition.⁷⁶ Although Cafaggi intends for

⁷¹ Frederick Mayer & Gary Gereffi, *Regulation and Economic Globalization: Prospects and Limits of Private Governance*, 12 BUS. AND POL. 1 (2010); John Humphrey & Hubert Schmitz, *Inter-firm relationships in global value chains: Trends in chain governance and their policy implications*, 1 INT'L J. OF TECH. LEARNING, INNOVATION AND DEV. (2008).

⁷² Ching-Fu Lin, *Public-Private Interactions in Global Food Safety Governance*, 69 FOOD AND DRUG L.J. 143 (2014); Carolin Hulke & Javier Revilla Diez, *Understanding regional value chain evolution in peripheral areas through governance interactions – An institutional layering approach*, 139 APPLIED GEOGRAPHY 102640 (2022); Janina Grabs & Sophia Louise Carodenuto, *Traders as sustainability governance actors in global food supply chains: A research agenda*, 30 BUS. STRATEGY AND ENV'T 1314 (2021).

⁷³ Sophia Carodenuto, *Governance of zero deforestation cocoa in West Africa: New forms of public-private interaction*, 29 ENVTL. POL'Y AND GOVERNANCE 55 (2019); Paul R. Furumo & Eric F. Lambin, *Scaling up zero-deforestation initiatives through public-private partnerships: A look inside post-conflict Colombia*, 62 GLOBAL ENVTL. CHANGE 102055 (2020); David M. Trubek & Louise G. Trubek, *New Governance and Legal Regulation: Complementarity, Rivalry or Transformation*, WISCONSIN PROJECT ON GOV. AND REG. 1 (2006), https://sociologiajuridica.files.wordpress.com/2011/10/microsoft-word-coexistence_paper-london_version-doc.pdf.

⁷⁴ Giovanni Pasquali et al., *Understanding regional value chains through the interaction of public and private governance: Insights from Southern Africa's apparel sector*, 4 J. OF INT'L BUS. POL'Y 368 (2020); Giovanni Pasquali & Shane Godfrey, *Governance of Eswatini Apparel Regional Value Chains and the Implications of Covid-19*, 34 EUR. J. OF DEV. RES. 473 (2021).

⁷⁵ Jennifer Bair, *Contextualising compliance: Hybrid governance in global value chains*, 22 NEW POL. ECON. 169 (2017).

⁷⁶ Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 44–45. Note that Cafaggi also classifies a “hybridization” interaction when a public actor operates under private law principles, or a private actor operates under public law principles. However, this hybridization category can be subsumed under the cooperative interaction category.

his classifications to apply broadly to different governed topics,⁷⁷ he uses several examples of labor exploitation in value chains as a subject of governance.⁷⁸

First, public and private governance institutions and their actors may *cooperate*. Cooperation occurs when the two sets of actors jointly draft rules and merge their governance tasks. For example, a private actor may draft the rules and a public actor approves or endorses them. MSIs with both private and public actors fall under this category.⁷⁹ However, not all interactions are fully cooperative; instead, they may simply be *coordinative*. In coordinative interactions, public and private institutional actors remain autonomous and independent, but jointly regulate activities in a mutually influential way. This occurs when exchanging information, mutually referring cases, or unilaterally designing private rules to be recognized through judicial or administrative means. Cafaggi mentions that coordinative interactions encourage transplantation of private strategies to public institutions and vice versa.⁸⁰

Competitive public-private interactions have a different nature. In this relationship, private actors raise the public actors' standards, thereby delegitimizing public institutions. In the most extreme form of competitive interaction, the private and public rules are incompatible or mutually exclusive. The public institutions may view the private scheme as a threat to their authority and thwart its efforts. A competitive public-private governance interaction may develop as private actors take on leadership positions without being subject to the same standards as public governance actors, like stringent procedural and administrative rules.⁸¹

Gary Gereffi and Joonkoo Lee offer a similar but slightly different perspective. They classify three types of private-public governance interactions: complementarity, conflict, and displacement.⁸² *Complementarity* appears when public and private institutions reinforce one another's governance efforts.⁸³ Private governance is most effective when private institutions are layered and blended with public institutions.⁸⁴ *Displacement* occurs when one type of

⁷⁷ He uses governance examples related to food safety and environmental protections.

⁷⁸ Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 26.

⁷⁹ *Id.* at 44.

⁸⁰ *Id.* at 45.

⁸¹ *Id.*

⁸² Gary Gereffi & Joonkoo Lee, *Economic and Social Upgrading in Global Value Chains and Industrial Clusters: Why Governance Matters*, J. OF BUS. ETHICS 25, 26 (2016), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2721292.

⁸³ *Id.* at 34–35.

⁸⁴ *Id.* at 35.

governance preempts, displaces, or crowds out the other.⁸⁵ Gereffi and Lee use CSR as an example of how private governance can crowd out or weaken public labor governance (local labor institutions).⁸⁶ Displacement is rarely full or complete, though, often resulting in compromised hybridization or left-over vestiges of the public governance system.⁸⁷ Finally, *conflict* occurs as externally-driven labor codes create tensions with local institutions.⁸⁸ They argue the optimal interaction is complementarity, when both groups of institutions have a synergistic effect.⁸⁹

I adopt a blend of the two classification sets, since each captures elements the other does not. Both Cafaggi's and Gereffi and Lee's classifications include conflict or competition as a type of interaction. The former would classify displacement and conflict as a subcategory of competition, while the latter separates the two interactions, as displacement may not necessarily be competitive or result in conflict. Additionally, an important contribution from Gereffi and Lee is the categorization of complementarity as a unique interaction, since Cafaggi only names coordination and collaboration. This is important because other scholars have shown that private and public actors' efforts may be complementary even when the actors are not coordinating or collaborating with one another.⁹⁰ When combining the two classifications, the list of basic private-public governance interactions looks as follows, in order from most to least harmonious: complementarity, collaboration, coordination, displacement, and competition or conflict. The first three represent various levels of mutually beneficial interaction, and the last two are detrimental.

As recent studies have shown, the factors that determine the way public-private governance interacts are varied, including the political-economic context of the physical locale, institutional ties to the regulated topic, and the identities and interests of the public and private

⁸⁵ *Id.* at 34.

⁸⁶ *Id.*

⁸⁷ *Id.*; Tim Bartley, *Corporate Accountability and the Privatization of Labor Standards: Struggles over Codes of Conduct in the Apparel Industry*, 14 RESEARCH IN POL. SOC. 211 (2005).

⁸⁸ Gereffi & Lee, *supra* note 82 at 31–34.

⁸⁹ Gereffi & Lee, *supra* note 82 at 34.

⁹⁰ See Matthew Amengual, *Complementary Labor Regulation: The Uncoordinated Combination of State and Private Regulators in the Dominican Republic*, 38 WORLD DEV. 405 (2010); Richard Locke et al., *Virtue out of Necessity? Compliance, Commitment, and the Improvement of Labor Conditions in Global Supply Chains*, 37 POL. & SOC'Y 319 (2009); Salo V. Coslovsky & Richard Locke, *Parallel Paths to Enforcement*, 41 POL. & SOC'Y 497 (2013).

governance actors.⁹¹ Regardless of the reasons why private-public governance systems have differing interactions with one another, it is increasingly well accepted that there are varied, complex interactions between the two kinds of governance that also change over time.⁹² The above classifications provide generalized, but nevertheless helpful, characterizations and definitions for the interactions of private and public governance.

1.2.B. Private-Public Labor Governance Relationship

Whereas the previous subsection dealt with the interactions of public and private governance in general terms, this section addresses them specifically in the context of labor governance. Does law support, hinder, or have some other role in relation to private labor governance? If so, how? Some scholars analyzing these questions have expressed concern that private governance of labor have a negative effect on public governance, displacing local law and preempting the capacity-building of local public governance regimes.⁹³ Others are more optimistic, finding that private and public institutions can complement one another in their efforts to protect workers' rights,⁹⁴ even when they do not intentionally coordinate their efforts.⁹⁵

However, a segment of the literature finds that the relationship of public and private labor governance is determined by domestic law and legal frameworks—specifically by the nature of local laws and their enforcement. Tim Bartley, in his book on transnational private

⁹¹ See Bair, *supra* note 75 at 170; Matthew Amengual & Laura Chiro, *Reinforcing the State: Transnational and State Labor Regulation in Indonesia*, 69 ILR REV. 1056, 1060 (2016); Bair et al., *supra* note 52; Coslovsky & Locke, *supra* note 90; Amengual, *supra* note 90.

⁹² Burkard Eberlein et al., *Transnational Business Governance Interactions: Conceptualization and Framework for Analysis*, SUNY BUFFALO LEGAL STUDIES RESEARCH PAPER NO. 2013-017 (2012), <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/228422567.pdf>; Richard M. Locke et al., *Complements or Substitutes? Private Codes, State Regulation and the Enforcement of Labour Standards in Global Supply Chains*, 51 BRITISH J. OF INDUS. REL. 519 (2012).

⁹³ JILL ESBENSHADE, *MONITORING SWEATSHOPS: WORKERS, CONSUMERS, AND THE GLOBAL APPAREL INDUSTRY* (2004); Henry J. Frundt, *The impact of private codes and the union movement*, LATIN AMERICAN STUDIES ASSOCIATION'S XXIII CONGRESS, WASHINGTON, DC. (2001); GAY SEIDMAN, *BEYOND THE BOYCOTT: LABOR RIGHTS, HUMAN RIGHTS, AND TRANSNATIONAL ACTIVISM* (2009).

⁹⁴ Sandra Polaski, *Combining global and local forces: The case of labor rights in Cambodia*, 34 WORLD DEV. 919 (2006); Bishnu N. Mohapatra & Peter Evans, *State-Society Synergy: Government and Social Capital in Development*, 27 CONTEMP. SOC. 292 (1998); Anuradha Joshi & Mick Moore, *Institutionalised Co-production: Unorthodox Public Service Delivery in Challenging Environments*, 40 J. OF DEV. STUD. 31 (2004).

⁹⁵ Amengual, *supra* note 90 at 409–10 (finding that the complementarity occurred because the state and private regulators had comparative advantages that made their monitoring, sanctioning, educating, and conflict resolution functions effective at achieving the same ends under different conditions, even without their coordination).

governance,⁹⁶ asks whether global norms can “remake” or fundamentally change local orders. Bartley utilizes case studies of private fair labor standards from CSR and MSI certification programs and forestry standards in Indonesia and China to show how they are constrained and reconfigured by domestic governance. The evidence presented in Bartley’s book suggests that transnational private labor governance was profoundly shaped by the pre-existing production environment on the ground, but that private governance still has the ability to push public governance toward building its own capacities—and that transnational governance can support stronger public labor law enforcement.⁹⁷ He argues that scholars should begin their analyses by examining the domestic public governance first, and then focus on how it influences the content and scope of employers’ compliance with private governance.

1.3. Part 1 Summary

The first section of this literature review dealt with the labor governance deficit in value chains and the troubled attempt of CSR to solve it. I then presented the novel WSR approach and its advantages, as well as its challenge with replication and expansion. Much of the literature has focused on the market conditions that are conducive to WSR growth, while the small but growing minority of articles probe the relationship between law and WSR. The findings are indicative that there is more to say about the role of law with regard to WSR.

The second section of this review took on a more theoretical lens by addressing how scholars have theorized the public-private governance interaction. Cafaggi’s and Gereffi and Lee’s papers provided useful classifications of public-private interactions that can be harmonized into a unified list of interaction types: complementarity, cooperation, coordination, displacement, and competition. Finally, I briefly addressed some literature on the interaction of public and private labor governance, which indicate that domestic law and public governance have a substantial effect on private labor regulation.

The conventional understanding is that WSR, as private labor governance, is separate from public labor governance. However, scholars like Cafaggi, Gereffi and Lee, and Bartley have begun to discover that public and private governance interact more than once believed, both generally and for labor in particular. Dias-Abey has specifically interrogated how law affects WSR, although he focuses only on the discursive and symbolic role of anti-trafficking

⁹⁶ See generally Bartley, *supra* note 40.

⁹⁷ *Id.* at 265.

law in the FFP. To my knowledge, there has not yet been any scholarly attempt to examine how contract law, and the public institutions that enforce it, have interacted with WSR programs on the ground—much less any attempt to extrapolate from it a larger lesson about how legal systems may hold clues for the way forward with WSR replication. This thesis contributes to the literature by filling this gap.

PART 2. CONTRACT LAW'S INTERACTION WITH WSR: THE FFP AND THE ACCORD

The purpose of this Part is both descriptive and analytical. First, I provide a brief but detailed description of the background of the two case studies, the FFP and the Accord. The case study descriptions introduce the two WSR programs, explain why they were needed, the mechanics of how they operate, and the history of how they came into existence. Then, I analyze the interaction between contract and WSR through the two case studies. This includes an examination of how both the relational and legal sanctions of contract facilitate the lead firms' and suppliers' compliance in the private governance program. Then, I turn to classify the broader public-private interaction of the WSR program's leadership (as the private governance actors) and the state's courts (as the public governance institutions) in regard to contract law. The analysis in the Accord is further complicated by its transnational nature, which raises private international law issues that, as I argue, increase the likelihood for a competitive public-private interaction with the WSR contract.

An important caveat to this work is to recognize two natural limits of its findings. First, this project analyzes merely two instances of WSR programs. The use of more than two case studies for this analysis would be ideal; however, the information is unavailable, and it would exceed the scope of this thesis. Second, this work examines only the legal interactions (law as written and the public institutions' enforcement of the law) with the two WSR programs. There are undoubtedly other economic, social, cultural, and further political factors at play in any given private governance program that are unaccounted for here, and any replication efforts must also reckon with the greater non-legal context. However, as I argue here, any attempt to replicate or scale up WSR must seriously consider the underlying legal foundation of a potential site for WSR, including contract. My hope is for this work to provide a helpful framework or mode of analysis that may be useful for such an effort, while nonetheless providing important nuance to existing conceptions of WSR as a hopeful panacea to the value chain labor governance deficit.

This Part proceeds as follows. Each of the two case studies is presented to explain its history and characteristics relevant for the coming analysis. Then, I focus on a particular facet of law that has played an important role in the initiation and work of each WSR program: freedom of contract. Contract law is examined in the context of the FFP, then the Accord, allowing for a more immediate and fluid comparison of the two. This Part concludes with a macro comparison of the public-private governance interactions in the FFP and Accord, considering the incentives and general disposition of the public institutions vis-à-vis the WSR program's leadership and vice versa.

2.1. Case Study One: The FFP

The FFP is the original WSR program after which the others were modeled. It also remains the most successful WSR program to date in terms of its longevity and its efficacy in improving workers' lives.⁹⁸ The Program deals with domestic value chains producing the tomatoes for fast-food companies within the U.S. The program officially launched in 2011 (although the campaign to start it began much earlier in 2001) as an attempt to eliminate modern slavery conditions in the Florida tomato farms that produce for the fast-food lead firms.⁹⁹ The program successfully eradicated previously rampant physical abuse, child labor, wage theft, and sexual coercion, among other abuses of workers.¹⁰⁰ The FFP has since been expanded to multiple other crops and six other states in the U.S.¹⁰¹

2.1.A. The Need for the FFP

Abuses of farmworkers were so prevalent in part because there were very few to no protections for the workers covered by the FFP. That is, agricultural workers are excluded from protection¹⁰² under the National Labor Relations Act of 1935, which protects employees' rights to organize labor unions, bargain collectively, engage in other concerted activities, and

⁹⁸ See Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 497; FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6.

⁹⁹ The Coalition of Immokalee Workers initiated the FFP in 2011 after an almost ten-year-long campaign, which began in 2001. See Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 498 & 509; FAIR FOOD STANDARDS COUNCIL, *Fair Food 2015 Annual Report* (hereinafter FFSC 2015 Report), FAIRFOODPROGRAM.ORG (2015) at 2, <https://fairfoodstandards.org/15SOTP-Web.pdf>.

¹⁰⁰ FAIR FOOD STANDARDS COUNCIL, *Fair Food: 2018 Update* 28 (2019); Sellers & Asbed, *supra* note 6; Marquis, *supra* note 6 at 169–70; FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 31.

¹⁰¹ Coalition of Immokalee Workers, *Anti-Slavery Program*, COALITION OF IMMOKALEE WORKERS, <https://ciw-online.org/slavery/> (last visited Jul 24, 2022); FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 28.

¹⁰² The term *employee* “shall not include any individual employed as an agricultural laborer”. See NLRA, *supra* note 27 at § 152(3).

strike.¹⁰³ Moreover, agricultural workers are excluded from protections afforded to other employees under the Fair Labor Standards Act of 1938.¹⁰⁴ Although there are no exact statistics on how many FFP-covered workers are migrant workers under the H2-A farmworker visa scheme, it appears to be a substantial number.¹⁰⁵ H2-A migrant workers face additional vulnerabilities because they are legally tied to their employers, who may cancel their employment contracts and have them deported if they attempt to organize.¹⁰⁶ Additionally, undocumented workers, who likely make up a substantial portion of FFP-covered workers,¹⁰⁷ are excluded from labor law protections as a whole.¹⁰⁸ Moreover, there was no active inspectorate on the ground prior to the FFP's arrival. For instance, in 2010, Florida had six Department of Labor inspectors, making the ratio of inspectors to workers one inspector to 1.2 million workers.¹⁰⁹

2.1.B. How the FFP Works

The FFP provided a private solution to the lack of workers' protections for Florida tomato farmworkers. The FFP accomplished this through what would later become known as the WSR model: a contract-based private governance regime that requires lead firms to use their superior bargaining position to pressure their suppliers to follow the FFP's worker-made

¹⁰³ See NLRA, *supra* note 27 at § 157 & 163 (detailing the right of employees to, *inter alia*, organize, collectively bargain, and strike).

¹⁰⁴ National Park Service, *Thirty Years of Farmworker Struggle (U.S. National Park Service)*, NATIONAL PARK SERVICE, <https://www.nps.gov/articles/000/a-new-era-of-farm-worker-organizing.htm> (last visited Jul 24, 2022); Kamala Kelkar, *When labor laws left farm workers behind — and vulnerable to abuse*, PUBLIC BROADCASTING SERVICE (2016), <https://www.pbs.org/newshour/nation/labor-laws-left-farm-workers-behind-vulnerable-abuse> (describing how this exclusion is a result of historically racist policies).

¹⁰⁵ This is based on how the FFP developed a special plan to reduce recruitment abuses of Mexican migrant farmworkers in the FFP. See FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6.

¹⁰⁶ ETAN NEWMAN ET AL., *No Way to Treat a Guest: Why the H-2A Agricultural Visa Program Fails U.S. and Foreign Workers*, 1, 17 (2011), <https://www.farmworkerjustice.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/05/7.2.a.6-No-Way-To-Treat-A-Guest-H-2A-Report.pdf>.

¹⁰⁷ Although it is unclear how many workers in the FFP are undocumented or on H-2A visas, a 2019 study shows that Florida was among the states with the most H-2A workers. See MARCELO CASTILLO ET AL., *Examining the Growth in Seasonal Agricultural H-2A Labor*, 1, 7 (2021), <https://www.ers.usda.gov/webdocs/publications/102015/eib-226.pdf?v=1074.7>. Moreover, in 2019, 42% of all agricultural workers in Florida were undocumented. See New American Economy Research Fund, *Immigration and Agriculture*, NEW AMERICAN ECONOMY RESEARCH FUND (2021), <https://research.newamericaneconomy.org/report/immigration-and-agriculture/>.

¹⁰⁸ *Hoffman Plastic Compounds, Inc. v. National Labor Relations Board*, 535 U.S. 137 (2002); Ruben Garcia, *Ten Years after Hoffman Plastic Compounds, Inc. v. NLRB: The Power of a Labor Law Symbol*, 21 CORNELL J. OF L. AND PUB. POL'Y 659 (2012); Robert Correales, *Did Hoffman Plastic Compounds, Inc. Produce Disposable Workers?*, 14 BERKELEY LA RAZA L.J. 103 (2003).

¹⁰⁹ See Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 at 263.

Code of Conduct that details workers' rights under the FFP. More specifically, the FFP agreements are contracts between the lead firms and the FFP itself, requiring the former to only purchase from suppliers that comply with the following conditions protected in the Code: workers' rights to worker-to-worker education on legal and FFP rights at the suppliers' worksites, a straightforward complaint process and 24-hour complaint hotline, and independent workplace audits and oversight by the Fair Food Standards Council (FFSC).¹¹⁰ Additionally, the Code demands that lead firms pay a small price premium to increase the workers' wages.¹¹¹

The FFSC is the FFP's oversight body that monitors the suppliers' compliance with these provisions and the Code. The FFSC operates without input from lead firms or suppliers, making it an independent committee. Should a supplier fail to comply with the Code, it faces exclusion from the FFP trade group. Should a lead firm fail to live up to its side of the bargain (i.e., by purchasing from an excluded supplier or failing to provide funding for the suppliers' remediation efforts) the firm faces a lawsuit for contract breach. The FFSC also performs an important adjudicative function to decide when to exclude noncompliant suppliers from the FFP or, after confirmed remediations, to let them rejoin.¹¹² Suppliers, in turn, have a right to appeal the FFSC's decision via binding arbitration.¹¹³

2.1.C. How the FFP Came to be

Although the FFP itself only launched in 2011, the CIW (the FFP's parent group) started a campaign for "fair" or slavery-free food almost a decade prior in 2001.¹¹⁴ This campaign involved a cross-country tour with thousands of protests and a boycott of Taco Bell, the CIW's target lead firm.¹¹⁵ The campaign led Taco Bell's parent company, Yum! Brands, to become the FFP's first signatory about four years later in 2005.¹¹⁶ Through strategic and painstaking mobilization of workers, consumers, faith groups, and students, the CIW organized demonstrations, hunger strikes, and boycotts over the next seven years. As a result, ten more

¹¹⁰ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 510.

¹¹¹ Referred to as a "penny per pound" because that is the general price premium per one pound of "gas green" tomatoes. See FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 5.

¹¹² Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 523–24.

¹¹³ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 524 n.163.

¹¹⁴ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 507; Coalition of Immokalee Workers, *Campaign for Fair Food*, COALITION OF IMMOKALEE WORKERS (2013), <https://ciw-online.org/campaign-for-fair-food/>.

¹¹⁵ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 508.

¹¹⁶ *Id.*

lead firms decided to sign into the FFP governance regime.¹¹⁷ Today, the FFP governs 90% of the value chain for tomatoes in Florida,¹¹⁸ which currently ranks as the nation’s top producing state for fresh-market tomatoes.¹¹⁹

The CIW traces its origins to 1993, when a group of farmworkers in Immokalee, Florida began meeting informally to discuss the abuses they experienced in the fields.¹²⁰ The group is part of a wider phenomenon called “alternative labor organizations” or “alt-labor” for short. Alt-labor organizations are worker-led groups that “engage in a combination of service, advocacy, and organizing to provide support to low-wage workers.”¹²¹ The organizations often serve predominantly immigrant populations, focusing on workers who legally cannot or are practically unlikely to unionize.¹²² Unlike unions, they neither collect dues nor engage in worksite-specific collective bargaining. Instead, alt-labor groups emphasize workers’ education regarding their legal rights and workers’ participation in bringing their problems to public fora.¹²³ Since these groups are technically not unions, they are free to boycott up and down the supply chain (i.e., to engage in secondary boycotts), negotiate with their employer’s buyers (the lead firms), and organize themselves as tax-exempt entities—all prohibited actions for traditional unions.¹²⁴ The alt-labor model has been likened to the guilds and mutual-protection associations that predated unions.¹²⁵

As an alt-labor organization, the CIW is unencumbered by the legal and historical burdens of traditional unions because it is not legally organized as one.¹²⁶ Moreover, the CIW

¹¹⁷ *Id.*; Marquis, *supra* note 6 at 68–69.

¹¹⁸ Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52 at 9.

¹¹⁹ Agricultural Marketing Resource Center, *Tomatoes*, AGRICULTURAL MARKETING RESOURCE CENTER (2021), <https://www.agmrc.org/commodities-products/vegetables/tomatoes>.

¹²⁰ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 504.

¹²¹ JANICE FINE, *Worker Centers: Organizing communities at the edge of the dream*, ECONOMIC POLICY INSTITUTE 1, 3 (2005), <https://files.epi.org/page/-/old/briefingpapers/159/bp159.pdf>.

¹²² *Id.* at 14.

¹²³ *Id.* at 15–16.

¹²⁴ Dylan Walsh, *Alt-labor, explained*, MIT SLOAN (2018), <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/alt-labor-explained>; *contra* U.S. CHAMBER OF COMMERCE, *Worker Centers: Union Front Groups and the Law*, 1 (2017), https://www.uschamber.com/assets/archived/images/uscc_worker_center_report_april_2018.pdf (arguing that worker centers should be considered taxable entities under the Labor Management Reporting and Disclosure Act of 1959).

¹²⁵ Dayne Lee, *Bundling “Alt-Labor”: How Policy Reform Can Facilitate Political Organization in Emerging Worker Movements*, 51 HARV. C.R.-C.L. L. REV. 509, 519 (2016).

¹²⁶ A traditional labor union is organized as a 501(c)(5), while the FFP is organized as a 501(c), which makes it eligible for tax-deductible donations, unlike a labor union. U.S. CHAMBER OF COMMERCE, *The New Model of Representation: An Overview of Leading Worker Centers*, 1, 17 (2014), https://www.uschamber.com/assets/archived/images/documents/files/wfi_worker_center_study_-

does not bargain with employers, but with the lead firms up the value chain—thus it does not operate as a traditional union either. However, the CIW also faces disadvantages because of its non-union status. Namely, the laws protecting labor unions, such as the ability to enter legally enforceable collective bargaining agreements, do not extend to the CIW.

The CIW also has a history of close cooperation with local public authorities that predates the FFP. This joint work can be described as *co-enforcement*,¹²⁷ referring to a work rights enforcement strategy that encourages unions, alt-labor organizations, and other grassroots organizations to partner with public authorities. The goal of various co-enforcement efforts has been to educate workers on their rights and patrol labor markets to identify unethical and illegal labor practices.¹²⁸ Since the 1990s, the CIW fostered relationships with public institutions like the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (suing growers that hire discriminatory/abusive crew leaders),¹²⁹ the Department of Justice (prosecuting cases of human trafficking and forced labor),¹³⁰ and the Department of Labor and local law enforcement (referring workers' complaints to them)¹³¹ in the style of co-enforcement.

Yet after repeatedly winning cases and securing convictions, the CIW's leadership grew dissatisfied with these methods' inability to *prevent* abuses. This frustration led Asbed and Hitov to design the FFP, aiming “to put the proper incentives in place at the top of the food market supply chain in order to change the outcomes for those at the bottom.”¹³² The CIW pivoted its strategy, from engaging suppliers directly, to pressuring lead firms to demand labor compliance from their suppliers.¹³³ This led to the campaign described above, and later, the FFP itself.

_new_model_of_representation_final_version_downloaded_2.20.14.pdf (arguing that the CIW and worker centers as a whole should not be allowed to organize themselves as 501(c) non-profits).

¹²⁷ For information on the co-enforcement model, see Fine 2017, *supra* note 49; *see also* Fine 2018, *supra* note 49.

¹²⁸ Fine 2018, *supra* note 49 at 146.

¹²⁹ E.E.O.C. v. DiMare Ruskin, Inc., No. 2:11-cv-158-FtM-99SPC, 2012 U.S. Dist. WL 12067868 (2012).

¹³⁰ U.S. Dep't of Just., *Two Mexican Nationals Sentenced to Prison for Participating in Forced Labor Scheme*, News Release 2017 WL 8791349 (D.O.J.) (2017).

¹³¹ Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52 at 15 & 18; *Id.*

¹³² Sellers & Asbed, *supra* note 6 at 44.

¹³³ Sean Sellers & Greg Asbed, *The History and Evolution of Forced Labor in Florida Agriculture*, 5 RACE/ETHNICITY: MULTIDISCIPLINARY GLOBAL CONTEXTS 29 (2011); Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 502–03.

2.1.D. Summary

Thus, the FFP is a contract-based private governance method to monitor farmworkers' rights in Florida. It has since been extended to six other states to protect farmworkers across the U.S. The CIW created the FFP because of a lacuna in existing U.S. labor law and public governance institutions that has left the labor and employment rights of farmworkers, and particularly migrant farmworkers, legally unprotected. The FFP protects these farmworkers' work rights through a private trade group established through contract. The contracts provide for a series of overlapping and mutually reinforcing monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to be applied to suppliers and lead firms.

2.2. Case Study Two: The Accord

The Bangladesh Accord was the second WSR program to be launched and the most prominent instance of transnational WSR.¹³⁴ The Accord worked to minimize dangerous conditions in Bangladeshi garment factories in the wake of the 2013 Rana Plaza Disaster, as will be detailed below. The program was constructed to hold lead firm clothing companies, that are primarily headquartered in Europe and North America, responsible for improving the health and safety conditions in their Bangladeshi-based manufacturers' garment factories. The Accord governs these lead firms' GVCs that stretch over 1,600 factories, employing over 2.5 million workers.¹³⁵ The Accord was a remarkably successful initiative, resulting in a 93% defect correction rate and the absence of building-related casualties since its initiation.¹³⁶

2.2.A. The Need for the Accord

Although Bangladeshi health and safety laws are quite protective on the books, the enforcement of those protections is severely lacking.¹³⁷ The Labour Act of 2006 and the

¹³⁴ The only other instance of transnational WSR is the GJP, which governs a GVC involving garment factories in Lesotho.

¹³⁵ MARK ANNER, *Binding Power: The Sourcing Squeeze, Workers' Rights, and Building Safety in Bangladesh Since Rana Plaza Research Report*, PENNSYLVANIA CENTER FOR GLOBAL WORKERS' RIGHTS (2018), <https://www.wiwiss.fu-berlin.de/forschung/Garments/Medien/2018-Anner-Research-Report-Binding-Power.pdf>.

¹³⁶ RMG SUSTAINABILITY COUNCIL, *Quarterly Aggregate Report: on Remediation Progress and Status of Workplace Programs at RMG Factories Covered by The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh*, BANGLADESHACCORD.ORG 4, 13 (2020), <https://tinyurl.com/accord-rep>; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 980–81.

¹³⁷ LAURA BOUDREAU, *Multinational enforcement of labor law: Experimental evidence from Bangladesh's apparel sector*, PRIVATE ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN LOW-INCOME COUNTRIES 1, 4 (2020), <https://pedl.cepr.org/sites/default/files/WP%205531%20Boudreau%20MultinationalEnforcementOfLaborLaw.p>

National Building Code of 2006 provide the blackletter protections for workers in factories like those covered by the Accord.¹³⁸ The poor legal enforcement of the law is due corruption and underfunding of public institutions.¹³⁹ Garment factory owners are well-insulated from scrutiny or state oversight because the garment industry plays a prominent role in the Bangladeshi economy¹⁴⁰ and, relatedly, a high percentage of Bangladeshi parliamentarians have financial interests in the industry¹⁴¹ Bair et al. have described the garment factory owners as “domestic elites”.¹⁴²

Neither can workers freely unionize and collectively bargain with their employers to attempt to improve their occupational safety conditions through collectivization. Although the Labour Act technically protects workers from discrimination or retaliation should they organize or participate in unions,¹⁴³ in reality, garment workers face fierce retaliation and even serious violence for attempting to unionize.¹⁴⁴ Moreover, the Ministry of Labour has routinely rejected the majority of unionization applications without providing its reasons for doing so.¹⁴⁵ The poor enforcement of Bangladeshi garment workers’ rights has led to a mere 3.5% unionization rate in garment factories.¹⁴⁶ Where there are unions, they reportedly operate only in name due to threats and retaliation.¹⁴⁷ The lack of enforcement of these laws led to a series of preventable accidents involving factory workers in the years leading up to the Accord’s inauguration.¹⁴⁸

df; Benjamin Evans, *Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh: An International Response to Bangladesh Labor Conditions*, 40 N.C. J. INT’L L. 597 (2015).

¹³⁸ The Bangladesh Labour Act, 2006, Act No. XLII of 2006, at Chapters VI & VII; Bangladesh National Building Code, 2006.

¹³⁹ Boudreau, *supra* note 137; Evans, *supra* note 137.

¹⁴⁰ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 974.

¹⁴¹ Ian M. Taplin, *Who is to blame? A re-examination of fast fashion after the 2013 factory disaster in Bangladesh*, 10 CRITICAL PERSP. ON INT’L BUS. 72, 77 (2014); Jim Yardley, *Garment Trade Wields Power in Bangladesh*, THE NEW YORK TIMES, July 25, 2013, <https://www.nytimes.com/2013/07/25/world/asia/garment-trade-wields-power-in-bangladesh.html#:~:text=Business%20interests%20dominate%20Bangladesh>.

¹⁴² Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 971, 973, 975, 990.

¹⁴³ The Bangladesh Labour Act, 2006, *supra* note 138 at Chapter XIII, §§ 195(c)-(d).

¹⁴⁴ HUMAN RIGHTS WATCH, “*Whoever Raises their Head Suffers the Most*”: *Workers’ Rights in Bangladesh’s Garment Factories*, 1, 30–40 (2015), https://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/report_pdf/bangladesh0415_web_0.pdf.

¹⁴⁵ Mia Mahmudur Rahim & S.K. Samidul Islam, “*Freedom of association*” in the Bangladesh garments industry—a policy schizophrenia in labour regulation, 159 INT’L LAB. REV. 423, 433 (2019).

¹⁴⁶ See Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 982 n.10.

¹⁴⁷ Human Rights Watch, *supra* note 144 at 31.

¹⁴⁸ Evans, *supra* note 137 at 600; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 973.

2.2.B. How the Accord Works

The Accord was intended to provide a private solution to the lack of workers' protections on-the-ground for Bangladesh's garment factory workers. It is modeled after the FFP,¹⁴⁹ being a contract-based value chain private governance regime. That is, the Accord requires lead firms to use their superior bargaining power to pressure their supplier factories to follow the Accord's standards. More specifically, the Accord itself is a contract between 200 clothing company lead firms¹⁵⁰ and the workers' representatives—two global union federations and eight local Bangladeshi unions.¹⁵¹ It requires the lead firms to purchase from suppliers that undergo thorough and independent inspections, engage in hazard remediation, make workers' available for fire and building safety training, and allow for an independently run complaint process and 24/7 hotline.¹⁵² The Accord also requires lead firms to make their supplying factories' remediation efforts financially possible.¹⁵³

The Accord is overseen by factory-level health and safety committees consisting of workers and their representatives, as well as a multiparty Steering Committee (SC). The SC is the primary oversight body, consisting of three corporate and three union representatives, plus an independent chairman appointed by the International Labour Organization (ILO).¹⁵⁴ While the tripartite structure is a notable departure from the FFP model—giving representation to the lead firms—tripartism is not the Accord's innovation.¹⁵⁵ What is particularly innovative about the SC composition is that the traditional “employer” seat is filled not by the suppliers, but by the lead firms. This follows the greater WSR model of supply chain collective bargaining. Moreover, as Donaghey and Reinecke characterize the Accord's SC structure, the exclusion of

¹⁴⁹ Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52 at 9.

¹⁵⁰ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 10.

¹⁵¹ REINGARD ZIMMER, *Corporate responsibility in the Bangladesh Accord: Which regulations are transferable to other supply chains?*, FRIEDRICH-EBERT-STIFTUNG 1, 6–7 (2016), <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/id-moe/13072.pdf>; Jimmy Donaghey & Juliane Reinecke, *When Industrial Democracy Meets Corporate Social Responsibility — A Comparison of the Bangladesh Accord and Alliance as Responses to the Rana Plaza Disaster*, 56 BRIT. J. OF INDUS. REL. 14, 22 (2017).

¹⁵² Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh (hereinafter 2013 Accord) (2013), <https://bangladesh.wpengine.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/2013-Accord.pdf>.

¹⁵³ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 22.

¹⁵⁴ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 4; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977; Worker-Driven Social Responsibility Network, *Fact Sheet: Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh*, WORKER-DRIVEN SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY NETWORK (2019), <https://wsr-network.org/resource/fact-sheet-accord-on-fire-and-building-safety-in-bangladesh>.

¹⁵⁵ Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 15.

the suppliers “minimiz[es] the degree to which the [WSR] process is vulnerable to obstructionism by local employers”.¹⁵⁶

Should a lead firm breach its agreement by purchasing from a noncompliant supplier or failing to provide funding for suppliers’ remediation efforts, it faces a binding arbitration dispute. Should a supplying factory breach, the lead firms will be prohibited from purchasing from the noncompliant factory. The SC also performs an important adjudicative function here by deciding when to exclude noncompliant suppliers from the Accord or, after remediations, to let them continue their membership in the trade group.¹⁵⁷ Unlike the FFP’s FFSC, however, suppliers have no right to appeal the SC’s decision via binding arbitration or otherwise under the Accord¹⁵⁸—a point which I will elaborate in the analysis that follows.

2.2.C. How the Accord Came to be

The Accord agreement was signed largely due to the 2013 Rana Plaza Disaster, an infamous collapse of a multi-factory building in Dhaka that caused the deaths of over 1,100 workers.¹⁵⁹ The factories produced garments for famous multinational clothing brands like H&M, Tesco, Carrefour, Inditex (the company behind Zara), and Fast Retailing (the owner of the brand Uniqlo), among others.¹⁶⁰ Several of the lead firms purchasing from the factories had audited the building just months before its collapse as part of their own CSR programs, but none had noted the building’s serious structural defects.¹⁶¹ Other collapses and fires in Bangladeshi garment factories precipitated the Rana Plaza Disaster, which had also incited international outrage.¹⁶² However, the scale of Rana Plaza sparked international industry and consumer pressure to adopt a new system that would escape current faulty auditing practices.

Although the heat of the moment in post-Rana Plaza Bangladesh created a unique opportunity for labor activists to seize,¹⁶³ the Accord was first drafted pre-Rana Plaza by a coalition of unions and NGOs as a memorandum of understanding.¹⁶⁴ When widespread bad publicity of the Disaster created an opportune moment to expand the memorandum’s efforts,

¹⁵⁶ *Id.*

¹⁵⁷ Zimmer, *supra* note 151 at 5.

¹⁵⁸ There is no such right under the Accord. See 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 4–7.

¹⁵⁹ Zimmer, *supra* note 151 at 2.

¹⁶⁰ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977.

¹⁶¹ Evans, *supra* note 137 at 603.

¹⁶² Evans, *supra* note 137 at 600; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 973.

¹⁶³ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 11; see generally Bair et al., *supra* note 52.

¹⁶⁴ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977.

the Accord's leadership intensified their efforts to secure lead firm signatories to make the Accord legally and practically operational.¹⁶⁵ Within the next month after Rana Plaza, the first lead firm, H&M, signed the Accord.¹⁶⁶ Dozens more followed in the coming days.¹⁶⁷

The Accord began in 2013 as a five-year renewable contract, intended to extend through June 2018. However, in May 2018, the Bangladesh High Court issued an order against the Accord, requiring it to cease operations in the country.¹⁶⁸ The Accord's leadership, along with the influential garment industry association and lobby group, Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA), and the Bangladeshi government proceeded to engage in protracted and largely unfruitful negotiations about how and when the Accord would transfer its work to the government.¹⁶⁹ They eventually reached an agreement about a year later, agreeing to hand off the Accord's work, by early 2020, to a new leadership board consisting of government inspectors, BGMEA, and factory owners.¹⁷⁰

2.2.D. Summary

The Accord was a contract-based private governance method to monitor garment workers' rights in Bangladesh. The global union federations and labor activists initially created the Accord in the FFP's image because of the lack of enforcement of the laws protecting garment workers' occupational safety. The Accord allow for workers' protection through the creation of a private trade group established through contract. The Accord contract provided a series of overlapping and mutually reinforcing monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to be applied to suppliers and lead firms, and it is tied to economic and legal sanctions for noncompliant actors. The Accord operated free from employer control from 2013 through early 2020 but has since been transferred to a new leadership that has substantially compromised its independence and worker-led nature.

¹⁶⁵ Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151.

¹⁶⁶ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977.

¹⁶⁷ *Id.*

¹⁶⁸ Smart Jeans Ltd. v. Stitching Bangladesh Accord Foundation, Writ No. 3826 High Ct. Div., para. 1 (2018) (Bangl.), [https://legislib.com/case/case-details/5f1196c2cb53edfaf4a41a30/?search=Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh|Accord Foundation 1/11](https://legislib.com/case/case-details/5f1196c2cb53edfaf4a41a30/?search=Accord%20on%20Fire%20and%20Building%20Safety%20in%20Bangladesh|Accord%20Foundation%201/11).

¹⁶⁹ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977.

¹⁷⁰ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 988.

2.3. Contract Law's Interaction with WSR

Scholars have remarked that, especially when compared to previous private regulatory efforts like CSR and other MSIs, the WSR model's legal enforceability is unprecedented.¹⁷¹ What makes legal enforcement possible is WSR's contractual framework, which is dependent on the signatories' freedom of contract. Freedom of contract refers to individuals' right to choose, with minimal state restriction,¹⁷² whether to contract, with whom to contract, and on which terms to contract.¹⁷³ Parties wishing to enter WSR contracts must be free to set up a mostly self-governing private trade group, where lead firms are bound to purchase from certified suppliers, and suppliers are required to adhere to agreed-upon rules to remain certified. Importantly, the WSR contracts also establish the terms for what will occur should the WSR program's terms be violated—including the appropriate dispute resolution method to be used (like court-based litigation, private arbitration, or some other method), the choice of forum for adjudication, and the substantive law to apply to contract interpretation in the event that breach occurs.

Does contract law and related institutions, like the judiciary, take on an enabling or hindering role vis-à-vis the WSR program in the two case studies? How so? I argue that contract's threat of legal sanctions (from litigation in Florida or international arbitration, respectively) and relational sanctions (from civil society-imposed reputational harm) both enable WSR by deterring the lead firm signatories from breaching the WSR contracts. In other words, the WSR programs are enabled by both the relational and legal sanctions of the WSR contracts. However, the relational and formal sanctions of contract appear to have held the FFP together with more success than the private legal sanctions utilized in the Accord.

Legal sanctions, which are thought to deter signatories from breach, refer to negative consequences flowing from litigation or adjudication, such as monetary damages imposed by a court or arbitrator.¹⁷⁴ Relational contract, on the other hand, is a long-standing theory that asserts contracting parties avoid breaching their contracts not because they fear formal, legal

¹⁷¹ Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 17; Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 16.

¹⁷² Restrictions of freedom of contract for health, safety, and public order have long been held to be legitimate exercises of government power. See David P. Weber, *Prohibiting the Freedom of Contract: A Fundamental Restriction*, 16 YALE HUM. RTS. & DEV. L.J. 51, 58 (2013).

¹⁷³ Legal Information Institute, *Freedom of Contract*, CORNELL LAW SCHOOL, https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/freedom_of_contract (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

¹⁷⁴ Scott Baker & Albert H. Choi, *Contract's Role in Relational Contract*, 101 VA. L. REV. 559, 562 (2015), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2374109.

sanctions in court but because they want to avoid the loss of a long-term contractual relationship (i.e., relational sanctions).¹⁷⁵ Stuart Macaulay famously found, in surveys of corporate executives, that commercial parties rarely relied on or even referenced their written contracts, but instead prioritized displays of trust and good faith to avoid deterioration of a beneficial long-term contractual relationship.¹⁷⁶ Relational contract theory has been used to explain a variety of contractual relationships from supply contracts¹⁷⁷ to marriage.¹⁷⁸

More recent scholarship has further bridged the gap between relational and legal contract, finding that contractual relationships in the real world use both relational and legal sanctions to effectively deter breach.¹⁷⁹ The WSR relationship, as I argue, mimics this blend of deterrence methods.

Both sets of lead firms have an undoubted interest in preserving their reputations, which incentivizes them to continue participating in the WSR programs without breaching (i.e., a classic relational contract). Both sets of lead firms also have an interest in avoiding litigation because of its expense and time, and potential for judgment against them. However, the greater occurrence of adjudication in the Accord, the emphasis on an immediate regulatory solution, combined with the parties' attempt to avoid Bangladeshi influence, as will be explored herein, may indicate the failures in the relational and legal contract. This is contrasted with the absence of litigation of the FFP, its leadership's greater emphasis on a long-term regulatory presence in Florida, and its strategic co-enforcement and submission to public authorities.

This subpart will proceed as follows: first, an analysis of the relationship between the FFP's signatory fast-food lead firms and the CIW, considering the choice of applicable law,

¹⁷⁵ Stewart Macaulay, *Non-Contractual Relations in Business: A Preliminary Study*, 28 AM. SOC. REV. 55, 61 (1963) (analyzing commercial entities that rely primarily on reputational sanctions); Lisa Bernstein, *Private Commercial Law in the Cotton Industry: Creating Cooperation Through Rules, Norms, and Institutions*, 99 MICH. L. REV. 1724, 1737–39 (2001); Lisa Bernstein, *Opting Out of the Legal System: Extralegal Contractual Relations in the Diamond Industry*, 21 J. LEGAL STUD. 115, 116 (1992); Ian MacNeil, *Contracts: Adjustments of Long-Term Economic Relations Under Classical, Neoclassical, and Relational Contract Law*, 72 NW. U. L. REV. 854, 875–83 (1978); Stewart Macaulay, *Relational Contracts Floating on a Sea of Custom? Thoughts about the Ideas of Ian MacNeil and Lisa Bernstein*, 94(3) NW. U. L. REV. 775 (2000); Richard Speidel, *The Characteristics and Challenges of Relational Contracts*, 94(3) NW. U. L. REV. 823 (2000) (there is enough flexibility in modern contract law, provided by considerations of good faith and public policy, to accommodate the relational contract).

¹⁷⁶ Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175 at 59, 64–65.

¹⁷⁷ MacNeil (1978), *supra* note 175.

¹⁷⁸ See, e.g., Elizabeth S. Scott & Robert E. Scott, *Marriage as Relational Contract*, 84 VA. L. REV. 1225 (1998); Ian MacNeil, *A Primer of Contract Planning*, 48 CAL. L. REV. 627 (1975); Sharon Thompson, *Feminist Relational Contract Theory: A New Model for Family Property Agreements*, 45 J. OF L. AND SOC'Y 617 (2018).

¹⁷⁹ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174.

forum, and use of arbitration as a dispute resolution method. Second, an analysis of the Accord for the contractual relationships between signatory clothing brand lead firms and the unions. This will involve the impact of private international law, which is an important consideration in the Accord because of its transnational nature. Specifically, the contractual choice of applicable law and forum, as well as Bangladesh's recognition and enforceability of a foreign arbitral decision are key components of the analysis.

2.3.A. WSR and Contract: The FFP

The designers of the FFP state “[t]he only point of contact between the two [law and the FFP] is the ability of CIW or a participating buyer to resort to the courts if there has been a breach of a FFA [Fair Food Agreement].”¹⁸⁰ Moreover, they emphasize that the role of law in WSR is “only to create and/or protect the space for market-based programs like the FFP to develop and operate”.¹⁸¹ Although they intended these statements to mean that there is little interaction between the FFP and the legal system, I take the statements as an indication that the ability to resort to court is one of the integral components that allows the FFP regime to operate. This analysis examines *how* the contract law facilitates the “creation” or “protection” of the space for FFP to develop and operate.

2.3.A.i. Relational Contract

It is important to note that the FFP has never been litigated. In fact, the CIW has not had occasion to bring an action against any of its signatories for breach. Conventionally, this fact has been used as a proof that the FFP system works in a way that is “divorced” from public governance and has no need for legal sanctions.¹⁸² The CIW’s general counsel explained that “once a buyer [lead firm] has signed, the agreement becomes part of its everyday business operations and is forgotten”,¹⁸³ indicating a relationship like that in a private CSR or MSI certification system. However, legally binding contracts also have also been known to promote this kind of relationship where the signatories never call upon the legal force of their contract or even look to its terms.¹⁸⁴ That is, the FFP contracts may be displaying the markings of a relational contract reliant on informal sanctions.

¹⁸⁰ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 526.

¹⁸¹ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 527 n.181.

¹⁸² Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 526; Siegmann et al., *supra* note 4 at 122–23.

¹⁸³ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 16.

¹⁸⁴ Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175 at 59.

In the FFP, the lead firms are signatories to the WSR contracts, while the suppliers are not signatories, but they are heavily affected by the contract. The informal, relational sanction for the lead firms' noncompliance with the FFP is trade group exclusion and, moreover, the reputational harm that would likely translate to economic damages. That is, the lead firms have strong incentives to live up to their end of the FFP bargain. The lead firms naturally wish to avoid paying higher prices because of the price premium charged by the CIW. However, the WSR program protects their brand reputation, which translates into economic gains (or at least not economic losses), which is a small price to pay in comparison.¹⁸⁵ To be clear, I am not suggesting that it is a universal truth that brand reputation is always worth more to the lead firms than the money that they save by not joining WSR. Rather, this offset in costs is a requirement for WSR to be viable in the first place, so that any lead firm voluntarily joining a WSR program may be safely assumed to satisfy this condition. Thus, viewing the FFP under the lens of relational contract, the FFP keeps the lead firms compliant by fostering a trade group relationship that the signatories have an intrinsic interest in continuing because the continued relationship is more valuable than the prospect of breach. Thus, the potential relational sanctions from the FFP contracts may themselves be sufficient to deter the lead firms from noncompliance. Indeed, this may explain why the CIW has never had occasion to sue a lead firm for breach.

As for the suppliers, who are not signatories to the formal contract, they are nonetheless the subjects of regulation in the relational contract. In a sense, while the legal contract operates formally only between the lead firms and the CIW, the relational contract operates in a three-way fashion—also including the suppliers. The suppliers too are integral to the FFP trade group, and they have strong incentives to comply with the FFP's Code of Conduct, so as to remain eligible to sell their produce to the lead firms. The sanctions of “breaching” their end of the relational contract bargain would be severe: being expelled from the FFP trade group. Thus, both lead firms and suppliers are deterred from violating the FFP relational contract.

2.3.A.ii. Legal Contract

If relational sanctions are sufficient to this end, though, what is the function of the legal contract itself and what is the role, if any, of legal sanctions? According to the designers of

¹⁸⁵ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174 (arguing that the relatively lower cost of formal contract is more desirable compared to the higher cost of deterrence from relational contract).

WSR, the role of law is “to create and/or protect the space” for programs like the FFP.¹⁸⁶ But how exactly does the contract law develop an environment conducive to WSR? One explanation lies in the research of Baker and Choi who asked this question in their research of goods and services contracts.¹⁸⁷ They found that parties still sign enforceable contracts—even where there seems to be no need for it due to their long-standing relationships—because the parties can maximize the deterrence effect through formal contract at a much lower cost than relational contract.¹⁸⁸

Take the FFP as an example. The relational harm from a lead firm’s noncompliance with its FFP contract would be great: the termination of the trade group participation, meaning monetary losses from being cut off from the FFP’s reputation-saving effects. However, the FFP prevents the lead firms from experiencing the full relational cost of breach by offering a legal adjudication method. That is, the FFP sets Florida civil courts as the choice of forum for contract disputes between the CIW and the lead firms.¹⁸⁹ Whereas relational contract’s sanctions are closer to an all-or-nothing penalty like suspension or termination of trade,¹⁹⁰ formal contract’s sanctions are usually monetary,¹⁹¹ which can be adapted and made proportional to the severity of breach.

Moreover, whereas relational sanctions can be imposed for a range of reasons—and not necessarily proper or legal ones (i.e., when relational sanctions “misfire”¹⁹²)—legal sanctions can only be imposed by the courts where they find an unlawful breach.¹⁹³ Through adjudication that is secured via the formal contract, the lead firms have some assurance that sanctions (both relational and formal) will only be imposed under specified circumstances by an external decisionmaker who is better positioned to avoid “misfiring” the sanctions.¹⁹⁴

Furthermore, when sanctions are imposed, it does not necessarily mean the end of the lead firm’s participation in the FFP. This may make the lead firms more willing to participate in the FFP initially and make them more likely to continue their participation throughout.

¹⁸⁶ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 527 n.181.

¹⁸⁷ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174.

¹⁸⁸ *Id.* at 590.

¹⁸⁹ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 16.

¹⁹⁰ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174 at 562.

¹⁹¹ *Id.*

¹⁹² *Id.* at 564–65.

¹⁹³ *Id.*

¹⁹⁴ *Id.*

The suppliers also benefit from the formal contract, although they are not legally parties to it. Specifically, FFP-participant suppliers are contractually afforded the opportunity to turn to binding arbitration as a method of appeal from an FFSC decision with which they disagree.¹⁹⁵ Additionally, the suppliers have the opportunity for reentry into the FFP trade group if they violate the Code of Conduct.¹⁹⁶ The formalization of the suppliers' right to appeal and of a method for trade group reentry are available through the legal aspect of contract.

Another explanation of the role of the legal contract in the FFP is that the act of signing the contract indicates mutual trust between the contracting parties, which may itself facilitate the relational contract. In Wilkinson-Ryan and Hoffman's research on common (mis)conceptions of contract law and how they affect relational contracts, they find that the legal moment of contracting "seems to cause a noticeable shift toward commitment even when there are no additional social or moral cues".¹⁹⁷ In other words, the act of signing a legally-binding contract signals the parties' seriousness about their commitment to comply with the formal terms.¹⁹⁸ Relatedly, Johnson et al., in their research, found that the belief in the effectiveness of courts has a significant positive effect on the amount of trust that is shown in new contractual relationships between parties.¹⁹⁹ Essentially, the courts' reputation for minimal effectiveness (i.e., that they are fair, impartial, able to issue decisions in a timely manner, able to enforce their decisions, etc.) is necessary to begin new contractual relationships²⁰⁰—relationships that may later be sustained by relational sanctions.²⁰¹ The authors explain that the courts, that are perceived to be effective, clarify the threat of legal sanctions to the signatories, which generates confidence in the relationship.²⁰²

In the FFP, the parties' signature of the formal contract communicates the lead firms' commitment to adhere to its provisions, which can be backed up with the force of law in Florida's courts. Thus, the legal contract makes the FFP participants' relational contract

¹⁹⁵ FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 39.

¹⁹⁶ FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 71–72.

¹⁹⁷ Tess Wilkinson-Ryan & David Hoffman, *The Common Sense of Contract Formation*, 67 STANFORD L. REV. 1269, 1301 (2015), http://www.stanfordlawreview.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2015/06/67_Stan_L_Rev_1269_Wilkinson-Ryan_Hoffman.pdf.

¹⁹⁸ *Id.* at 1295–1300 (discussing how lay people understand the act of signing a contract as the act of contracting itself, which connotes formalism).

¹⁹⁹ Simon H. Johnson et al., *Courts and Relational Contracts* 1–67 (Nat'l Bureau of Econ. Rsch., Working Paper No. 8572, 2001), <https://www.nber.org/papers/w8572>.

²⁰⁰ *Id.* at 3–4, 18–19, 22, 26–27, 33.

²⁰¹ *Id.* at 18–19.

²⁰² *Id.* at 5.

possible. Both of these explanations for the existence of the formal contract in the FFP—the cost-reducing aspect and the trust-signaling aspect—rest on the signatories’ belief in the effectiveness of Florida’s legal system. While confirming the signatories’ initial perceptions of Florida’s civil courts as effective would require qualitative analysis that is beyond the scope of this thesis, the apparent role of the courts as public institutions related to contract is noteworthy.

Although the FFP is not a sale of goods or services contract like those examined in the relational and legal contract literature, from the lead firms’ perspective, the FFP contracts may not be perceived as substantially different from contracts for the sale of services. To the lead firms, they essentially agree to pay for the monitoring and enforcement services of the FFP in exchange for the reputational safeguarding that the FFP provides.

Whether the relational or the legal sanctions of contract are more important to the enablement of the FFP is still up for debate. However, as I have introduced and argued here, the legal structure provided through relational and formal contract plays a crucial role in enabling the WSR framework.

2.3.A.iii. Public-Private Governance Interactions Regarding Contract

The previous subpart considered the roles of the contract itself in facilitating or hindering WSR in the FFP. But what is the role of the public institutions and actors? Here, I examine the type of interaction is exhibited by the public and private actors in the FFP. Note that “interaction” refers to how WSR and the judicial system that interprets/applies contract affect one another to create a relationship of complementarity, collaboration, coordination, displacement, or competition. The public actors here are the Floridian courts and other public institutions, such as the Department of Labor, and the private actor is the CIW.

Arguably, the public and private actors are *competing* with one another, as the private inspectorate attempts to *displace* the public. Both the Department of Labor and the CIW attempt to enforce their own standards for workers’ treatment. However, there was no active inspectorate on the ground prior to the FFP’s arrival²⁰³ and there were very few to no

²⁰³ In 2010, for example, Florida had six Department of Labor inspectors, making the ratio of inspectors to workers one inspector to 1.2 million workers. See Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 at 263.

protections for the workers covered by the FFP.²⁰⁴ It would not be an overstatement to say that the inspection and regulatory activity in Florida’s tomato farms was essentially null prior to the FFP. That is, there was nothing for the FFP’s governance to displace or compete with.

Additionally, from the perspective of the adjudication of the FFP contracts, there was likely no competition or conflict with the jurisdiction of the Florida civil courts. The FFP contracts themselves designate the Florida civil courts as the appropriate forum and method for adjudication.²⁰⁵ The applicable substantive law also appears to be Floridian contract law.²⁰⁶ Since the FFP governs a domestic value chain, the appropriate forum would not be outside of the U.S., even considering the expansion of the FFP to U.S. states beyond Florida.²⁰⁷ This significantly simplifies the jurisdictional considerations and reduces the chance of a competitive interaction arising from two contending jurisdictions. (This is contrasted with the dynamic in the Accord in the following section.) Hence, there was also no displacement or competitive public-private interaction.

The interaction seen in the FFP is not *complementary* nor *cooperative* either. The CIW and workers draft the Code, while the signatories (CIW and lead firms) and oversight body (the FFSC) apply the rules without public institutional involvement. The public is not synergistically, jointly drafting the contract provisions or Code rules with the private actors. Instead, the CIW, along with the lead firms, agree upon the provisions and the courts apply them. Thus, the FFP does not exhibit a truly complementary or cooperative interaction.

Rather, the public-private relationship in FFP best mirrors the interaction one step “below” cooperation on the spectrum of interactions—that of *coordination*. As Cafaggi defined public-private coordination, this may occur when the private actor unilaterally designs private rules to be recognized through judicial or other public means.²⁰⁸ Here, the private signatories essentially establish the contractual rules via the contract, and the courts apply

²⁰⁴ Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1 at 262–63; *See, e.g.,* NLRA, *supra* note 27 at § 152(3) (“employee “shall not include any individual employed as an agricultural laborer”); NEWMAN ET AL., *supra* note 102.

²⁰⁵ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 16.

²⁰⁶ FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 69–70; Courtland H. Peterson, *Conflict Avoidance through Choice of Law and Forum*, 45 DENVER L. REV. 20, 24 (1968) (“the power to select a forum often exerts a strong though indirect influence on the law actually to be applied”).

²⁰⁷ The FFP is said to operate in a domestic chain because the tomatoes themselves are not bought or sold transnationally. This does not consider whether the laborers themselves are crossing national lines.

²⁰⁸ Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 45.

them.²⁰⁹ In actuality, the FFP also involves a coordinative interaction, as the public and private mostly remain in their discrete regulatory spheres—not merging their actions but also not competing. The cooperative interaction seen in the FFP between the CIW and the courts facilitates the WSR program’s functionality—in terms of its longevity and ability to successfully improve working conditions.

A truly complementary interaction between the public and private institutions in a context like the FFP may be able increase the state’s regulatory capacities²¹⁰—which the FFP currently does not aim to do—but it may also raise hazards for the WSR model, as the private actors lose control over their private bargain. Regardless of the potential to be complementary, however, it seems the best placement for the FFP’s interaction is coordination.

2.3.A.iv. Summary

This analysis of the WSR program and contract law included two parts. First, I explored how the relational and legal aspects of contract support the FFP. The FFP appears to rely on both aspects, although it is unclear the relative impact of the two without further qualitative research. Nevertheless, the relational contract enables the WSR program because the sanctions from violating the relational contract are severe for both lead firms and suppliers—termination from the FFP and its reputational and economic benefits. As for the role of the legal contract, legal sanctions also appear to enable the WSR program because of its cost-reducing effect (compared to the all-or-nothing sanctions from relational contract) and its trust-signaling effect. Both of these likely rest on the signatories’ belief in the effectiveness of Florida’s court system for contract interpretation and enforcement.

Throughout this subpart, I build on the existing concept that a legal contract gives rise to relational contract²¹¹ by finding that the legal contract in the FFP involves a two-party

²⁰⁹ Ordering through private contract is something of a myth or oxymoron because contracts are dependent upon the well-functioning of the state to enforce them. See Margaret Jane & Radin Polk Wagner, *The Myth of Private Ordering: Rediscovering Legal Realism in Cyberspace*, 73(4) CHICAGO-KENT L. REV. 1295 (1998); Gillian K. Hadfield, *Privatizing Commercial Law: Lessons from the Middle and the Digital Ages*, 1, 6 (John M. Olin Program in L. and Econ., Working Paper No. 195, 2000), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=220252. This also comports with Cafaggi’s institutional complementarity approach that applies not just to contract law. The theory holds that private regulatory systems require strong public institutions to function effectively and credibly. See Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 41.

²¹⁰ Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 45 (“Coordination favours legal transplants; it promotes transfer of regulatory strategies and enforcement from private to public and vice versa, as is the case for the ‘supply-chain approach’ adopted in many public safety regimes.”).

²¹¹ Johnson et al., *supra* note 199; Wilkinson-Ryan & Hoffman, *supra* note 197.

dynamic between the signatories (CIW and suppliers), but the relational contract involves a three-party dynamic between the CIW, lead firms, and suppliers. The suppliers play a crucial role in WSR because they are the targets that the legal contract hopes to regulate, albeit indirectly through the lead firms. To achieve the relational sanctions of contract as to the suppliers, the formal contract is necessary. Finally, the FFP exhibits a coordinative interaction with the judicial system in Florida by applying the private FFP provisions and rules. This furthers the argument that the public governance system, even if only through its reputation for effectiveness, enables the structure of the WSR program.

2.3.B. WSR and Contract: The Accord

This subpart seeks to answer how the contract law “created” or “protected” the space for the Accord to develop and operate. It also seeks to examine how the contract’s interaction with law may have contributed to the dissolution of the Accord. First, this subpart examines how the relational and legal sanctions of the Accord contract have worked to keep the parties in the WSR program compliant with its private governance regime. Secondly, this subpart investigates the public-private interaction in the Accord in regard to the contract’s adjudication. Unlike the FFP, the Accord is a transnational instrument, making it significantly more complicated from a jurisdictional standpoint. As such, it must be analyzed under the lens of private international law doctrines. I argue that the Accord contract, due to its attempt to govern a global value chain with signatories from differing legal jurisdictions, displays more of a competitive interaction with the Bangladeshi court system than a coordinative interaction, let alone a cooperative one.

I propose that Accord’s legal contract essentially excluded the suppliers from the review mechanism (as non-signatories to the Accord contract), leaving them with no alternative but to pursue litigation in Bangladeshi courts. Two cases before the Bangladeshi High Court demonstrated the competitive, nearly hostile interaction between the Accord’s leadership and the Bangladeshi High Court. The result of the second case led to the Accord’s cancellation.

2.3.B.i. Relational Contract

Relational contract asserts that contracting parties avoid breaching their contracts because the loss of a long-term relationship and its associated negative reputational

implications (the “relational sanctions”) deter them.²¹² The relational contract literature indicates that contracting parties do not rely on their written contracts for enforcement, but rather that relational sanctions serve as much stronger deterrents than the prospect of legal sanctions.²¹³ This depends on the signatories’ desire to continue a repeated or long-term contractual relationship with each other and the value of said relationship.²¹⁴

When examining the Accord, it seems to have the same elements that made the FFP relational contract work: a trade group that designed to keep both lead firms and suppliers compliant with their respective roles by threatening reputational sanctions for noncompliance. Indeed, the long-term aspect of relational contract is reflected in Accord’s text where it states, “Signatory companies to this agreement are committed to maintaining *long-term sourcing relationships* with Bangladesh”, which establishes the basis for what may be considered a relational contract.²¹⁵

The lead firms in the Accord naturally wish to avoid paying for the remediation efforts of their supplier factories and to ensure their compliance with the Accord—both of which are obligations of lead firms under the contract.²¹⁶ In the Accord, the lead firms agree to pay up to \$500,000 per year to fund the Accord’s inspection and oversight operation.²¹⁷ However, they have a stronger incentive to comply with the terms because the informal, relational sanction for violation is reputational harm, like what that occurred immediately after the Rana Plaza Disaster, that threatens to cause even larger monetary damages. In other words, the contract’s deterrence capacity relies on the Accord’s ability to safeguard the reputation of lead firms.

The relational sanctions also apply to the suppliers, reflecting a three-way relational contract, although the legal contract formally extends only between the unions and the lead firms. Although the supplier factories are not signatories to the contract, the private governance program intends to govern them. Note how the Accord states its scope: “The agreement covers all suppliers producing products for the signatory companies.”²¹⁸ They too form an important side in the Accord program’s governance mechanism. The relational sanctions applicable to

²¹² Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (2001), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (1992), *supra* note 175; Macneil, *supra* note 175; Macaulay (2000), *supra* note 175; Speidel, *supra* note 175.

²¹³ Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175 at 59.

²¹⁴ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174 at 563 & 572.

²¹⁵ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 23.

²¹⁶ *Id.* at cl. 12 & 22.

²¹⁷ *Id.* at cl. 24.

²¹⁸ *Id.* at para. 7.

the suppliers are termination or suspension from the Accord trade group, which directly impacts their ability to sell their garments to the financially powerful lead firms. While an Accord-participant supplier naturally does not wish to expend the time or effort to fulfill its obligations under the Accord (i.e., to remediate or allow for the workers' ability to leave what they believe to be unsafe premises²¹⁹), the relational expense of suspension or termination from the Accord trade group would likely be more costly than compliance. Essentially, the relational sanctions for breach, from the perspective of either the lead firms or the suppliers, is ultimately great economic loss.

Thus, when viewing the Accord in terms of relational contract, the WSR trade group mechanism apparently should support a long-term relationship that encourages both the lead firms and the suppliers to comply with their respective obligations. As relational contract theory holds, the parties rarely resort to litigation.²²⁰ However, the unions behind the Accord have twice filed arbitration disputes against the lead firms for contract breach.²²¹ Moreover, the suppliers have also twice filed suit in local Bangladeshi court: one time for breach of contract²²² and the other time for the Accord's allegedly improper usage of private governance authority.²²³ These disputes and cases are examined in detail below.

2.3.B.ii. Legal Contract

The legal contract also offers benefits to the parties in the Accord, even discounting the possibility of a relational contract that ensures parties' compliance. The Accord itself operates as a legal contract between the two groups of signatories. The signatories are, on one side, the global union federations plus the Bangladeshi unions, referred to collectively in the literature as the "Labor Caucus".²²⁴ The Labor Caucus represents the garment workers. On the other side are approximately 200 lead firms in the clothing industry.²²⁵

²¹⁹ *Id.* at para. 7 & cl. 15.

²²⁰ Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (2001), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (1992), *supra* note 175; Macneil, *supra* note 175; Macaulay (2000), *supra* note 175; Speidel, *supra* note 175.

²²¹ IndustriALL Global Union v. [Redacted], Case No. 2016-36 (Perm. Ct. Arb. 2018); Uni Global Union v. [Redacted], Case No. 2016-37 (Perm. Ct. Arb. 2018).

²²² Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd. v. Bangladesh Accord Foundation, Writ No. 10929, 37 High Ct. Div. 255, 6CLR, 1 (2016) [Appendix B].

²²³ *Smart Jeans Ltd.*, Writ No. 3826 High Ct. Div.

²²⁴ Cedric E. Dawkins, *An Agonistic Notion of Political CSR: Melding Activism and Deliberation*, 170 J. OF BUS. ETHICS 5, 13 (2021); Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 15 & 35.

²²⁵ Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 14.

Among several benefits of the legally binding contract is the advantage of adaptability that the formalized agreement offers. Baker and Choi identified a number of comparative advantages that legal contract offers that relational contract cannot.²²⁶ The reason discussed in the FFP contract subpart above is related to the parties' ability to decrease the cost of deterrence. Part of that benefit, the authors explained, is how a formal contract allows a level of "flexibility" that relational contract is unable to accomplish.²²⁷ Namely, the parties can choose to use arbitration as their adjudication method, which has the power to reduce the costs of deterrence. Specifically, Baker and Choi explain how arbitration allows the parties to lower the procedural and evidentiary hurdles for adjudication.²²⁸ Arbitration also offers a number of advantages for transnational contracts, allowing the disputing parties accessible, neutral, and private adjudication distinct from any specific national legal system.²²⁹ Further, the arbitrator has the power to tailor the balance of relational and legal sanctions²³⁰ and control the costs of dispute resolution.²³¹ Perhaps most importantly for relational contract, arbitral proceedings and decisions can be kept confidential, which may be used as damage control for the party's reputation.²³²

The Accord signatories make good use of the flexibility of the legal contract, tailoring its dispute resolution system with two tiers. First, the SC retains original jurisdiction over all disputes between the Accord signatories.²³³ Recall that the SC is the oversight committee of the Accord, comprised of seven seats representing the Labor Caucus, the lead firms, and a neutral ILO chair.²³⁴ If the parties are unable to resolve the dispute before the SC, then the parties may appeal to final and binding arbitration.²³⁵

²²⁶ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174.

²²⁷ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174 at 577.

²²⁸ *Id.*

²²⁹ Hans Smit, *Substance and Procedure in International Arbitration: The Development of a New Legal Order*, 65 TUL L. REV. 1309 (1991).

²³⁰ Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174 at 563 & 577.

²³¹ *Id.* at 564.

²³² *Id.* at 576.

²³³ Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh (hereinafter 2018 Accord), at cl. 3 (2018), <https://bangladesh.wpengine.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/2018-Accord.pdf>; Reingard Zimmer, *International Framework Agreements: New Developments through Better Implementation on the Basis of an Analysis of the Bangladesh Accord and the Indonesian Freedom of Association Protocol*, 17 INT'L ORG. L REV. 178, 200 (2020), https://brill.com/view/journals/iolr/17/1/article-p178_178.xml.

²³⁴ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 4; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 977; Worker-Driven Social Responsibility Network, *supra* note 154.

²³⁵ 2018 Accord, *supra* note 233 at cl. 3.

Although specificity as to the seat of arbitration and the applicable law cannot be found in the original 2013 Accord, the flexibility of the usage of arbitration is still apparent. This flexibility, facilitated by the legal contract, is especially relevant in a transnational setting where it is unclear which court has *in personam* jurisdiction.²³⁶ This is due to the differing places of “residence” or central administration of the different parties.²³⁷ Namely, the Labor Caucus is comprised of two global union federations headquartered in Switzerland²³⁸ and eight unions located in Bangladesh.²³⁹ On the business side of the contract, the 200 lead firms are headquartered and doing business across the globe.²⁴⁰

The use of arbitration and a foreign choice of law is not uncommon for other transnational contracts, such as commercial and investment disputes, because it provides a neutral forum for dispute resolution.²⁴¹ Neither is it particularly rare in the labor field, as about ten percent of global framework agreements between multinational companies and global union federations use mediation or arbitration procedures.²⁴² Since transnational, private governance contracting does not yet have a legal framework to enforce it, arbitration seems a natural choice in this sense as well.

The Accord’s transnational nature and the use of arbitration, however, does bring up several complexities in the choice of forum and applicable law, as well as with the recognition

²³⁶ For more information on personal jurisdiction, see Trevor C. Hartley, *Basic Principles of Jurisdiction in Private International Law: The European Union, the United States, and England*, 71 INT’L AND COMP. L.Q. 211 (2021), <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/182043EE13152356A884C1F58204251B/S0020589321000427a.pdf/basic-principles-of-jurisdiction-in-private-international-law-the-european-union-the-united-states-and-england.pdf>.

²³⁷ *Id.* at 214.

²³⁸ UNI Global Union is headquartered in Nyon, Switzerland. UNI Global Union, *About*, UNI GLOBAL UNION, <https://uniglobalunion.org/> (last visited Jul 25, 2022). IndustriALL Union is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland. IndustriALL Global Union, *About us*, INDUSTRIALL (2019), <https://www.industriall-union.org/who-we-are> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²³⁹ Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh, *Accord Signatories: Trade Union Signatories*, BANGLADESH ACCORD, <https://bangladeshaccord.org/signatories/trade-union-signatories> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²⁴⁰ The Accord’s three largest fashion retailer signatories were H&M, Inditex, and Uniqlo. Worker Rights Consortium, *International Safety Accord*, WORKER RIGHTS CONSORTIUM, <https://www.workersrights.org/our-work/international-safety-accord/#:~:text=The%20Accord%20Today&text=Signatory%20brands%20included%20three%20of> (last visited Jul 25, 2022). They are headquartered in Sweden, Spain, and Japan, respectively.

²⁴¹ Tamar Meshel, *International Arbitration: The New Frontier of Business and Human Rights Dispute Resolution?*, 44(1) DAL. L.J. 101, 109 (2021), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3877676.

²⁴² Felix Hadwiger, *Looking to the future: mediation and arbitration procedures for global framework agreements*, 23(4) TRANSFER: EUR. REV. OF LAB. AND RES. 409 (2017).

and enforcement of an arbitral decision by a local court. These three considerations call for the application of private international law or conflict of laws doctrines. It is important to note that private international law would have bearing on the Accord even without the arbitral mechanism, as long as the local Bangladeshi courts and law are not exclusively utilized.

The challenges with private international law arose in the two instances that the Accord was brought to arbitration: *IndustriALL Global Union v. [Redacted]*²⁴³ and *Uni Global Union v. [Redacted]*.²⁴⁴ On each side of the two disputes were the global union federations, while the unnamed parties are lead firms whose names were redacted for confidentiality. The two arbitral disputes commenced in 2016 but were consolidated because they concerned the same allegations. The two global union federations alleged that the lead firms violated Articles 12 and 22 of the Accord,²⁴⁵ which provide that the lead firms must require their suppliers to repair facilities on a timely basis and that the lead firms must provide the finances for the suppliers to repair.²⁴⁶ The complaints were originally submitted to the SC, per the Accord's provisions, but the SC was "unable to reach a decision on the merits of the charge."²⁴⁷ The arbitral tribunal was formally constituted in early 2017, and proceeded to issue a number of procedural orders in the following months.²⁴⁸ However, after determining that the appeal was appropriate, by early 2018, the parties had settled privately and agreed to suspend arbitration.²⁴⁹ One of the lead firms reportedly agreed to pay \$2 million toward safety remediation of 150 factories.²⁵⁰ Although the arbitration was of a preliminary nature, it signified that the Accord contract was

²⁴³ *IndustriALL Global Union*, Case No. 2016-36 Perm. Ct. Arb.

²⁴⁴ *Uni Global Union*, Case No. 2016-37 Perm. Ct. Arb.

²⁴⁵ Isabelle Glimcher, *Arbitration of Human and Labor Rights: The Bangladesh Experience*, 52 NYU J. INT'L L. & POL. 231, at 254, 262 (2019); *IndustriALL Global Union*, Case No. 2016-36 Perm. Ct. Arb.; *Uni Global Union*, Case No. 2016-37 Perm. Ct. Arb.

²⁴⁶ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at art. 12 & 22.

²⁴⁷ *In re Arbitration Commenced Pursuant to the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh and the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law Arbitration Rules*, Case Nos. 2016-36 & 2016-37, Procedural Order No. 2 ("Decision on Admissibility Objection and Directions on Confidentiality and Transparency"), para. 20 (Perm. Ct. Arb. 2017), <https://pcacases.com/web/sendAttach/2234>.

²⁴⁸ PERMANENT COURT OF ARBITRATION, *Press Release: Bangladesh Accord Arbitrations Under the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh Between IndustrialALL Global Union and Uni Global Union (As Claimants) and Two Global Fashion Brands (As Respondents)*, PERMANENT COURT OF ARBITRATION 1–2 (2017), <https://docs.pca-cpa.org/2017/10/20171016-Press-Release-No.-1-ENG-1.pdf>; *In re Arbitration Commenced Pursuant to the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh and the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law Arbitration Rules*, Case Nos. 2016-36 & 2016-37, Procedural Order No. 1, para. 104 (Perm. Ct. Arb. 2017), <https://pca-cpa.org/en/cases/152>; Procedural Order No. 2, *supra* note 232, para. 2–3.

²⁴⁹ Glimcher, *supra* note 245 at 267.

²⁵⁰ Barrett et al., *supra* note 3 at 28 n.19.

indeed a legally enforceable agreement and arbitration was a viable vehicle to resolve labor exploitation in value chains claims.

The first consideration is the appropriate jurisdiction, or in other words, which forum should hear a dispute. The text of the original 2013 Accord does not specify the arbitral seat. It simply states, “Upon request of either party, the decision of the SC may be appealed to a final and binding arbitration process.”²⁵¹ The 2018 “Transition” Accord, which sought to prepare the program for operational transfer to Bangladeshi actors, specified the arbitral seat at the Hague and administration by the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA).²⁵² Indeed, the PCA was the agreed upon seat for arbitration in the two arbitral disputes that occurred prior to the 2018 Accord. The PCA may be considered a curious choice, though, since the Bangladesh International Arbitration Centre, the country’s only government-licensed international arbitration institution, was also available at the time.²⁵³ While this avoidance could have several explanations, a compelling one is that the Centre is sponsored by Bangladesh’s Chamber of Commerce,²⁵⁴ which has ties to BGMEA.²⁵⁵

The second consideration is the choice of procedural and substantive law to be applied by the arbitrator, since a forum can apply foreign law.²⁵⁶ The Accord merely provides the chosen procedural law. Clause five of the Accord specifies that the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Model Law on Arbitration should be used to govern the binding arbitration process.²⁵⁷ This is what was applied by the PCA in the two arbitral disputes.²⁵⁸ Ema Vidak-Gojkovic et al. note that the UNCITRAL Model Law is a

²⁵¹ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 5.

²⁵² 2018 Accord, *supra* note 233 at cl. 3.

²⁵³ Bangladesh International Arbitration Centre, *Home*, BANGLADESH INTERNATIONAL ARBITRATION CENTRE (BIAC), <https://www.biac.org.bd/> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²⁵⁴ *Id.*

²⁵⁵ Bangladesh International Chamber of Commerce, *Trade Organizations*, INTERNATIONAL CHAMBER OF COMMERCE BANGLADESH, <https://iccbangladesh.org.bd/trade-organizations/> (last visited Jul 25, 2022) (listing BGMEA as one of its partner trade associations).

²⁵⁶ The choice of law is a central concern in private international law (also known as the law of conflicts or conflicts of law). *See, e.g.*, Gregory S. Alexander, *Application and Avoidance of Foreign Law in the Law of Conflicts*, 70(4) NW. U. L. REV. 602 (1976).

²⁵⁷ *See* 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 5 (“The process for binding arbitration, including, but not limited to, the allocation of costs relating to any arbitration and the process for selection of the Arbitrator, shall be governed by the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration 1985 (with amendments as adopted in 2006).”).

²⁵⁸ Permanent Court of Arbitration, *Bangladesh Accord Arbitrations: Case information*, PERMANENT COURT OF ARBITRATION, <https://pca-cpa.org/en/cases/152/> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

highly unusual choice,²⁵⁹ since it was designed for *states* to use in reforming their laws on arbitral procedure to better resolve international commercial disputes.²⁶⁰ This odd choice may have been the result of confusion or oversight, or it could have been a signal to Bangladesh that the signatories believed its law to be inadequate. The later 2018 Accord modified the procedural law choice, naming the more customary UNCITRAL *Arbitration Rules*.²⁶¹ The UNCITRAL *Arbitration Rules* are designed for the contracting parties' selection to govern the conduct of an arbitration that is intended to resolve a dispute between them.²⁶² It is also notable that the Bangladeshi Arbitration Act of 2001 is not used, although it was substantially formulated based on the UNCITRAL Model Law.²⁶³ Scholars examining the Accord from the perspective of arbitration have noted that both iterations of the Accord are “regrettably imprecise”.²⁶⁴

The applicable substantive contract law is also left unspecified in the 2013 Accord, apparently leaving the decision to the arbitrator. In the two Accord arbitral disputes, the lead firms claimed that Bangladeshi law applied, and the global union federations argued that Dutch law applied.²⁶⁵ The PCA arbitrator proceeded to address the law applicable to the dispute pursuant to Article 35 of the UNCITRAL *Arbitration Rules*.²⁶⁶ Since the SC involves a neutral representative from the ILO and the Accord references a few international standards,²⁶⁷ some scholars have argued that international business and human rights and labor rights were

²⁵⁹ Ema Vidak-Gojkovic et al., *The Medium is the Message: Establishing a System of Business and Human Rights Through Contract Law and Arbitration*, 35(4) J. OF INT'L ARB. *1, *6 (2018), <https://omniastrategy.com/wp-content/uploads/News-Article-The-Medium-is-the-Message-Establishing-a-System-of-Busi...pdf>.

²⁶⁰ United Nations Commission on International Trade Law, *UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration (1985), with amendments as adopted in 2006*, UNCITRAL, https://uncitral.un.org/en/texts/arbitration/modellaw/commercial_arbitration#:~:text=adopted%20in%202006- (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²⁶¹ 2018 Accord, *supra* note 233.

²⁶² United Nations Commission on International Trade Law, *Frequently Asked Questions - Arbitration*, UNCITRAL, <https://uncitral.un.org/en/texts/arbitration/faq#:~:text=Put%20simply%2C%20the%20Model%20Law> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²⁶³ Munir Maniruzzaman, *International Commercial Arbitration in Bangladesh: The New Law*, 70(2) ARB.: THE INT'L J. OF ARB., MEDIATION AND DISP. MGMT. 131, 131 (2004).

²⁶⁴ Vidak-Gojkovic et al., *supra* note 259 at *7; Glimcher, *supra* note 245 at 260.

²⁶⁵ Meshel, *supra* note 241 at 116.

²⁶⁶ Procedural Order No. 1, *supra* note 248 at para. 14.1.

²⁶⁷ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 9.

applicable.²⁶⁸ But before the PCA made its decision of whether to apply Bangladeshi or Dutch law, the parties settled.²⁶⁹

The 2018 Accord updated the choice of law, stating in its final clause that “The Accord shall be governed by the law of the Netherlands.”²⁷⁰ Moreover, the arbitrator is to have experience in business and human rights, or at least human rights law,²⁷¹ suggesting that the applicable substantive law should also consider international labor standards. Thus, the procedural and substantive law are tailored by the Accord contract—a unique benefit of legal contract.

The third and final private international law consideration is how to ensure enforcement of the arbitral decision (or any court order from another jurisdiction). The Accord includes a provision in both of its iterations stating,

Any arbitration award shall be enforceable in a court of law of the domicile of the signatory against whom enforcement is sought and shall be subject to The Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (The New York Convention), where applicable.²⁷²

The New York Convention allows the arbitral award or order to be enforced in a local court.²⁷³ The Convention provides that each state that is signatory to the instrument, “shall recognize arbitral awards as binding and enforce them in accordance with the rules of procedure of the territory where the award is relied upon”.²⁷⁴ Over 160 countries are signatories to the New York Convention, including Bangladesh and every other country where an Accord signatory is based.²⁷⁵ Thus, the local courts of each member of the Accord are required to

²⁶⁸ See, e.g., Glimcher, *supra* note 245 at 261.

²⁶⁹ PERMANENT COURT OF ARBITRATION, *Press Release: Bangladesh Accord Arbitrations Under the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh Between IndustrialALL Global Union and Uni Global Union (As Claimants) and Two Global Fashion Brands (As Respondents)*, PERMANENT COURT OF ARBITRATION 1–3, 2 (2018), <https://perma.cc/JCA9-ZAQ3>.

²⁷⁰ 2018 Accord, *supra* note 233 at cl. 24.

²⁷¹ Judith Levine & Ashwita Ambast, *Responsibility Rising from the Rubble: Lessons from the Bangladesh Accord for Arbitration of Business and Human Rights Disputes*, 25(1) AUSTL. INT’L L.J. 1, 14 (2018).

²⁷² 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 5; 2018 Accord, *supra* note 233 at cl. 3.

²⁷³ Evans, *supra* note 137 at 608.

²⁷⁴ U.N. Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards, July 6, 1988, Art. III <https://www.newyorkconvention.org/11165/web/files/original/1/5/15432.pdf>.

²⁷⁵ The signatories are based throughout Europe, Australia, Canada, Chile, China, Hong Kong, Japan, and Malaysia, all of which are member states of the New York Convention. Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh, *Accord Signatories*, BANGLADESH ACCORD, <https://bangladeshaccord.org/signatories> (last visited Jul

recognize and enforce arbitral awards made against a lead firm that breaches its contractual obligations.²⁷⁶ In other words, any decision the PCA makes would be legally recognizable and enforceable if brought to a court anywhere else that is relevant in the Accord. This is true, unless there is a sharp contradiction in the substantive law of two jurisdictions—for instance, if the decision is opposed to the laws or public policy of Bangladesh.²⁷⁷

In summary, the legal contract played a crucial role in enabling the WSR framework in the Accord. It allowed the signatory parties the ability to tailor several aspects of the dispute resolution mechanism. Namely, the usage of arbitration was key to supporting the Accord. Indeed, the level of compliance with the Accord rose after the two arbitral disputes.²⁷⁸ Jessica Champagne notes in her analysis that, “The filing of the [arbitral] cases contributed to a marked increase in compliance: when enforcement actions were initiated in 2015, only 33 percent of hazards had been corrected; by the time the cases were decided, that figure had reached 80 percent.”²⁷⁹ She notes that while this is partly due to the additional time the parties had to come into compliance with the Accord, anecdotal reports confirm that the global union federations’ choice to aggressively pursue the disputes via arbitration communicated the legal seriousness of the Accord’s enforceability.²⁸⁰ This review also comports with other scholars’ estimation that the legally-binding nature of the Accord gave it a significant advantage over other voluntary CSR-based governance schemes.²⁸¹

The Accord’s nature as a legal contract also enabled the signatories to tailor the arbitration to keep the identities of the lead firm defendants confidential, as in the *IndustriALL Global Union v. [Redacted]* and *Uni Global Union v. [Redacted]* disputes. Keeping the lead

25, 2022); New York Arbitration Convention, *Contacting states*, NEW YORK CONVENTION, <https://www.newyorkconvention.org/countries> (last visited Jul 25, 2022).

²⁷⁶ Evans, *supra* note 137 at 608.

²⁷⁷ Mohammed Abdur Razzak, *Conflict of Laws—State Practice of Bangladesh*, in PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW: SOUTH ASIAN STATES’ PRACTICE 265, 283 & 284 n.93 (Sai Ramani Garimella & Stellina Jolly eds., 2017), <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-981-10-3458-9.pdf>; Bangladesh Bank v. Md. Kasedul Haque Majumder, Civil Revision No. 6159 High Ct. Div., para. 13 (2003) (Bangl.), <https://legislib.com/case/case-details/5aec1e5476ab0b2994b911bb/?search=freedom>.

²⁷⁸ Jessica Champagne, *From Public Relations to Enforceable Agreements: The Bangladesh Accord as a Model for Supply Chain Accountability*, in POWER, PARTICIPATION, AND PRIVATE REGULATORY INITIATIVES: HUMAN RIGHTS UNDER SUPPLY CHAIN CAPITALISM 154, 173 (Daniel M. Brinks et al. ed., 2021) (arguing that the marked increase in compliance from a 33% correction rate to an 80% correction rate was due to the arbitral proceedings).

²⁷⁹ *Id.*

²⁸⁰ *Id.*

²⁸¹ Richard Croucher et al., *Legal Sanction, International Organisations and the Bangladesh Accord*, 48(4) INDUS. L.J. (2019); Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 17.

firms' identities private is an important act when considering the relational aspect of contract and the potential reputational fallout from having their names made public. That is, the signatories were able to reduce the relational costs of bad publicity from public litigation by setting up a private arbitral mechanism. Finally, the legal contract gave the signatories' the ability to control many of the private international law complexities inherent in a transnational WSR program governing a global value chain with multiple parties in different jurisdictions.

As discussed in regard to the FFP, the legal contract facilitates the relational contract,²⁸² since the parties must initially perceive the judiciary to be effective at enforcing their contract, should the need arise.²⁸³ In the Accord, the relevant adjudicator was not local courts but the PCA—a foreign arbitrator. The notion that the arbitral forum may have been worse at facilitating the relational contract than a national court system with a good reputation for effectiveness is examined in closer detail in the following section.

2.3.B.iii. Public-Private Governance Interactions Regarding Contract

While the previous subpart examined how the contract itself enabled the Accord WSR program, this subpart investigates how the competitive interaction between the public and private actors hindered the Accord WSR program. The private actors in the Accord are the members of the Labor Caucus, and the public actors are the Bangladeshi courts and other public institutions, like the Ministry of Labour's Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments (DIFE). Recall the different types of public-private governance interactions described by Cafaggi and Gereffi and Lee: complementarity, cooperation, coordination, displacement, and conflict.

Complementary or cooperative interactions occur when the public and private actors reinforce one another's governance efforts or cooperate to jointly draft rules or merge their governance tasks. This may occur as private actors draft the rules, and the public institution approves or endorses them. Here, the Bangladeshi judiciary is simply not invoked in Accord. Because of the arbitration clause in the Accord, the local courts do not “approve” or “endorse” the terms of the Accord contract and its privately made rules. The closest reference to the public Bangladeshi courts in the text of the Accord is the clause referring to the New York Convention, which addresses the enforceability of an arbitral decision in Bangladesh.

²⁸² Johnson et al., *supra* note 199; Wilkinson-Ryan & Hoffman, *supra* note 197; Baker & Choi, *supra* note 174.

²⁸³ Johnson et al., *supra* note 199.

Furthermore, as opposed to the original WSR's separatist design, the purported intention of the Accord was to "build on" and work with Bangladesh's National Action Plan on Fire Safety, a public initiative by the Ministry of Labour's DIFE to inspect garment factories. The Accord's preamble states explicitly,

The programme will *build on* the National Action Plan on Fire Safety (NAP), which expressly welcomes the development and implementation by any stakeholder of any other activities that would constitute a meaningful contribution to improving fire safety in Bangladesh. The signatories commit to align this programme and its activities with the NAP and to ensure a *close collaboration*, including for example by establishing common programme, liaison and advisory structures.²⁸⁴

However, there was little cooperation with the DIFE in the Accord's operations in the years to follow. Some scholars have described the Accord as a "parallel safety inspectorate" that functioned as a substitute for public authorities.²⁸⁵ Thus, the lack of involvement of the Bangladeshi judiciary in the Accord is not characteristic of a complementary or cooperative public-private interaction.

Neither is there a *coordinative* interaction in the Accord. As Cafaggi defined public-private coordination, public and private institutional actors remain autonomous and independent, but jointly regulate activities in a mutually influential way. This may occur when exchanging information, mutually referring cases, or unilaterally designing private rules to be recognized through judicial or administrative means. In the Accord, the Labor Caucus and the lead firms designed the private rules via contract, but the courts did not apply them. Instead, the PCA interprets and enforces the Accord's provisions and privately made rules. Neither did the DIFE or larger Ministry of Labour refer cases to the Accord's inspectorate.²⁸⁶ Ironically, the Accord aligns more closely with a separatist design than does the FFP, despite the original intent of their respective designers.

²⁸⁴ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at para. 3 (emphasis added).

²⁸⁵ Bartley, *supra* note 39 at 275 (arguing the Accord is unlikely to encourage the Bangladeshi government to enforce its law or build long-term state capacities); Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 975 (arguing the Accord has not been successful in substituting for the local inspectorate, but it has encouraged the Bangladeshi government to change its laws in some superficial ways).

²⁸⁶ *Id.*

Displacement occurs when one type of governance preempts, displaces, or crowds out the other. Gereffi and Lee use CSR as an example of how private governance can crowd out or weaken public labor governance, like local labor institutions.²⁸⁷ *Competition* or *conflict* means the private rules create tensions with local public institutions, potentially through incompatibility or as the private actors take on positions without being subject to the same standards as public governance institutions.²⁸⁸

The Accord program installed its own factory inspection scheme and Safety Inspector,²⁸⁹ although the public institution, the DIFE, already had its own Chief Inspector,²⁹⁰ charged with parallel duties and powers. Moreover, the adjudicative mechanism in the Accord was handed exclusively to an arbitrator. The courts and the public institutions seemed to interpret the Accord's lack of dependence on them as an affront to their authority. The tensions between the Accord's private leadership and the public institutions are evidenced by two court cases regarding the Accord that came before local courts, despite the PCA's stipulated authority over disputes arising in the Accord (as between the signatories). In one of the decisions, the judiciary scrutinized whether the Accord had the authority to perform the functions reserved for the public inspectorate, and the Accord resisted the public institutions' demands. In the other decision, the Court described the Accord's lack of collaboration with the NAP as "defiance"²⁹¹ and found that the Accord regime had improperly "arrogated to itself a unilateral and arbitrary role in implementing safety measures without due oversight of any national authority."²⁹²

The first case demonstrates how the Accord's leadership resisted the public institutions' demands, while the second case exhibits how the High Court considered the Accord to be a competitive or conflicting inspectorate regime.

²⁸⁷ Gereffi & Lee, *supra* note 82 at 34.

²⁸⁸ Cafaggi, *supra* note 34 at 45; Gereffi & Lee, *supra* note 82 at 31–34.

²⁸⁹ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 8.

²⁹⁰ The Labour Act and the National Building Code refer to the duties of the "Chief Inspector" and "inspector" throughout. *See generally* The Bangladesh Labour Act, 2006, *supra* note 138; Bangladesh National Building Code, 2006.

²⁹¹ *Smart Jeans Ltd.*, Writ No. 3826 High Ct. Div. at para. 13.

²⁹² *Id.* at para. 14.

The first case, *Liberty Fashion Wears Limited v. Bangladesh Accord Foundation* (hereinafter *Liberty Fashion*), was filed in 2015.²⁹³ The High Court took up the issue of the Accord performing a public function without being subject to the same standards as public governance institutions. The facts of the case are as follows: The Accord adopted as its own a private factory inspection report performed by Tesco, one of the signatory lead firms, in its own CSR program. The Tesco report found the factory to be dangerous. The Accord adopted the report and, based on its findings, effectively shut down the factory's operations by prohibiting lead firms from purchasing from it. Although the Ministry of Labour and the DIFE's Inspector General repeatedly sent letters to the Accord to inspect the factory,²⁹⁴ the Accord's inspectorate refused several times because it had already accepted Tesco's report.²⁹⁵

The factory owner filed suit, complaining that the stoppage of his business was a violation of his rights to profession and equality under the Bangladeshi Constitution,²⁹⁶ and the refusal to inspect was a breach of the Accord's contractual commitment under Clause 10 of the contract.²⁹⁷ The Clause states that "all factories within the scope of this Agreement shall still be subject to all the provisions of this Agreement, including but not limited to a least one safety inspection carried out by personnel acting under the direction of the [Accord] Safety Inspector."²⁹⁸ On the merits of the case, the Court found the Accord's adoption of Tesco's report to be insufficient because the Accord contract required the private inspectorate to perform its own inspection, instead of relying on the inspection report of a participating lead firm. The Court interpreted Clause 10 as a duty to inspect all Bangladeshi garment factories supplying foreign buyers at least once by an international reputable independent inspector.²⁹⁹ The Court ordered the Accord to inspect the factory itself.³⁰⁰ A follow-up complaint was filed in 2017³⁰¹ because the Accord eventually inspected but still failed to assist the factory in remediating. The Court ordered the Accord to also assist in the remediation process, saying

²⁹³ *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd.*, Writ No. 10929 High Ct. Div. (2016). A follow-up case was brought in 2017 and decided in 2018. The Accord inspected the plaintiff's factory in accordance with the High Court's 2016 order, but the plaintiff factory again brought suit because the Accord did not assist it in its remediation process. See *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd. v. Bangladesh Accord Foundation*, Writ No. 8716, 37 High Ct. Div. 255, 6CLR, para. 1 (2018), <https://legislib.com/case/case-details/5f119672cb53edfaf4a4151c/?>.

²⁹⁴ *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd.*, Writ No. 10929 High Ct. Div. (2016) at 7–8.

²⁹⁵ *Id.*

²⁹⁶ CONSTITUTION OF THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF BANGLADESH Nov. 4, 1972, Part III, arts. 40 & 27.

²⁹⁷ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at cl. 10.

²⁹⁸ *Id.*

²⁹⁹ *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd.*, Writ No. 10929 High Ct. Div. (2016) at 28.

³⁰⁰ *Id.* at 34.

³⁰¹ *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd.*, Writ No. 8716, 37 High Ct. Div. (2018).

the “Accord cannot shirk its responsibilities in the matter of monitoring, supervising and supporting the necessary remediation work of the petitioner’s factory.”³⁰² *Liberty Fashion* indicates the Accord’s repeatedly resistant stance to the public institutions’ authority. The Accord was willing to take on a public governance function but unwilling to be subject to the authority of public governance institutions—fostering a competitive interaction.

The second case, *Smart Jeans Limited v. Stitching Bangladesh Accord Foundation* (hereinafter *Smart Jeans*), was filed in 2017 by another supplier.³⁰³ The High Court’s ruling dismantled the Accord’s foreign-run operations. The factory in this case was inspected by the Alliance for Bangladesh Worker Safety (the Alliance), a CSR-type private inspection program run by North American lead firms. The Alliance’s inspection found the factory to be dangerous. The Accord adopted the Alliance’s findings and suspended the factory’s participation until their remediations were complete. The Accord and the Alliance had an informal understanding that if one of them inspected a factory, the other would adopt its findings to avoid duplicating inspections during the remediation process. The Accord, departing from this norm, inspected the Alliance-inspected factory during its remediations, and found the factory to be in violation, thus terminating its participation in the Accord trade group.

The Court found that the Accord had been acting “unilaterally” as a private governance mechanism³⁰⁴ and “without due oversight by any national authority”.³⁰⁵ Furthermore, the Court stated the “Accord has indeed arrogated to itself a unilateral and arbitrary role in implementing safety measures without due oversight of any national authority.”³⁰⁶ The Court acted on its own motion to end the Accord’s foreign-run office by November 2018, ordering its locally-run replacement to be a “more equitable regime of collective and coordinated function of all partners/stakeholders”, including factory owners.³⁰⁷

Scholars examining the Accord’s interaction with the local inspectorate have come to similar conclusions as the High Court. Donaghey and Reinecke state that the Accord allowed for “brands, rather than states... to become the ultimate enforcer in employment relations”.³⁰⁸

³⁰² *Id.* at paras. 72–76.

³⁰³ *Smart Jeans Ltd.*, Writ No. 3826 High Ct. Div.

³⁰⁴ *Id.* at para. 7.

³⁰⁵ *Id.* at para. 6.

³⁰⁶ *Id.* at para. 14.

³⁰⁷ *Id.*

³⁰⁸ Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 15.

Bartley expressed his concern that the Accord attempted to bypass or substitute for the state in order to secure lead firm accountability.³⁰⁹ Bair et al. find that the Accord’s governance regime did not succeed in substituting or bypassing the state, although they also suggest that it attempted to do so.³¹⁰

In conclusion, the Accord appeared to have the potential to be a cooperative—or at least coordinative—public-private interaction, but both the public and private actors found each other’s efforts to conflict with their operations. Both the *Liberty Fashion* and the *Smart Jeans* cases demonstrate the Accord’s tension-filled relationship with the Bangladeshi High Court and the public inspectorate. In *Liberty Fashion*, the Accord’s disposition was characteristic of a competitive interaction between it and the DIFE, as well as the Court itself. In *Smart Jeans*, the Court found the Accord to be directly competing with the authority of the local inspectorate.

Most notably, the Bangladeshi courts reviewed these two cases, despite the stipulation for arbitration, because the non-signatory suppliers were the plaintiffs. Recall that only the signatories may seek arbitral adjudication per the terms of the Accord’s legal contract, although they serve an important role in the relational contract.³¹¹ The suppliers are essentially left out of the legal contract, not only in terms of control in the SC (which makes sense in the supply chain collective bargaining model of WSR), but most importantly, they were left without an external review or appeal mechanism. Indeed, the Court addressed this matter in the 2015 *Liberty Fashion* case, finding that the Court had jurisdiction to hear the case because it had no opportunity for review otherwise.³¹² Since the suppliers were unable to seek external review under the Accord contract, this left the Accord vulnerable to review in the local courts, which led to the *Liberty Fashion* and *Smart Jeans* cases, and ultimately the dismantlement of the Accord WSR program.

Despite the comparative advantages of arbitration as an adjudication mechanism over ordinary courts, especially in a transnational contract setting like in the case of the Accord, it

³⁰⁹ Bartley, *supra* note 39 at 275.

³¹⁰ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 975.

³¹¹ The exclusion of the suppliers also extended to their exclusion from the SC, since its “employer” seat was filled by representatives of the lead firms, not the suppliers. *See* Donaghey & Reinecke, *supra* note 151 at 15.

³¹² *Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd.*, Writ No. 10929 High Ct. Div. (2016) at 21–28 (finding that the High Court had jurisdiction under Article 102 of the Bangladeshi Constitution, which provides for the Court’s special jurisdiction to provide relief in disputes where there is otherwise no relief available, provided that the offending person is performing a function in connection with the “affairs of the Republic”); *see also* CONSTITUTION OF THE PEOPLE’S REPUBLIC OF BANGLADESH Nov. 4, 1972, Part VI, Chapter 1, art. 102.

may have served to disrupt the legal contract's facilitation of the relational contract—specifically as to the suppliers. The Accord's relational impact on the suppliers is a unique result of the WSR structure that is not accounted for in other kinds of transnational contracts. Exclusion of the suppliers in the legal contract, particularly as to their right to review, seems to have undermined the reality in the three-way relational contract and further entrenched a hostile interaction between the Accord and the public institutions.

2.3.C. WSR and Contract: Comparison of the Two Case Studies

Both of the case studies, the FFP and the Accord, are built as part of the same WSR private labor governance model, but there are some key differences in how each addresses: (i) the relationship between the relational and legal contract and (ii) the public-private interaction.

2.3.C.i. The Relational and Legal Contract

Upon first glance, the FFP and the Accord appear to possess the same contractual framework that should facilitate its governance functions as to lead firms and suppliers in their respective value chains. However, a significant distinction is that the legal contract created in each WSR program recognizes a different right to adjudicative review for the suppliers. Moreover, the end results of each WSR program have been quite different as well—one program continuing successfully without adjudication and the other going through adjudication and ending prematurely.

In both of the WSR programs, the relational aspect of the WSR contracts intimately connects the suppliers to the trade group. Yet the two case studies' legal protections extend very differently to the suppliers and afford them different rights to review in the formal contracts. In the FFP, although the suppliers are not signatories, their right to appeal an FFSC decision through arbitration is recognized.³¹³ This is contrasted sharply in the Accord, where the suppliers do not have a recognized right to appeal in the contract, either through arbitration or another adjudicative mechanism.

While it may not appear to be a major difference in and of itself, the difference in the treatment of suppliers in the formal contract is significant for two reasons. Firstly, the opportunity for review likely communicates a level of fairness on part of the WSR program,

³¹³ Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 524 n.163.

which is important to facilitating the relational contract with the suppliers.³¹⁴ For example, in the FFP, there was a single instance of arbitral review for a supplier that appealed an FFSC decision, and it occurred without threatening the operation of the FFP.³¹⁵ Since the nature of the WSR framework is such that the suppliers are effectively bound by terms of a contract to which they never agreed, the provision for the suppliers' right to review by an external adjudicator gives some minimum assurance of fairness in the program's operations.

Secondly, and relatedly, if there is no review mechanism for the suppliers, they will likely turn to the public courts for the same function, as occurred in the Accord. Turning to the local courts, while not inherently a hindrance to WSR, can challenge its authority and cause the public institutions to scrutinize its legitimacy. In other words, the act of the suppliers lodging a complaint in local courts may itself increase the chances for a public-private interaction that hinders WSR. The transnationality of a WSR program that attempts to govern a global value chain further complicates the matter. The uncertainty of the proper forum and applicable law casts a shadow over the legal contract's ability to facilitate relational contracts, especially for the lead firms and workers' representatives vis-à-vis the suppliers.

2.3.C.ii. The Public-Private Interaction

The public-private interaction in the FFP and the Accord also varied. Most notably, the FFP facilitated a coordinative interaction between the Florida courts and the WSR program, as well as a coordinative interaction between the public institutions (i.e., the Department of Labor) and the WSR program. The Accord, on the other hand, exhibited a competitive interaction between the Bangladeshi courts and the WSR program, as well as competitive or displacement-oriented interaction between the public institutions (i.e., the Ministry of Labour and the DIFE) and the WSR program.

The characteristics of these public-private interactions matter because they demonstrate the real-life outcomes of the relationship between WSR and its surrounding legal and

³¹⁴ L. Hawthorne, *Relational Contract Theory, Principles of European Contract Law - Long-Term Contracts, and the Impact of Implicit Dimensions*, 70(3) TYDSKRIF VIR HEDENDAAGSE ROMEINS-HOLLANDSE REG. (J. OF CONTEMP. ROMAN-DUTCH L.) 371, 388 (2007) (neo-classical contract law with its commitment to good faith and fairness is capable of accommodating the relational contract); Speidel, *supra* note 175 at 837 (there is enough flexibility in modern contract law, provided by considerations of good faith and public policy, to accommodate the relational contract).

³¹⁵ FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 39 ("As a testament to the Program's fair, objective, and thorough approach, there has been only one such appeal to date.").

institutional environment. A coordinative interaction, as seen in the FFP, appears to have facilitated or enabled WSR. A competitive interaction, as seen in the Accord, seems to have severely hindered its functions. To describe some possible explanations for why these differences occurred, at least three characteristics should be considered: (i) the differences in adjudicative mechanisms and the related length and transnationality of the governed value chains, (ii) the set duration of the contracts, and (iii) the extent of regulatory activity prior to the WSR program's implementation.

First, the FFP and Accord used two different mechanisms for adjudication of contractual disputes. The FFP used local courts for formal contract enforcement, while Accord used arbitration. The difference led to a different sort of public-private interaction in each WSR program, as between the judicial institutions and the WSR program's leadership. In the FFP, the legal provision of court-based adjudication for the signatories demonstrated the private governance program's willingness to work with the public institutions or at least to come under their authority. This also comports with the general operations of the FFP, where the private inspectorate coordinated with public authorities by referring cases and aiding them in their work.³¹⁶ In the Accord, the formal contract did not provide for Bangladeshi court review, instead opting for arbitral adjudication. While this is a natural choice for a transnational contract that governs a global value chain involving parties with differing nationalities, the choice distanced the Accord from the local authorities. This also aligned with the general operations of the Accord, where the private inspectorate did not cooperate or coordinate with the National Action Program, the Chief Inspector of the DIFE, or the larger Ministry of Labour.³¹⁷ The overall public-private interactions in the Accord reflected competition, not cooperation.

Relatedly, the length and transnationality of the value chain governed by the WSR program is of consequence to the decision to arbitrate in the Accord. Practical private international law questions can be a source of tension for the signatories, as well as the private

³¹⁶ This refers to the co-enforcement by the CIW and the Department of Labor and Department of Justice, as well as local authorities. *See* Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52 at 15 & 18; U.S. Dep't of Just., *supra* note 130; E.E.O.C. v. DiMare Ruskin, Inc., No. 2:11-cv-158-FtM-99SPC, 2012 U.S. Dist. WL 12067868 (2012). For information on the co-enforcement model, see Fine 2018, *supra* note 49; Fine 2017, *supra* note 49.

³¹⁷ Rather, the Accord ran a parallel inspectorate program. For arguments of whether this dynamic challenged the local inspectorate to improve or not, see Bartley, *supra* note 39 at 275 (arguing the Accord is unlikely to encourage the Bangladeshi government to enforce its law or build long-term state capacities); Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 975 (arguing the Accord has not been successful in substituting for the local inspectorate, but it has encouraged the Bangladeshi government to change its laws in some superficial ways).

program vis-à-vis the public courts. These include the choice of appropriate forum and law and effective methods to ensure enforcement of a foreign judgment, which were necessary considerations in the Accord that were simply not needed in the FFP. While other scholars have examined the additional complexities arising from the transnational nature of the Accord, these have pertained mostly to market consequences³¹⁸—not to how the complexity of the value chain influences the legal considerations. The Accord governed a global value chain with various parties from jurisdictions around the world, making the appropriate jurisdiction and law less than patent. These issues made it more sensible for the Labour Caucus and lead firms to opt for foreign arbitration. The FFP signatories, on the other hand, have no such need for arbitration because the value chain is domestic, and the signatories are all domiciled in the U.S. and doing business in Florida. Thus, the length and transnationality of the value chain appears to affect the public-private interaction through the choice and forum of adjudication method (as well as the applicable law), thereby enabling WSR in domestic programs and hindering WSR in transnational ones.

Second, the length of the contracts could have set different expectations for the public institutions. In the Accord, the contract had an expiration clause, stating that the safety program would operate for a period of five years.³¹⁹ Ter Haar and Keune note that the uncertainty regarding the reality of the Accord after its expiration casted doubt on the workers' long-time rights.³²⁰ Bair et al., in their analysis, suggest that the governmental officials and garment industry leaders used the Accord's five-year limit to argue for a return of control to the local DIFE inspectorate.³²¹ The public officials' actions seem to indicate that they did not think the Accord was an arrangement that would permanently change the Bangladeshi garment industry.³²² This is consistent with the relational contract literature that finds contracts are more effective in the context of long-term relationships.³²³ Rather, the garment industry perceived the Accord as a short-term program that was useful for immediate concerns about the future of the garment industry after Rana Plaza, but could be dismissed after the industry

³¹⁸ Siegmann et al., *supra* note 4 at 122–23; Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 507 n.66, 526–27, 529–31; Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1; Blasi & Bair, *supra* note 4; Brudney, *supra* note 52 at 374–76; Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52.

³¹⁹ 2013 Accord, *supra* note 152 at para. 2.

³²⁰ Haar & Keune, *supra* note 52 at 24–25.

³²¹ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 987.

³²² *Id.* at 991.

³²³ Macaulay (1963), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (2001), *supra* note 175; Bernstein (1992), *supra* note 175; Macneil, *supra* note 175; Macaulay (2000), *supra* note 175; Speidel, *supra* note 175.

stabilized.³²⁴ The FFP does not appear to be self-expiring. If anything, the CIW views itself as “the new Department of Labor” for the agricultural industry³²⁵ and shows no signs of stopping. The intended length of the WSR program may have affected the relational contract, which depends on the repeated and long-term relationship of the contracting parties. Thus, the Accord may have established the state’s expectation of its own expiration when the original contract was signed. When the Accord’s foreign leadership refused to step down because they did not believe that the Bangladeshi authorities were equipped to take over its operations,³²⁶ another competitive public-private interaction ensued.

Third, the extent of regulatory activity prior to the WSR program’s implementation may also help explain why the FFP and the Accord had such different public-private governance interactions, even aside from the WSR programs’ reliance on the judiciary. The idea is simple—the more public regulatory activity there is, the more likely the WSR program’s private system will conflict with existing public efforts. In the tomato fields in Florida, there was not much public regulatory activity to speak of when the FFP began. Vosko et al. explain that the FFP “emerged in a context in which government inspection and enforcement was virtually non-existent leaving a vacuum that community coalitions sought to fill.”³²⁷ This is contrasted with the garment factories in Bangladesh where, prior to the Accord’s creation, there was a thick preexisting layer of public regulation, although its efficacy was quite low due to underenforcement.³²⁸

In an analysis of the legal protections for temporary migrant agricultural workers in Ontario, Canada, Vosko et al. argue that an FFP-type private governance program would be unsuccessful in Ontario. They explain that this would be the case because the employment law is already highly regulated and under the authority of a centralized public institution, making it inhospitable to private regimes like WSR.³²⁹ The Accord here is comparable to the situation Vosko et al. describe in Ontario. Essentially, the Accord’s private rules and operations created

³²⁴ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 988.

³²⁵ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 16 at 15; Geraldo Reyes Chavez, *Food Chains*, DIRECTED BY SANJAY RAWAL (2014).

³²⁶ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 987.

³²⁷ Leah F. Vosko et al., *Enforcing Employment Standards for Temporary Migrant Agricultural Workers in Ontario, Canada: Exposing Underexplored Layers of Vulnerability*, 35 INT’L J. OF COMP. LAB. L. AND INDUS. REL. 227, 254 n.81 (2019), <https://clcw.queenslaw.ca/sites/clcwwww/files/CLCW%20Papers/Migration%20and%20Work/Paper%20004%20Vosko%20Tucker%20and%20Casey%20Enforcing%20Employment%20Standards%20for%20Temporary%20Migrant%20Agricultural%20Workers%20in%20Ontario.pdf>.

³²⁸ Boudreau, *supra* note 137; Evans, *supra* note 137; Bair et al., *supra* note 52 at 974.

³²⁹ Vosko et al., *supra* note 327.

through private contract repeatedly clashed against the public institutions and legal system when the rules and systems were duplicative.

In summary, I have highlighted three distinct considerations that may help to explain why the FFP and the Accord had such different public-private interactions despite apparently similar contractual frameworks. I identified three factors as potential explanations. First, the differences in adjudicative mechanisms in the contract and the transnationality of the governed value chains determines the WSR programs' reliance on local courts, which may be indicative of whether an interaction with courts will be enabling of WSR or not. Second, using a predetermined expiration of the contracts may lead the public institutions to expect the WSR program will not be renewed, so an attempt to renew it would be considered a competitive move. Third, and finally, the pervasiveness of preexisting regulatory activity prior to the WSR program's implementation likely heightens the chances for a competitive, rather than a coordinative or other WSR-enabling public-private interaction.

There are undoubtedly other factors at play, both within the ambit of the legal system and outside of it. One notable example might be the distinction in the two case studies regarding the level of worker involvement. The FFP appears to have a much higher level of participation from the workers on-the-ground versus the Accord.³³⁰ As Janice Fine has argued, worker involvement is important because the workers are in the best position to know what is happening on the ground (because state investigation and audit mechanisms will never have the resources to reach the same information), and worker organizations generate more trust than the state can.³³¹ However, the scope of this work has been closely tailored to examining only the private-public interactions involving law, and even more narrowly than that, to those in contract. Comparative research on this and related topics would be fruitful to better understand how WSR operates in its greater context.

³³⁰ For instance, the FFP Code is formulated by employees, while the Accord was created primarily by global union federations. See Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 510 (“a code of conduct drafted with the direct input of the workers”); see Juliane Reinecke & Jimmy Donaghey, *After Rana Plaza: Building coalitional power for labour rights between unions and (consumption-based) social movement organisations*, 22(5) ORGANIZATION 720, 729–30 (2015) (describing how the Accord was based on an earlier draft of an agreement headed by Worker Rights Consortium and the Clean Clothes Campaign). Additionally, the FFP was built by the farmworkers themselves. The workers marched and protested during the FFP's Fair Food Campaign. Although Bangladeshi trade unions took to the streets after the Rana Plaza Disaster, the real catalyst was the Disaster itself. See Asbed & Hitov, *supra* note 3 at 505 n.52; see Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8 at 11–12.

³³¹ See Fine 2018, *supra* note 49 at 149–54; Fine 2017, *supra* note 49 at 364–66 (2017).

2.3.C.iii. Summary

To review, this subpart has discussed the comparison of the two case studies in regard to three points of analysis—the relational contract, the formal contract, and the public-private interactions involving contract adjudication. I first considered the differences in the relationship between the legal and relational contract in the FFP and Accord, focusing particularly on how the formal contract in each program recognized a different right to adjudicative review for the suppliers. The Accord stood out as the example of how the exclusion of suppliers from a review right neglected their role in the WSR relational contract. I found this difference to be important because the provision for review communicates the WSR program’s fairness toward the suppliers. Additionally, if the suppliers are unable to seek appeal through arbitration, they will likely turn to the local courts as a last resort, which may be competitively primed to challenge the WSR program’s private authority.

I then considered the differences between the FFP and Accord in regard to the public-private interaction, where the former program exhibited a cooperative interaction, and the latter displayed a competitive one. There are several explanations related to contract that may explain why the public-private interaction was cooperative in the FFP and competitive in the Accord. These include the differences in the: adjudicative mechanisms in the contract and the transnationality of the governed chains, usage of an expiration clause in the contracts, and extent of the preexisting regulatory activity prior to the WSR program’s implementation.

2.4. Part 2 Summary

In Part 2, I addressed the contract’s interaction with WSR in both the FFP and the Accord, first introducing the case studies and then moving into the analysis of how the relational and formal contract were mutually influential, as well as the interactions of the public and private governance regimes.

Overarching this Part is the premise that the WSR contract is more than just a legal contract that connects the workers’ representatives and the lead firms. Although the WSR regime’s key innovation is the facilitation of bargaining between the workers and the lead firms up the supply chain (thereby seemingly bypassing bargaining with the suppliers), a relational aspect that includes the suppliers remains significant to WSR’s functions. That is, unlike other labor contracts that extend legally and relationally only between workers and their direct employers, WSR specifically regulates the suppliers, and ultimately depends on their relational

and legal incentives under the lead firms to comply in the trade group. The suppliers' involvement in the contract becomes particularly important when they request review of a decision made by the WSR's oversight committee. If there is an option available to arbitrate, as in the FFP, the supplier can do so without causing any long-term disruption to the WSR trade group.³³² If there is no option to arbitrate, the supplier turns to the local courts that may have an interest in dismantling the WSR program, as in the Accord.³³³

I have also argued in this Part that the WSR contract requires a public-private interaction that enables it or, at the very least, does not hinder it. A cooperative interaction, as seen in the FFP, may not necessarily be the optimal WSR interaction with public institutions—but it is at least functional. A displacement or competitive interaction, as seen in the Accord, appears to be a bad sign for a WSR program.

The question of why the differences in public-private interactions occurred might be attributed to a variety of reasons, but I identified a handful on which to focus that are related to contract. These include the adjudicative mechanisms in the contract and the transnationality of the governed chains, the usage of an expiration clause in the contracts, and the extent of the preexisting regulatory activity prior to the WSR program's implementation. That is, the transnationality of a chain will make arbitration more attractive as a primary adjudication method but, naturally, will reduce the signatories' submission of the program to the local court authority. At the same time, the use of arbitration as an appeal method for suppliers may assure them of the WSR program's trustworthiness, and failure to provide a review mechanism may lead the program back to local courts. A competitive interaction may become more likely as the WSR contract governs topics that are already highly regulated by public institutions, and as the private contract sets an expectation of a short-term WSR program with a self-termination clause.

PART 3. PRELIMINARY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR AN OPTIMAL INTERACTION BETWEEN THE WSR CONTRACT AND PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

Whereas Part 2 was descriptive and analytical—addressing how publicly-given law and private WSR governance have interacted—Part 3 is normative. I aim to offer some preliminary recommendations for an optimal interaction between the WSR contract and the public

³³² Indeed, this is what happened in the FFP. See FFSC 2021 Report, *supra* note 6 at 39.

³³³ Bair et al., *supra* note 52 (arguing the state of Bangladesh had an interest in getting rid of the Accord).

institutions. These recommendations are based on the arguments and findings in the comparison of the two case studies in Part 2.

To reiterate the caveats made at the beginning of this project, the legal analysis is merely one part of a larger puzzle. In order for WSR to be replicated responsibly and well, it must account for the legal landscape, as well as other non-legal factors that are beyond the scope of the present analysis. A handful of scholars, such as Bair and Babineau,³³⁴ Blasi and Bair,³³⁵ Fine and Bartley,³³⁶ Sellers,³³⁷ Brudney,³³⁸ Dias-Abey,³³⁹ have identified a number of such considerations in their works. These considerations include the market structure (including the susceptibility of lead firms to civil society-backed campaign mobilization), the value chain dynamics (primarily the unequal bargaining power of lead firms and suppliers, so the former can use their weight against the latter to require them to meet program standards), and the willingness of consumers to put pressure on lead firms.

Dias-Abey's work addresses the particular power of anti-trafficking law in supporting the CIW's creation of the FFP.³⁴⁰ However, Bair and Babineau recently pointed to a consideration that has not been well-addressed in the literature thus far—the importance of a functioning judicial regime capable of upholding the WSR contracts in the event of a dispute.³⁴¹ This project has attempted to make some headway toward filling this gap in the literature, although the role of contract is undoubtedly just one of several factors that are key to understanding why WSR has bloomed in some locales but stunted in others.

Moreover, the following recommendations are ultimately synthesized from merely two discrete instances of WSR, albeit from detailed case studies. Future case studies of the structure and role of the WSR contracts in the Milk with Dignity WSR program in Vermont and the Gender Justice Program in Lesotho would add a depth and richness of comparative information to the analysis, especially once more information on them is available. Nevertheless, the unprecedented success of the FFP and its coordinative interrelation with the American legal system, contrasted with the mixed success of the Accord and its competitive interrelation with

³³⁴ Babineau & Bair, *supra* note 4.

³³⁵ Blasi & Bair, *supra* note 4.

³³⁶ Fine & Bartley, *supra* note 1.

³³⁷ Sellers, *supra* note 62.

³³⁸ Brudney, *supra* note 52 at 374–76.

³³⁹ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 8; Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14; Dias-Abey, *supra* note 16.

³⁴⁰ Dias-Abey, *supra* note 14.

³⁴¹ *Id.*

the Bangladeshi legal system, already provide useful indicators for future private-public labor governance relations.

I intend for these recommendations to be useful to workers and labor activists (together “WSR proponents”) who wish to create and sustain WSR programs. This is a compilation of suggested actions for WSR proponents to adapt the WSR contract for a given legal environment. Underlying this Part is the premise that the WSR contract should strive to facilitate at least a coordinative interaction with public authorities and avoid a competitive interaction. The focus on contract law’s role with regard to WSR is a particularly relevant factor to consider when attempting to establish such a program in labor-repressive jurisdictions with scant or under-enforced labor and employment law, since WSR makes use of another area of law—contract—to establish private governance. If there were adequate labor protections that allowed the farmworkers in Florida or the garment workers in Bangladesh to effectively organize and create collective bargaining agreements to better their working conditions, there would have been no need for WSR. The issue, rather, is how WSR proponents can use contract law to strengthen their bargaining positions when they have been marginalized and cannot turn to the ordinary routes of labor and employment law.

3.1. Choice of Adjudicative Mechanism

WSR proponents should pay attention to the different adjudicative mechanisms available to them and make their choice of dispute resolution method and forum with care. The need for such a mechanism may arise in two situations—when the signatories have a dispute for violation of contract and when the suppliers are under scrutiny for violation of the WSR rules. In the first instance, it is better for the signatories to subject the WSR program to local courts and local law, if it is jurisdictionally and politically practicable. The case studies indicate that the act of subjecting the WSR program to local law may itself gesture to the local authorities that the WSR leadership and regime is willing to cooperate with them—or at least not to challenge their authority.

The second situation that the contract should address is the mechanism available for suppliers’ appeals of the WSR oversight board’s decisions. Although it is unclear whether it is better to secure their right to review through arbitration or the local courts, the WSR contract should make certain to secure the suppliers’ right to review the board’s holdings in some fashion. The review mechanism gestures to the suppliers that the WSR leadership is running a trustworthy operation in good faith and is willing to let an external party review its decisions.

External review also shows that the signatories recognize the suppliers' important role in the WSR trade group, and hence relational contract. Practically, providing for such a mechanism in the contract also sets limits on and provides guidance for the suppliers' right to review. This may prevent a situation where suppliers turn to the courts that take an aggressive stance against the private governance program—for imposing restrictions on parties that are not contract signatories and not answering to public authorities—deciding to dismantle the program altogether, as occurred with the Accord.

Intuitively, arbitration appears to be better for achieving this end (e.g., to control details of the arbitral process like procedure and privacy). Nonetheless, any kind of review mechanism for the suppliers is likely better than none, which—especially when the base contract between the signatories is not subject to local courts or law—opens the contract to scrutiny from a potentially hostile judicial authority.

3.2. Transnationality of the Governed Value Chain

Another important consideration for WSR proponents is the location of the contract's signatories. When the prospective value chain extends over national borders, the contract's enforceability becomes complicated for jurisdictional and practical reasons. Global value chains make arbitration a particularly attractive alternative to court-based litigation when the lead firms are headquartered and operating in different jurisdictions than the WSR proponents or the workers. Although it makes practical sense for the WSR contract to be arbitrated, rather than litigated, arbitration eliminates the possibility of the signatories subjecting themselves to public institutions. Related to the recommendation in the subpart above, this may signal to the judiciary that the WSR program is unwilling to come under local authority.

As such, proponents should attempt to compensate via other means. Firstly, it is recommended that they attempt to maintain good relations with both the court and the suppliers, which is particularly important in global value chains, as well as strive to prevent disputes from escalating to court-based litigation in the first instance. This may mean strengthening the relational contract between the suppliers and the signatories (for example, through providing them a review mechanism as a signal of trustworthiness and good faith), so suppliers do not think it is necessary to litigate. The WSR proponents should also take care to make extra gestures of goodwill to the public institutions, since even small oversights (like the choice of arbitral law in the Accord contract) may contribute to potentially major problems. Secondly, if the court is already involved in adjudication, the WSR leadership should ensure that it

thoroughly follows the contractual terms it has agreed to for itself. *Liberty Fashion* in the Accord stands as a pointed example of how its leadership did not follow the WSR contract to-the-letter in its obligation to inspect the factory itself. Third, the WSR proponents may generally attempt to foster more trust with the public institutions through other means. One possible way to accomplish this might be to use the local contract law, even if the mechanism is arbitration because local courts are an impractical venue. This may indicate to the state that the WSR program recognizes its sovereignty and authority in the matter.

Finally, the WSR proponents should carefully investigate and map out the differing jurisdictions that may come into play when a foreign arbitral award (or a court decision) is issued. Private international law issues are of particular import, as the signatories are likely situated in different jurisdictions. The involved nations' membership in the New York Convention will dictate whether the arbitral award or foreign decision can be honored and enforced. Another factor is the national law governing arbitration disputes, which determines the extent of national adoption of the New York Convention and other relevant law, like the UNCITRAL Model Arbitral Rules. The proponents should also consider the state's contract law and precedent. If the foreign arbitral award or judgment is reliant upon rules that sharply contravene the local law, the state court will not enforce the award. For instance, in Bangladesh, the High Court recognizes public order limitations, permitting a judge to refuse to recognize or enforce an arbitral award if it is opposed to the laws or public policy of the state.³⁴²

3.3. Duration of the WSR Contract

A less substantial recommendation is to consider not limiting the duration of the WSR contract to a set period or at least clarifying the wind-down process of the program. A set expiration clause may indicate to the state that the program is merely a temporary measure that will automatically cease operations. When the WSR program shows no intention of ceasing its operations, a competitive interaction may ensue.

However, an expiration clause may be a necessary concession in the bargaining process between the signatories, and potentially as between the state and the signatories. In this case, the WSR proponents should pay even more attention to securing good relations with the public institutions and state at large. Signatories may also specify in the WSR contract what will be the procedures for closure of the WSR program, how that will be determined, and by whom.

³⁴² Razzak, *supra* note 277; *Md. Kasedul Haque Majumder*, Civil Revision No. 6159 High Ct. Div., para. 13.

3.4. Extent of Regulatory Activity Prior to the WSR Program's Implementation

Proponents of WSR should also examine the extent and pervasiveness of the existing regulatory activity. Although the workers who find themselves in the situation where they need WSR do not have the luxury of choosing the legal jurisdiction they fall under, they and their representatives should consider the thickness of the layers of regulatory activity that already exist, and whether the public institutions may be potential allies or rivals. The FFP is an example of where the regulatory field was mostly vacant for the tomato farmworkers, and the public authorities were willing to coordinate with the WSR program. If there is already a heavily active local inspectorate, the chances may be that there is less opportunity or “room” for a successful private governance program that performs the same functions. The problem is accentuated when the inspectorate is highly politicized, like in Bangladesh.³⁴³

This recommendation realistically contends with the ability of the WSR contract to set up a private governance scheme where it directly conflicts with public institutions' functions. However, there is reason for a measure of cautious optimism, even where there are existing public authorities on the ground. Although the FFP's regulatory activities were not nearly as expansive as the Accord's inspectorate, the CIW managed to coordinate with the public regulatory institutions to enable the WSR program. Their coordinative interaction, however, was likely founded on years of co-enforcement between the CIW and the local authorities. That is, the CIW strategically partnered with state officials to help educate workers on their rights and patrol their labor markets to identify engaged in unethical and illegal practices (i.e., *co-enforcement*)³⁴⁴ even before creating the FFP.³⁴⁵ Perhaps a starting point for WSR proponents is to adopt co-enforcement mechanisms where practicable—in the image of alt-labor organizations—thereby setting the stage for a WSR program to come.

³⁴³ Staff Correspondent, *Beware of conspiracy against RMG sector: PM*, PROTHOMALO, December 7, 2014, <https://en.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/Beware-of-conspiracy-against-RMG-sector-PM>; Tamanna Rubya, *The Ready-Made Garment Industry: An Analysis of Bangladesh's Labor Law Provisions After the Savar Tragedy*, 40(2) BROOK. J. OF INT'L L. 685, 689 (2015), <https://brooklynworks.brooklaw.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1042&context=bjil>; Sajjadur Rahman, *Owners probe owners' fault*, THE DAILY STAR (2013), <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/owners-probe-owners-fault>. Also note that BGMEA plays a quasi-public institution role, having the authority to issue certificates of origin and customs documents relating to the import of fabric and materials, as well as authority to conduct investigations of fatal workplace incidents.

³⁴⁴ Fine 2018, *supra* note 49 at 146.

³⁴⁵ See Mieres & McGrath, *supra* note 52 at 15 & 18; U.S. Dep't of Just., *supra* note 130; E.E.O.C. v. DiMare Ruskin, Inc., No. 2:11-cv-158-FtM-99SPC, 2012 U.S. Dist. WL 12067868 (2012).

3.5. Part 3 Summary

In this Part, I have set forth four primary recommendations for WSR proponents who wish to promulgate and sustain WSR programs. These are to opt for local court adjudication for primary disputes between the signatories where practicable, and to ensure the suppliers are recognized members in the WSR relational and legal contracts. An important way to recognize the suppliers' role is by contractually providing for their ability to seek external review. I also recommend that the proponents of WSR contend carefully with the transnationality of the governed value chain. Not only is the length of the value chain important, as others have noted before, but the jurisdictional considerations significantly complicate adjudication and enforcement, as well as obfuscate relational contract ties. Additionally, I recommend that the WSR contract not set a predetermined durational limit to the WSR contract. Or, if the contract must have such a limit, that the terms for how and why it may be terminated are clear. Finally, I recommend that the WSR proponents examine the thickness of the regulatory activity on the ground prior to the WSR program's arrival and consider whether a WSR program may have a chance of coordinative interaction with existing public institutions.

PART 4. CONCLUSION

Many scholars view WSR as the most promising and viable existing model of value chain governance, yet its replication and diffusion have proved challenging. WSR has been attempted a handful a times, but only one of these has enjoyed lasting success in improving labor conditions. Furthermore, WSR advocates have faced difficulty replicating and sustaining WSR in more complicated, global value chains. Nevertheless, WSR presents a promising model of value chain labor governance because it concretely addresses CSR's and MSIs' problems with weak monitoring and lack of enforcement that flow from exaggerated corporate power and a lack of workers' participation.

Through this research, I have attempted to investigate whether and to what extent existing contract structures and public legal institutions have played a role in supporting and hindering WSR, by focusing particularly on the contract structures enabling the establishment of WSR trade groups. The aspects of contract examined include the formal and relational facets of WSR contracts, as well as the interactions between public and private actors in the FFP and the Accord programs. I have distilled several recommendations therefrom that provide new insight into how WSR contracts and public-private contractual relationships may be adapted to promote the development of WSR in more value chains, especially in global ones.

The literature indicates clearly that there are certain background conditions that render WSR unsuitable, such as when the lead firms are not susceptible to reputational damage from consumers or when they operate in geographically dispersed and mobile industries. Still, research into the legal environment in which WSR operated remains extremely limited. I propose that the existing list of background conditions—which currently concerns primarily the market dynamics of a proposed locale for WSR—would be amiss to discount the role of contract and associated legal institutions in the proposed locale. The judiciary in particular has the power to not only interpret and enforce the WSR contract, but it also has the ability to restructure or even dismantle a WSR program.

The primary finding of this work is that contract law and public institutions do play a role the ability of WSR to form and function. Yet the contracts from the most successful WSR program—the FFP—have never had reason to be litigated. Nevertheless, the role of the contract and courts are significant in the Program’s efficacy. Specifically, the relational contract with its associated informal sanctions (e.g., trade group exclusion and reputational harm) can help to explain how it has achieved such success without resorting to the local courts. Although impossible to prove definitively with only case studies, the legal contract and its associated formal sanctions also appear to be advantageous to the WSR program. In particular, the relational aspect of contract depends on its formalization to establish a cost-reducing mechanism and serve as a signal of trustworthiness between the signatories. These findings are premised on the idea that the signatories have a perception of trust in the effectiveness of the local courts to enforce their WSR contract.

The other main finding is that the contract and arbitration structures, as well as the private international concerns of jurisdiction, applicable law, and enforceability are particularly important for WSR that governs global value chains. That is, the transnational nature of a WSR contract that intends to govern signatories from multiple legal jurisdictions appears to multiply its chances of failure. The case study of the Accord indicates that the WSR leadership might have been able to mitigate the chances of such failure by taking certain steps to ensure a mutually beneficial, cooperative public-private interaction.

Proponents of WSR, then, should contend and think strategically about the extent and richness of existing inspectorates and rules prior to its inauguration, as well as the willingness of local public institutions to establish a coordinative or cooperative relationship with the WSR regime. Moreover, when the governed value chain is a transnational one, proponents must

have an in-depth knowledge of the state's treatment of private international law issues that will determine WSR's enforceability and interaction with the state. These include the state's ratification of the New York Convention, its contract law's adoption of the UNCITRAL Model Arbitral Rules, and local acts and precedent that determine the incompatibility of a foreign award or judgment based on foreign applicable law.

Private actors also influence the public-private interaction, determining whether their actions will be conducive to WSR. There are several steps that WSR proponents can take to attempt to mitigate the chances of a competitive interaction with local courts and officials, and instead to encourage a coordinative interaction. The WSR program may opt for local court adjudication for primary disputes between the signatories, where practicable, and attempt to ensure that the suppliers are recognized members in the WSR relational and legal contracts (e.g., by contractually providing for their ability to seek external review). Additionally, the WSR contract should attempt to set clear expectations regarding the winding-down or termination of the WSR program, so as to avoid uncertainty that may lead to a hostile public-private interaction.

In conclusion, contract and surrounding legal structures, particularly the courts, in the WSR environment indeed can facilitate WSR's ability to succeed, but they may also hinder it. The findings herein indicate that workers, their allies, and other stakeholders must become intimately familiar with not only the market organization and value chain dynamics in a prospective location for WSR, but also the legal contract structures therein. Although WSR is a private governance regime that is mostly self-regulatory, it is still a contract-based mechanism reliant on the power of contract law and contractual relationships. None of the recommendations I have provided here are simple adaptations that will ensure that a WSR initiative succeeds. The findings and recommendations do, however, make a concrete contribution to a growing body of literature examining the legal background conditions and structures that WSR needs to prosper.

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Appendix A

Glossary of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Accord	The Accord on Fire and Safety in Bangladesh
Alliance	The Alliance for Bangladesh Worker Safety
BGMEA	Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association
BIAC	Bangladesh International Arbitration Centre
CIW	Coalition of Immokalee Workers
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DIFE	Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments
DVC	Domestic value chain
EEOC	Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (U.S.)
FFA	Fair Food Agreement
FFP	The Fair Food Program
FFSC	Fair Food Standards Council
GJP	Gender Justice Program
GVC	Global value chain
ILO	International Labour Organization
Labour Caucus	The group of workers' representatives in the Accord—the two global union federations and eight local Bangladeshi unions
MD	Milk with Dignity
MSI	Multi-stakeholder Initiative
NAP	(Bangladesh) National Action Plan on Fire Safety
NLRA	National Labor Relations Act of 1935 (U.S.)
PCA	Permanent Court of Arbitration
RMG	Ready Made Garment (Industry)
SC	Steering Committee
UNCITRAL	United Nations Commission on International Trade Law
WSR	Worker-driven Social Responsibility

Appendix B

**Liberty Fashion Wears Ltd. v. Bangladesh Accord Foundation, Writ No. 10929,
37 High Ct. Div. 255, 6CLR, 1 (2016).**

(Begins on the following page)

IN THE SUPREME COURT OF BANGLADESH
HIGH COURT DIVISION
(SPECIAL ORIGINAL JURISDICTION)

Writ Petition No. 10929 of 2015

-AND-

IN THE MATTER OF

An application under Article 102 of the Constitution
of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

-AND-

IN THE MATTER OF:

Liberty Fashion Wears Limited

.... Petitioner

-Versus-

Bangladesh Accord Foundation and others
..... Respondents

Mr. Qumrul Haque Siddique with

Mr. Imtiaz Moinul Islam

.....for the petitioner.

Mr. K.S. Salah Uddin Ahmed

.....for the respondent No. 1

Mr. Azinalul Hossain QC with

Mr. Foyez Uddin Ahmed and

Mr. Sulhan Khan

...for the respondent Nos. 2 and 3

Mr. Md. Yousuf Ali

...for the respondent Nos. 4 and 5

Ms. Amatul Karim, D.A.G with

Mr. A.R.M. Hasanzaman A.A.G. and

Mr. Abu Saleh Md. Fazle Rabbi A.A.G.

.....for the Respondents

Heard on 17.07.2016

Judgment on 01.09.2016, 04.09.2016

and 06.09.2016

Present:

Mr. Justice Tariq ul Hakim

and

Mr. Justice Md. Faruque (M. Faruque)

Tariq ul Hakim, J.

On an application under Article 102 of the Constitution by the petitioner Rule Nisi was issued calling upon the Respondent No.1 to show cause why it should not be directed to circulate the name of the petitioner as a compliant garment-manufacturing factory amongst its members all over the world and/or pass such other or further order or orders as to this Court may seem fit and proper.

In the midst of hearing of the Rule on another application of the petitioner, a Supplementary Rule was also issued on the Respondent No.1 to show cause why it should not be directed to immediately arrange for inspection of the factory of the petitioner as per Clause 10 of the Accord agreement in accordance with all necessary protocols and publish the inspection report in its website and/or pass such other or further order or orders as this Court may seem fit and proper.

The case of the petitioner is that it is a private limited company incorporated under the Companies Act, 1994, engaged in the business of manufacturing readymade garments. The factory of the petitioner comprises three buildings, plant and machineries valued at about Taka 120 crore. It was established in the year 2001 and about 5000 workers directly depended on it for their livelihood. In 2013 the petitioner made a gross annual income of about Taka 200 crore by manufacturing and exporting readymade garments to European and American buyers including the respondent No.2 Primark, Debenhams, Target, K-mart and other well known brands/ companies .

The respondent No.1 Bangladesh Accord Foundation (hereafter referred to as Accord) is registered in the Netherlands with the primary objective of ensuring fire and building safety in the garments factories of Bangladesh for a period of five years pursuant to an agreement amongst its members under the name and style "Accord on fire and building safety in Bangladesh" (hereafter referred to as the Accord Agreement). The signatories to the Accord Agreement are more than 150 apparel corporations including the respondent No.2, 2(two) global trade unions, eight Bangladeshi trade unions and the International Labour Organization (ILO). The Accord Agreement was signed on 13.5.2013 after the Rana Plaza disaster where 1129 people died and the Tazreen Garments devastating fire of 24.11.2012. The Ministry of Labour and Employment of the Government of Bangladesh also formed a National Tripartite Committee, respondent No.4, with the owners of garments factories and Labour Organizations and adopted a National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA or NAP) to ensure fire and building safety in garments factories. The committee in their joint statements welcomed assistance from stakeholders (foreign garments buyers International Development Organizations, donors etc.) wanting to help improve the fire and building safety conditions in garment factories in Bangladesh leading to the setting up of the Accord Foundation by European Buyers.

Similar to Accord, American buyers of Bangladeshi garments formed an Association under the name and style "Alliance" with objectives similar to "Accord on fire and building safety in Bangladesh". They also entered into an agreement among themselves with similar objectives like the Accord Agreement. There is an unwritten understanding between Accord and Alliance that the inspection report of Accord regarding the infrastructural fire and building safety conditions of a particular garments factory in Bangladesh would be accepted by Alliance and vice-versa. Thus if a negative report is published either by Accord or Alliance in its website, the members of both Accord and Alliance stops sourcing ready made garments from that factory and in effect the whole world stops taking goods from such a factory. Both Accord and Alliance committed themselves to work under the platform created by the respondent No. 4 National Tripartite Committee (NTC) to ensure fire and building safety measures pursuant to the National Tripartite Action Plan (NAP) as stakeholders. The Accord agreement came into effect on 23.5.2013.

After the collapse of Rana Plaza, foreign buyers of readymade garments from Bangladesh became concerned about fire and safety hazards in garment factories in the country and the respondent No.2 appointed the respondent No.3 Medway Consultancy Services to inspect the factory of the petitioner. The respondent No.2 and 3 visited the factory of the petitioner on 18.5.2013 and 25.5.2013 and after a cursory visual inspection, the

respondent No.3 reported that there was a serious structural weakness in the main production building i.e. building No. 2. The same building however was reported to be safe by the respondent No.2 in an earlier report dated 28.06.2012. The respondent No.3's report stated that the slab of each floor is only just able to support its own weight and that the weight of workers or equipment on each floor is likely to cause one of these floors to collapse. Should one floor collapse, the extra weight on the floor will cause the building to progressively collapse. This was a complete surprise to the petitioner and he immediately requested the Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers & Exporters Association (BGMEA) to inspect the said building. The engineers of BGMEA certified that the aforesaid building no. 2 was safe vide their letter dated 10.06.2013. Thereafter the petitioner engaged Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (hereinafter referred to as the BUET) which is the most reputable Institution on civil engineering in the country and they also by their letter dated 29.06.2013 certified that the petitioner's buildings may be used with caution but minor retrofitting work should be done to make the building better. Thereafter the petitioner, at the insistence of the respondent no. 1, took advice from one Ali Asgar & Associates, a renowned engineering firm who also confirmed that the building may be used for production. Thereafter on 11.06.2013 the Respondent No.2 along with Primark (an apparel Corporation based in UK and the Respondent No.3 went to the petitioner's factory and compelled the

petitioner to shut down building no. 2 completely. After the petitioner's factory was shut down the petitioner wrote several letters to the Respondent No. 2 to review their decision but the respondents insisted that the petitioner submit proposals for retrofitting. The petitioner submitted retrofitting proposals prepared by Ali Asgar and Associates but the respondent no. 1 asked for Professional Indemnity Insurance (PII) from Ali Asgar and Associates amounting to 10 Million Pounds Sterling but that engineering firm was not willing to provide the indemnity Insurance nor did any other Engineering Consultancy Company agreeable to do so. The petitioner accordingly requested Accord to withdraw the condition of Professional Indemnity Insurance but while negotiations were going on suddenly on 15.10.2013 the Respondent No.1 informed the petitioner that all Accord brands (members of Accord) would terminate their relationship with the petitioner if it did not repair its factory. The petitioner by its letter dated 21.10.2013 and 27.10.2013 offered to comply with the requirements of the Respondent No.1 but requested it to withdraw its demand for the Professional Indemnity Insurance of 10 Million Pound Sterling because the engineering firms of this country were unwilling to provide it.

It is further stated that by this time all buyers cancelled their orders with the petitioner and the petitioner was thrown out of its business but the Respondent No.1 did not bother to inspect the petitioner's factory to determine the actual condition of the buildings. The Government of

Bangladesh intervened in the matter and requested the Respondent No.1 by letter dated 24.11.2013 under the signature of the Senior Assistant Chief, Planning Cell, Ministry of Labour and Employment to inspect the petitioner's factory but the Respondent No.1 by its letter dated 08.12.2013 addressed to the Secretary, Ministry of Labour and Employment of the Government of Bangladesh informed it that the Respondent No.1 had accepted the inspection report of the Respondent No. 3 and did not place the petitioner's factory in its list for inspection.

It is further stated that under Clause 10 of the Accord Agreement the Respondent No.1 is required to arrange inspection of all factories of readymade garments at least once by a Safety Inspector appointed by Accord to determine its safety standard but the Respondent No.1 has been refusing to inspect the petitioner's factory. On the other hand Accord published the name of the petitioner's factory in its web site as non compliant and risky causing buyers all over the world to refrain from placing orders for ready made garments to the petitioner's factory. It is further stated that although the Respondent No.1 undertook to work in sync with the NTPA i.e. the Respondent No. 4 but the Respondent No.1 has refused to listen to the requests made by the Government of Bangladesh to inspect the petitioner's factory pursuant to clause 10 of the Accord Agreement resulting in complete shut down of the petitioner's factory causing it substantial financial loss. The petitioner again wrote to the Respondent No.1 on 30.4.2014 and

4.5.2014 to inspect its factory and the BGMEA vide their email dated 08.09.2014 also requested the Respondent No.1 to inspect the condition of the petitioner's factory. Similarly the Inspector General (Additional Secretary of the Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments) i.e. respondent No. 5, by its letter dated 14.9.2014 also requested the Respondent No. 1 to inspect the petitioner's factory but the Respondent No.1 has continuously refused to inspect it. The petitioner sent a Notice for Demand of Justice through its learned Advocate to the respondents on 27.10.2014 (Annexure L) to inspect the petitioner's factory but the said respondents did not bother to take any steps or even reply to the said notice.

It is further stated that (the International Labour Organization (ILO) appointed) TUV SUD, a Bangladeshi private limited company inspected the petitioner's factory on the recommendation of BGMEA and found it to be absolutely safe and satisfactory. Thereafter the BGMEA again wrote to the Respondent No.1 on 12.08.2015 to inspect the petitioner's factory but the said respondent continued to ignore the request of every one. It is also stated that Clause 10 of the Accord Agreement imposes a duty upon the Respondent No.1 to inspect the petitioner's factory as it is a supplier of readymade garments to many of signatories of the Accord Agreement but the persistent refusal of the Respondent No.1 to inspect the petitioner's factory and publication of a false report in its website about the petitioner's factory being risky and unsafe has made the petitioner bankrupt and having no other

alternative remedy it has been compelled to come to this Court and obtain the present Rule.

In a Supplementary Affidavit on behalf of the petitioner it has been further stated that BUET after inspecting the petitioner's factory submitted its report on 29.6.2013 making seven recommendations and corrective works and the petitioner complied with the said recommendations .

The Respondents are contesting the Rule by filing separate Affidavits-in-Opposition.

The Respondent No.1 Accord in its Affidavit-in-Opposition has denied the material allegations against it and stated inter alia that the Accord Agreement was signed in May, 2013 by global apparel companies, international retailers, two global trade unions and eight Bangladeshi trade union Federations. The agreement is designed to make RMG factories in Bangladesh safe and sustainable. Accord was established in the Netherlands with its liaison office in Bangladesh with permission from the Board of Investment to implement commitments of the signatory companies towards making their supplier RMG factories in Bangladesh safe. One of its objectives is to provide technical support to the National Tripartite Committee (NTC) but neither the NTC nor Accord has any authority to give directions to each other. Accord has conducted engineering based safety inspections of more than 1400 RMG factories in Bangladesh. Accord and its signatories provide significant technical support and resources to all

the RMG factories to ensure that safety hazards are identified through inspection and are properly corrected and has spent almost 50 million US Dollars over the 5 years of their agreement period for the purpose .

It is further stated that in cases where factory buildings after inspection are found unsafe rectifications are recommended and if a factory owner does not comply , the Respondent No.1 publishes it as non-compliant and since the petitioner's factory was unsafe and the petitioner did not cooperate with the Respondent No. 2 , Accord decided not to source from the petitioner's factory. It is further stated that the members of the Respondent No.1 cannot continue to do business with a factory which does not have a safe building. The petitioner's factory was inspected by the Respondent no. 2 and 3 before the Respondent No.1 opened any office in Bangladesh . Since the inspection was conducted on behalf of a signatory organization of the Respondent No.1, Accord accepted the findings of the Respondent No.3 and considered it as part of its program activities pursuant to clause 10 of the Accord Agreement. As per clause 10 of the Accord Agreement the Respondent No.1 Accord had accepted the report prepared by the Respondent No.3 as it met the standards of thorough and credible inspection. The proviso to Clause 10 of the Accord Agreement is applicable to a situation where the factory has been inspected by any signatory organization and has worked on the rectification plan as per the recommendations suggested by the inspectors. Respondent No.1 is required to make at least

one inspection but the petitioner has not worked on the retrofitting work and was insisting to continue operation in the unsafe building thereby risking the lives of thousands of workers. Several communications were made to the petitioner by the Respondent No.1 to do retrofitting works in its factory building and on one occasion Respondent No.1 even scheduled a visit to the petitioner's factory but when it knew that the retrofitting work had not been done or even started Accord had no option but to cancel its visit because it would be a waste of its valuable funds and time.

It is further stated that Accord even provided funds to pay salaries and bonuses to the petitioner's workers but still the petitioner repeatedly ignored the Respondent No.1's direction to complete retrofitting works of its factory and therefore the said respondent was constrained to declare the petitioner's factory as a non compliant factory. Once a factory is categorized non compliant as per the Accord Agreement the Respondent No.1 has no authority to inspect it as any inspection would be a violation of the agreement amongst the members of Accord. Furthermore such inspection would open the flood gates for other non compliant factories to demand multiple inspections. The petitioner's name was accordingly published in the respondent No. 1's web site as a non compliant factory on 14th October, 2013 and although more than 2 years have elapsed the petitioner has not carried out any retrofitting work in its factory and any inspection by the

Respondent No.1 will be a meaningless exercise involving unnecessary cost and this Rule has no substance and is liable to be discharged.

The Respondent No.2 Tesco in its Affidavit-in-Opposition has stated that in April, 2013 it initiated a program of Structural and Safety Audits of its Bangladeshi supplier factories through an international engineering consultancy firm MCS (Medway Consultancy Services) with offices in the United Kingdom and Bangladesh. On 17.5.2013 the Respondent No.2 Tesco came to know of the petitioner's name appearing in the list of "unapproved facilities" published by another major American retailer, Walmart. Immediately thereafter the Respondent No. 2 Tesco instructed Respondent No.3 MCS to audit the petitioner's factory and to report on the structural safety of the petitioner's factory building. After inspecting the petitioner's factory on two occasions it came to the finding that building no. 2 could not support itself along with the equipment and workers and revealed the risk of structural collapse, technically known as "punching shear failure". The findings and calculations were checked by Fairhurst one of the largest Consulting Engineering Partnerships in the United Kingdom as well as another independent engineering firm called String Maynard which confirmed the Respondent No.3's findings. The Respondent No.2 thereafter urgently informed the petitioner on 7.6.2013 about the Respondent No.3's report and asked it to evaluate building no. 2 but the petitioner refused to stop production in it. The Respondent No. 2 sent a letter to BGMEA on

07.06.2013 informing it about the critical safety risks at the petitioner's factory and asked it to take immediate action to protect employees working there. The Respondent No.2's representative during its factory visit on 11.6.2015 also recommended relocating the sewing machines to the ground floor of other buildings at the site for safety of the workers in the endangered building.

It has also been stated that the Respondent No.1 Accord does not represent Tesco since Accord is an independent entity with its own independent press office. Tesco did not participate in or cause the publication of any report published by Accord. Tesco informed Accord about Respondent No.3's report and findings and Accord chose not to reassess the same in exercise of its own discretion and judgment. Tesco did not participate in the decision making process pertaining to the conditions imposed by Accord on the petitioner. The persistent failure by the petitioner to take remedial action in its buildings led the Respondent No.2 to stop taking readymade garments from the petitioner. Although the petitioner has claimed no relief against the Respondent No.2, the relief claimed by the petitioner if granted would amount to licensing a non compliant building as compliant without making the factual assessment of the conditions of the factory building.

The Respondent No.3 in its Affidavit-in-Opposition has stated that in April, 2013 the Respondent No.3 was appointed by the Respondent No.2 Tesco to carry out inspection of all its Bangladeshi suppliers' factories

under its program of Structural and Safety Audits following the Rana Plaza disaster. The petitioner's factory was inspected by the Respondent No.3 on two occasions, on 18.05.2013 and 03.06.2013 by a team of the Respondent No.3 led by Mr. I. A. Khan OBE, a British national and a Chartered Civil engineer from the United Kingdom. Inspection revealed various faults in building no. 2 of the petitioner's factory specially relating to the load carrying capacity of the floor slabs. Building No. 2 was of flat slab construction without beams supported on columns. On physical measurement, it was apparent that the thickness of the slab was less than that required by the Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC). Moreover, the use of brick aggregate for the concrete slab raised further concern. The findings of the Respondent No.3 were checked by two other consultancy firms in the United Kingdom, Fairhurst and String Maynard who agreed with the calculations. The said respondent requested the petitioner to stop production at building no. 2 but the petitioner refused to do so. It is further stated that the said respondent is not a member of Accord and has no role in Accord's decision making process and did not participate or cause the publication of any report that may have been published by Accord. It is further stated that the instant Writ Petition involves a number of disputed questions of fact and calls for an adjudication on the basis of inspection and since no relief has been claimed against the Respondent No.3 by the

petitioner there is no legal basis for making the Respondent No.3 a party in the instant Writ Petition.

The respondent No. 4 Secretary, Ministry of Labour and Respondent No. 5, Inspector General of Factories, in their separate Affidavits-in-Opposition, have stated that pursuant to the third meeting of the National Tripartite Committee (NTC) the representative of the International Labour Organization (ILO) arranged a consultation meeting with Accord and Alliance and as per their suggestions a team from the Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET) prepared a revised version of the Operation Manual (OM) for assessing the infra-structural integrity and fire safety of readymade garments buildings in Bangladesh which was endorsed by the said meeting. In a subsequent meeting of the National Tripartite Committee (NTC) it was decided that the evaluation and recommendations of Accord and Alliance on readymade garments factories will be subject to review by a Review Panel formed under the said Operation Manual (OM). In the case of the petitioner however since the recommendation for closure of the petitioner's factory was not made by Accord, Alliance or BUET, the same was not subject to review by the Review Panel. The respondent No.1 found the assessment of the petitioner's factory by Primark and Tesco as credible and accepted it as an inspection under its own program and accordingly on 14.10.2013 and 24.10.2013 published a summary of the aforesaid inspection report in their website and declared the petitioner's

factory as a non complaint manufacturing facility. It is further stated that they welcomed Accord's initiative to assess the infrastructure of garments factories in Bangladesh under the National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) framework using the Operational Manual developed by the National Tripartite Committee (NTC) under the monitoring and review system of the National Tripartite Committee (NTC). However the inspection conducted by Tesco and Primark of the petitioner's factory was not a specific inspection under the National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) framework and therefore the office of the respondent No.4 by its letter dated 24.11.2013 requested Accord to include the name of the petitioner's factory in the list of factories for inspection by it. The respondent No.5 also sent a similar request by their letter dated 24.9.2014 but Accord did not comply with any of the aforesaid requests.

It is further stated that there is no formal agreement between the respondent Nos. 4 and 5 with Accord and Alliance apart from the Operation Manual (OM) and the National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) and therefore the said respondent cannot exercise any authority on the respondent No.1 for any of its activities outside the scope of the National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) framework. Furthermore, the said respondent does not have the authority to compel the respondent No.1 to inspect a particular factory including the petitioner's factory if it is unwilling to do so as there is no binding agreement with the respondent No.1. After

introduction of the provision for review in the Operation Manual (OM) on 28.01.2014 in cases of recommendations for evacuation or closure of factories by Accord or Alliance the decision will be subject to automatic review by the Review Panel of which the respondent Nos. 4 and 5 are members. In the instant case since the inspection of the petitioner's factory was not conducted by the respondent no. 1 Accord and it was done before the creation of the Review Panel, the respondents cannot compel the Respondent No.1 to inspect the petitioner's factory

Mr. Qumrul Haque Siddique, appearing with Mr. Imtiaz Moinul Islam, the learned Advocates for the Petitioner submit that the respondent No.1 has acted arbitrarily without any legal basis in publishing the name of the petitioner in its website as a unsafe and non compliant factory prompting foreign buyers to stop placing orders to the petitioner's garments factory and therefore causing it to be shut down. He has become bankrupt due to the arbitrary and unlawful action of the Respondent No. 1 and his fundamental right to profession, trade and business as guaranteed by Article 40 of the Constitution has been infringed. The learned Advocates further submits that the respondent No.1 without inspecting the petitioner's factory has published a false and fabricated report about the petitioner's factory. The learned Advocates further submit that the respondent No.1 has embarked upon a policy of 'pick and choose' and although it has inspected over 1400 garments factories in Bangladesh, it has not inspected the petitioner's factory

and therefore the respondent No.1 is also liable for discrimination and is in breach of the equality Clause i.e. Article 27 of our Constitution. The learned Advocates further submit that the respondent No.1 is in breach of its own Rules and standards of operation and the provisions of "Accord on fire and safety in Bangladesh" specifically Clause 10 which requires Accord to inspect all RMG factories supplying foreign buyers at least once by an international reputed independent Factory Inspector causing loss and damage to the petitioner. The learned Advocates further submit that there is no specific contract between the petitioner and the respondent No.1 and as such the petitioner has no remedy under contract or otherwise before a Civil Court or any other forum to compel the respondents to inspect its factory and publish the findings and therefore he has been constrained to invoke the special jurisdiction of this Court under Article 102 of the Constitution. The learned Advocates further submit that the respondent No.1 did not give the petitioner any hearing or opportunity to defend itself and instead of assessing the situation themselves they relied upon a false and fabricated report by a third party and arbitrarily published the petitioner's name in its website as a non compliant Ready Made Garments facility. The petitioner was acting in the public domain performing a public function and its arbitrary unlawful action has caused loss and damage to the petitioner. In this respect the learned Advocates for the petitioner have drawn our attention to the decision

in the English case *R v Panel on Take Overs and Mergers, ex-parte Datafin plc and another 1987 1 All England 564* .

As against this, Mr. K.S. Salah Uddin Ahmed and Mr. Azmalul Hossain QC, the learned Advocates appearing for the respondent Nos.1, 2 and 3 have submitted in one voice that the instant Rule is not maintainable since the action impugned by the petitioner is not by a person performing any function in connection with the affairs of the republic. The learned Advocates further point out that the impugned action is by the respondent No.1, an association of foreign buyers and that they are all private entities for which the petitioner must seek relief elsewhere and cannot invoke the special jurisdiction of this Court under Article 102 of the Constitution .

Mr. K.S. Salah Uddin Ahmed, the learned Advocate for the respondent No.1 further submits that there has been no breach of provision of Article 40 of the Constitution since the petitioner is at liberty to do business with any buyer of the world and supply readymade garments to any company and that the respondent No.1 has merely stated the inspection findings on its website. The learned Advocate further submits that the respondent No.1 requested the petitioner several times to perform retrofitting works to make its factory fit and safe but the petitioner continuously refused to do so and therefore they had no choice but to publish the findings of the inspection report in its website to inform its members which calls for no interference by this Court.

Mr. Azmalul Hossain, the learned Advocate for the respondent Nos. 2 and 3 submits that no relief has been claimed against the said respondents and that their names be struck out from the Writ Petition . The learned Advocate further submits that the respondent No.2 requested the respondent No.3 to conduct certain inspections of the petitioner's factory and the respondent No.3 did so in accordance with the highest standards and submitted their report to the respondent No. 2 who in turn informed the respondent No.1. The learned Advocate further submits that the respondent No.2 does not represent the respondent No.1 in any way and takes no responsibility for the publication of the report in the respondent No.1's website.

Mr. Md. Yousuf Ali, the learned Advocate for the respondent Nos. 4 and 5 submits that there is no binding agreement between the said respondents and the petitioner and although they cannot compel it to inspect any readymade garments factory nevertheless they requested the respondent No.1 on several occasions to inspect the petitioner's factory but it did not comply. The learned Advocate further submits that after incorporating the provision for review any inspection conducted by the respondent No.1, is subject to review by a Review Panel at the request of an aggrieved party but in the instant case since the inspection was conducted prior to the inclusion of the provision for review on 28.1.2014 and since the inspection was not conducted by the respondent No.1 therefore the decision of the Respondent

No. 1 to publish the name of the petitioner as a non compliant factory could not be reviewed by the Review Panel.

We have considered the submissions of the learned Advocates and perused the averments and the Annexures.

Since maintainability of this Rule has been challenged by the learned Advocates for the respondent Nos. 1,2 and 3 on the ground that the impugned action was not performed by a person in the service of the Republic we will address this point first .

Article 102 of the Constitution states:

- 1) *"The High Court Division on the application of any person aggrieved, may give such directions or orders to any person or authority, including any person performing any function in connection with the affairs of the Republic, as may be appropriate for the enforcement of any of the fundamental rights conferred by Part III of this constitution.*
- 2) *The High Court Division may, if satisfied that no other equally efficacious remedy is provided by law-*
 - (a) *on the application of any person aggrieved, make an Order –*
 - (i) *directing a person performing any functions in connection with the affairs of the Republic or of a local authority to refrain from doing that which he is not permitted by law to do or to do that which he is required by law to do; or*
 - (ii) *declaring that any act done or proceeding taken by a person performing functions in connection with the affairs of the Republic or of a local authority has been done or taken without lawful authority and is of no legal effect ;or*
 - (b) *on the application of any person, make an order-*
 - (i) *directing that a person in custody be brought before it so that it may satisfy itself that he is not being held in custody without lawful authority or in an unlawful manner; or*
 - (ii) *requiring a person holding or purporting to hold a public office to show under what authority he claims to hold that office.*
 - (iii) *.....*

A plain reading of the aforesaid provision of the Constitution shows that pursuant to Article 102(1) this Court is empowered to give directions or orders to any person or authority for the enforcement of any aggrieved person's fundamental rights .

Generally to maintain an application under Article 102(1) the impugned action must be by a person who is in the service of the Republic or a statutory body or a local authority . The language of Article 102(1) however clearly states that a person must be aggrieved by the action or order of "any person" including a person acting in connection with the affairs of the Republic. Thus it is not necessary for the impugned act or order to be done or made by a public functionary or statutory body or local authority for Article 102(1) to be attracted. When fundamental rights of a person is infringed the remedy under Article 102(1) is available to the aggrieved person irrespective of whether he is in the service of the Republic, local authority, statutory body or even a private capacity.

In the case of ***Moulana Md. Abdul Hakim Vs. the Government of Bangladesh and others reported in 34 BLD (HCD)(2014) 34*** it has been held "when issues of fundamental rights are raised, the sanction under Article 102(1) is clearly of availability of redress against "anyone", or "any authority", inclusive of any person performing any function in connection with the affairs of the Republic. The reference to government functionaries

must accordingly be seen as an appendage made to the broader category of "anyone" or "any authority" by way of abundant caution."

Similarly in an unreported decision of this Court in Writ Petition No. 2499 of 2010 in the case Rokeya Akter Begum Vs. Bangladesh and others it has been held "as far as Article 102(1) is concerned i.e. when fundamental rights are relied on, the question of status of the impugned person or authority loses its relevance because the phrases "any person or authority" in the said sub-Article necessarily refers to a person or any authority, irrespective of his/it's status. Decisions by such a person or any authority, whether he /it is a public functionary or a private one, is hence reviewable, provided however, that infringement of one of the fundamental rights, figured in Part III of the Constitution, is in question. In so far as such a person need not be a public functionary, little complication arises in fundamental rights oriented cases."

In *Rajuk Vs. A. Rouf Chowdhury and others in 61 DLR (AD) 28* it has been held when violation of fundamental right as enumerated in the Constitution is the only ground and no violation of legal right or law has been alleged whatsoever resort may be taken under Article 102 of the Constitution. This decision of the Appellate Division establishes that when any violation of fundamental rights enumerated in Part III of the Constitution is established, this Court may issue appropriate orders provided the aggrieved person has no other alternative remedy before any other court. Thus it appears when

infringement of fundamental rights is alleged, this Court under Article 102(1) can give directions to any person or authority irrespective of whether he is in the service of the Republic or not for redress of the aggrieved person's loss or grievance.

The question however as to when a person is performing functions in connection with the affairs of the Republic has caused considerable concern in many countries of the world where the common law is practiced resulting in considerable jurisprudence.

Since private bodies are increasingly performing public functions the courts are intervening and passing appropriate directions and orders reviewing the action, inaction and functions of private bodies. The Courts regulate their discretion by looking at the nature of the function exercised by the private bodies and by scrutinizing whether the body is acting in the public domain and whether the aggrieved person has any other alternative efficacious remedy. This view has also been confirmed in the Indian case of *Board of Control for Cricket V. Cricket Association of Bihar and others AIR 2015 SC 3194*.

In the Landmark English case *R v Panel on Take Overs and Mergers, ex-parte Datafin plc and another reported in 1987 1 All England Reports 564* the Court of Appeal held that where a public duty is imposed on a body, expressly or by implication, or where a body exercises public functions the court will have jurisdiction to entertain an application for judicial review of that body's decision. There is no single test however as to what is public

function. The source of the body's power is a significant factor; if it is by an Act of Parliament or subordinate legislation then the body's action will be subject to judicial review. On the other hand, if the decision of the body is derived solely from contract its decision will not be amenable to judicial review. In such cases the Court will try to decide whether the impugned action has been performed in the public domain in which case the court is likely to infer that the decision has been taken in connection with the affairs of the Republic. A government element may also appear where governmental functions are carried out by private bodies. By contrast, when the nature of the function is such that it does not generate any interest of the Government then the body's action will not be subject to judicial review. Thus not only the source of the power of the body but also the nature of the action exercised by it will determine the availability of judicial review. It also appears that when a private sector body steps into the shoes of a public body then its action will be amenable to judicial review. In *Shri Anadi Mukta Sadguru S.M.V.S.J.M.S. Trust v. V. R. Rudani reported in AIR 1989 SC 1607* it has been held :

"The judicial control over the fast expanding maze of bodies affecting the rights of the people should not be put into watertight compartments. It should remain flexible to meet the requirements of variable circumstances. Mandamus is a very wide remedy which must be easily available to reach injustice wherever it is found. Technicalities should not come in the way of granting that relief under Article 226."

In the case of *Consumer Education and Research Centre and others Vs. Union of India and others reported in AIR 1995 (SC) 922* the Supreme Court of India held that in an appropriate case, the Court would give appropriate directions to the employer be it the State or private employer to make the right to life meaningful; to prevent pollution of work place; protection of the environment; protection of the health of the workmen or to preserve free and unpolluted water for the safety and health of the people. The authorities or even private persons or industry are bound by the directions issued by the Supreme Court under Article 32 and Article 142 of the Constitution. In the aforesaid case the Supreme Court issued mandamus upon a private industry for the enforcement of the petitioner's fundamental rights .

In the *Datafin* case Lloyd L.J. held

"If the body in question is exercising public law functions or if the exercise of its functions have public law consequences, then that may be sufficient to bring the body within the reach of judicial review. It may be said that to refer to public law in this context is to beg the question. But I do not think it does. The essential distinction, which runs through all the cases to which we referred, is between a domestic or private tribunal on the one hand and a body of persons who are under some public duty on the other".

In Bangladesh the responsibility for inspecting factories and their safety vests on the Inspector General of Factories i.e. respondent no. 5. This is

conferred by sections 61 and 62 of the Bangladesh Labour Law, 2006 which provide as follows:

“Sec.-61: Safety of the building and the machinery. - (1) If any inspector deems it necessary that any building or any of its part or any of its passage, machinery or plant is in such condition that it is dangerous to life or security of man then he shall by a written order direct to take the necessary steps within the specified time.

(2) If it deems to any inspector that any building of any factory or establishment is very dangerous to life or safe of man then he shall, by written order to the owner restrict their of such building or part of a building until the repairment or re-shaping.

Sec.-62: Precautions about fire. - In every factory at least one exit way with each floor must be attached so that at the time of fire accident it can be used as a substitute way and necessary provision for extinguishing fire should be taken.

(2) If any inspector deems it fit that as per sub-section (1) there is no means of exit, then he shall, by an order writing to the owner inform him to take necessary steps within the stated period of time.

(3) In every factory or establishment no exit way from the room shall be made under lock and key so that every man working inside it can get easily open and all three type of doors, if not sliding type, shall be made in such way so that it is kept open outward or if any door is between the two rooms, it must be kept open clear to the exit way and no such door shall be kept under lock and key at the working hour.

(4) Every passage for exit must be used except the exit during the time of fire accident and every such window door or any other exit must be worked with red letters.

(5) To aware or whistle the workers in such establishment the provision for easily audible whistle must be maintained in for each working workers.

(6) For all the workers of the factory of each establishment there shall be made an exit way for all at the time of fire accident.

(7) In any factory or establishment where in any above place of the ground floor ten or more workers one working or explosive or easily inflammable substance

is used or is stored then the workers shall be cautions about the incident of fire and can determine what they should do at that time and so that they can take proper and full-fledged training and so why necessary steps should also be taken for it.

(8) In every factory and establishment having fifty or more workers a rehearsal of extinguishing of fire shall be maintained and for this reason a record book must be preserved by the owner.”

The work of checking and inspecting the safety conditions of all readymade garments factories in the country within a short time after the Rana Plaza tragedy was not possible for the Government. The Government therefore welcomed the assistance of other stake-holders like Accord and Alliance through the National Tripartite committee (respondent No.4) and the National Tripartite Plan of Action (NTPA) in this regard. The agreement of the respondent no. 1 Accord states that all Bangladeshi garments factories supplying its members would be inspected at least once by an independent Safety Inspector appointed by the respondent No.1. The commitment of the respondent No.1 to inspect fire and safety facilities of readymade garments factories in Bangladesh at their own expenses is no doubt a welcome step for the improvement and development of the infrastructure of garments factories in the country. In the process they are assisting the Inspector General of Factories of the Government in ensuring fire and building safety of readymade garments factories in the country. Respondent No.1 has accordingly inspected over 1500 garments factories in the country and found some of them to be non compliant and lacking

adequate facilities on fire and building safety. Thus it is apparent that the respondent No.1 has been acting with the consent of the Inspector General of factories and assisting it in inspecting and ensuring the safety of the garments factories in the country and therefore performing functions" in connection with the affairs of the Republic".

Furthermore the Respondent No 1 has been performing a public function and acting in the public domain. The facts seem to be similar to the aforesaid Datafin case. Thus the petitioner's application under Article 102(1) is maintainable on this ground as well.

In the instant case the petitioner's right to profession trade and business as guaranteed by Article 40 of the Constitution has been infringed by the arbitrary act of the Respondent No.1 in publishing/showing the name of the petitioner as a non compliant and unsafe garments factory in its website without inspecting it and therefore in the opinion of this Court the Rule is not only maintainable under Article 102(1) but has substance.

For Article 102 (2) to be attracted however the petitioner must be aggrieved by an action of a person performing functions "in connection with the affairs of the Republic", or local authority or statutory body and he should be without any other alternative remedy or redress. The remedy sought by the petitioner is simply a direction on the Respondent No.1 for inspecting the petitioner's factory and publishing the findings in its website. If the petitioner's factor is unsafe and not fit in any way then the Respondent No.1

has nothing to loose. The petitioner cannot seek remedy from the Civil Court or any other forum in the form of a direction since there is no contractual relationship with the respondent No.1. Similarly an action for defamation also will not serve any purpose since the petitioner wants the Respondent No.1 to publish the accurate condition of its factory. Thus to compel the Respondent No. 1 to inspect its factory and publish the findings in its website the petitioner does not appear to have any other alternative remedy. In such view of the matter therefore this Rule is also maintainable unde Article 102 (2).

In the instant case it is admitted that the respondent No.1 never inspected the petitioner's factory but relied upon a report submitted by the respondent No.3 who inspected the petitioner's factory at the request of the respondent No.2 on 18.5.2013 after Accord was created although Clause 10 of the Accord Agreement clearly stipulates that all garments factories would be inspected by an independent internationally reputed Inspector appointed by Accord. The petitioner's factory was never inspected by an Inspector appointed by the Respondent No.1 despite several requests by the petitioner and the Government. The respondent no. 1 without inspecting the petitioner's factory published its name in its website and stated it to be a non compliant and unsafe factory resulting in adverse publicity of the petitioner's garments factory causing all European buyers not only to cancel their existing orders but also refrain from giving future orders to the petitioner factory. Due to

the adverse report of the respondent No.1 in its website even American buyers of readymade garments represented by Alliance refrained from giving orders to the petitioner causing it huge financial and economic loss and driving it to bankruptcy.

The contention of the respondents that the petitioner's factory was not inspected by the Respondent No. 1 as it did not comply with its report to make certain structural improvements of its factory building is misconceived since there is no such precondition for inspecting a factory in the Accord Agreement and therefore the arbitrary insistence of such condition prior to inspecting the petitioner's factory is illegal and not sustainable in law. Furthermore, in the inspection report of the respondent No.3 although certain apprehensions have been expressed regarding safety of the petitioner's factory, no specific and detailed corrective measures was suggested and therefore the petitioner was justified in requesting the inspection of his factory by the respondent No.1 or its appointed Safety Inspector to specify the nature of correctional works required for the petitioner's factory so that compliance may be made to the satisfaction of the said respondent. The arbitrary imposition of pre-conditions by the respondent No.1 for inspecting the petitioner's factory and publishing a report containing adverse remarks in its website has caused serious damage and loss to the petitioner which could have been easily avoided by the respondent No.1 by merely inspecting it as it did in the case of other garments factories. This

policy of pick and choose, of inspecting some factories and not inspecting the petitioner's factory cannot be condoned or approved by any standard of fairness. The Respondent No.1 Accord was acting in concert with the Inspector General of Factories of the Government of Bangladesh through the National Tripartite Action Committee to ensure the safety of ready made garments factories in Bangladesh and therefore the Respondent No.1 was acting in connection with the affairs of the Republic. Their failure to act in accordance with law, by publishing a report in their website about the petitioner's factory without inspecting it is a breach of Clause 10 of their own agreement and the action may be subject to judicial review under Article 102(2) of the Constitution also.

The submission by the learned Advocate for the respondent No.1 that if a direction is given to the respondent No.1 to inspect the petitioner's factory it will open up the floodgates for other non compliant factories to come to this Court and obtain similar orders is misconceived since it has not been denied that the petitioner is the only factory whose name has been published on the respondent No.1's website as a non compliant factory without inspecting it. Had the petitioner's factory been inspected it could seek relief before the Review Panel. Other non compliant factories therefore have every opportunity to review the decision by the Review panel.

It is not for this court to decide whether the petitioner's factory is safe for manufacturing garments or direct any particular foreign buyer to place orders with the petitioner. The foreign buyers are free to decide where to place their orders and from which source to procure their products; what this court is concerned about is that the petitioner's name should not be published in the website of the Respondent No.1 as a non compliant/ unsafe factory without any prior inspection in accordance with the terms and conditions enumerated in its own Agreement.

It is to be noted that the respondent No.4 (National Tripartite Committee headed by the Secretary, Ministry of Labour and Employment) as well as the respondent No.5 (Inspector General of Factories of the Government of Bangladesh) requested the respondent No.1 to inspect the petitioner's factory but the request was not complied with and since the respondents did not have any binding contractual relationship with the respondent No.1 they were unable to compel it to comply with their request. The petitioner therefore had no other choice but to approach this court and invoke the special jurisdiction under Article 102 of the Constitution.

The petitioner's application is thus not only maintainable both under Article 102(1) as well as under Article 102(2) and also has substance for the reasons stated above.

Accordingly, the Rule is made absolute.

The respondent No.1 is directed to immediately arrange for inspection of the petitioner's factory as per Clause 10 of the Accord Agreement and other necessary protocols and publish the inspection report in its website and circulate it among its members all over the world.

There will be no order as to costs.

Md. Faruque (M. Faruque), J.

I agree